

MASTER'S DEGREE PROGRAMME

Sustainable Energy Systems

**Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance:
Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and
Mitigating Degradation Effects**

SUBMITTED AS A MASTER THESIS

TO OBTAIN THE ACADEMIC DEGREE OF

MASTER OF SCIENCE IN ENGINEERING (MSC)

by

Soha Essbai

October 2023

Thesis Supervisor

FH-Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Dr. Michael Steinbatz

UNIVERSITY
OF APPLIED SCIENCES
UPPER AUSTRIA
RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT

WELS CAMPUS

SWORN DECLARATION

I hereby declare that I prepared this work independently and without help from third parties, that I did not use sources other than the ones referenced and that I have indicated passages taken from those sources.

This thesis was not previously submitted in identical or similar form to any other examination board, nor was it published. This printed thesis is identical with the electronic version submitted.

.....

Soha Essbai

Wels, October 2023

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I am profoundly grateful to my thesis supervisor, Dr. Rennhofer Marcus at the Austrian Institute of Technology, for his invaluable scientific insights and enriching discussions across various fields. He initiated my journey through an internship and remained a steadfast source of support and mentorship. Equally, I thank Dr. Michael Steinbatz, for his flexibility, understanding, and encouragement, granting me independence. His pivotal role in my admission to the master's program is deeply appreciated. I also extend my heartfelt appreciation to Gusztáv Újvári and Ankit Mittal. Gusztáv's guidance in laboratory work and experimental procedures, coupled with his infectious enthusiasm, made our collaboration productive and enjoyable. Ankit's unwavering assistance, especially with Python codes, enriched my experience and Analytical understanding.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the PROMISE project (GA Nr. 101079469) for their generous support, which has been instrumental in the completion of this work. Their support significantly contributed to my research and the advancement of my goals. Additionally, I extend my appreciation to the ReliaREN-Pro project (FFG Nr. FO999889024) for their valuable assistance and collaboration throughout the course of this project.

And to my beloved parents, words cannot express the depth of my gratitude. You have always put me first and believed in me, even when I doubted myself. Your unwavering love, support, and sacrifices have been the cornerstone of my journey. Every late-night study session, every moment of self-doubt, and every triumph I have achieved is a testament to your enduring belief in me. Your emotional support has carried me through the toughest of times, and I will forever be grateful for your faith in my abilities. I carry your love with me in every step I take towards my dreams.

To my dear sister Rim, you have always been my support system. Your unconditional love, belief in me, and happiness for my achievements mean more to me than words can express. Your encouragement has been a constant source of inspiration, and I am profoundly grateful for your presence in my life. I also want to mention, Malak, and Abdassamad. You are my motivation to create a model of success for you to look up to as you grow. I aspire to be the person you can turn to for guidance and inspiration in the future. Your presence in my life fills me with a sense of purpose and determination.

To my grandparents, and my extended family, who have always prayed for me, your love has shaped me into the person I am today. Your prayers have been a source of strength and inspiration, and I carry the warmth of our family bonds with me, grateful for the roots that ground me.

To my beloved Ghaith, your unwavering support and understanding were my rock throughout this journey. Daily, as I returned from the lab, sometimes worn down with aching muscles and frayed nerves from lifting PV modules, you were my sanctuary. You became my wellspring of motivation and strength. You never faltered in your love and steadfast support. Your presence has been the driving force behind my determination, and I am profoundly moved and grateful for your love, patience, and belief in me.

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to every individual whose support and guidance have played a pivotal role in the successful completion of my master's thesis.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Kurzfassung	V
Abstract	VI
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Motivation	1
1.2 History of PV	2
1.3 Potential of PV	3
2 Theoretical background	5
2.1 Photovoltaic Technology.....	5
2.2 The Physics of Semiconductors	7
2.3 Light and matter	8
2.4 p-n Junction	9
2.5 Air Mass	10
2.6 Standard Conditions (STC)	11
2.7 I-V Curve	12
2.7.1 Four-Point probes Method	13
2.7.2 Norms for IV-curve Measurements.....	14
2.8 characteristics of Solar Cells	15
2.8.1 Dark Characteristics	15
2.8.2 Illuminated Characteristics.....	16
2.9 Characteristics of Current-Voltage.....	17
2.9.1 Short Circuit current.....	17
2.9.2 Open-circuit voltage.....	19
2.10 Different types of solar cells	20
2.11 Metastability in solar modules	22
2.11.1 Light-Induced Degradation (LID).....	22
2.11.2 Staebler-Wronski Effect (SWE).....	22
2.11.3 Bias-Induced Metastability	23
2.11.4 Temperature-Induced Metastability	24
2.11.5 Relaxed state	26
2.12 Metastability models	27
2.12.1 Device-level simulation models	27

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

2.12.2	Defect-related models	28
2.13	Degradation	30
2.13.1	Potential induced degradation	30
2.13.2	Hot Spots	32
2.13.3	Corrosion.....	33
2.13.4	Discoloration	34
2.13.5	Delamination	35
2.13.6	Potential Induced Degradation	36
2.13.7	Cracks and Breakage.....	37
2.13.8	Bubbles.....	37
2.14	Degradation Analysis	39
2.14.1	Visual Inspection.....	39
2.14.2	Infrared Analysis.....	39
2.14.3	I-V curve	40
2.14.4	Electroluminescence.....	40
2.14.5	Thermal Cycling.....	41
2.15	IEC 61215	42
2.16	Computational analysis	42
2.16.1	JMAK Model in PV	42
2.16.2	Arrhenius Model in PV	43
3	Methodology.....	45
3.1	Devices.....	45
3.1.1	I-V Flasher	45
3.1.2	Static Sun Simulator.....	45
3.1.3	Climatic Chamber	46
3.1.4	Electronic Load	46
3.1.5	Electroluminescence Camera	46
3.1.6	Module Samples.....	47
3.2	Comparative test scheme.....	47
3.2.1	Exchange Scheme	49
3.2.2	Out of box measurement	49
3.2.3	Preconditioning standardized	49
3.3	Stabilization Methods.....	50

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

3.3.1	Thermal Treatment.....	50
3.3.2	Light soaking.....	51
3.3.3	Electrical Bias	51
3.3.4	LeTID.....	51
3.4	Module parameters.....	52
3.5	Modules' Response to Stabilization	52
4	Result and Discussion.....	54
4.1	Out of the box measurements.....	54
4.1.1	Isc vs. Voc.....	55
4.1.2	Isc * Voc vs. FF	56
4.1.3	ideal vs. Pmax	57
4.1.4	Sorting of the Modules.....	57
4.2	6.2 MQ19 under MPP	58
4.2.1	First Cycle	59
4.2.2	Second Cycle.....	62
4.2.3	Third Cycle.....	63
4.3	Comparison of MPP's Three light induced stabilization Rounds	65
4.4	Comparison of Fill Factor and Cell efficiency	67
4.5	Further Power comparison	69
4.6	MQ19 open circuit	70
4.6.1	First Cycle	71
4.6.2	Second Cycle.....	72
4.6.3	Third Cycle.....	74
4.7	Comparison of Open Circuit's Three light induced stabilization Rounds.....	77
4.8	Comparison of Fill Factor and Cell efficiency	78
4.9	Further Power comparison	80
4.10	Dark Bias 1.6 Isc	82
4.10.1	First Cycle	83
4.10.2	Second Cycle.....	84
4.10.3	Third Cycle.....	85
4.11	Comparison of Dark Bias 1.6 Isc Rounds	86
4.12	Comparison of Fill Factor and Cell efficiency	89
4.13	Dark Bias 0.6 Isc	90

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

4.13.1	First Cycle	91
4.13.2	Second Cycle.....	92
4.13.3	Third Cycle.....	93
4.14	Comparison of Dark Bias 0.6 Isc Rounds	94
4.15	EL Camera Results.....	98
4.15.1	Module A8	98
4.15.2	Module A13	99
4.15.3	Module A11	102
4.15.4	Module A14	103
4.15.5	Module A6	104
4.15.6	Module A7	105
4.15.7	Module A4	106
4.15.8	Module A15	107
4.16	Time evolution of stabilization	107
4.16.1	MQ19 under MPP	108
4.16.2	MQ19 under OC.....	109
4.16.3	Dark Bias 1.6Isc	112
4.16.4	Dark Bias 0.6Isc	115
4.17	Stabilization criterium	118
5	Conclusion and Discussion.....	121
6	List of Figures	124
7	List of Tables.....	126
8	References.....	127
9	Appendix	138
9.1	Out of the Box Measurement	138
9.1.1	I-V curves.....	138
9.1.2	EL Camera	139

KURZFASSUNG

Die Leistungsbewertung von Photovoltaik (PV) Modulen unter Standardtestbedingungen (STC) dient als grundlegender Maßstab zur Beurteilung der Auswirkungen von beschleunigten Tests und Freiluftbelastung auf deren Leistungsfähigkeit. Allerdings stellen inhärente reversible und metastabile Variationen, die über Zeitspannen von Sekunden bis zu mehreren Tagen auftreten, eine Herausforderung dar, um die STC-Performance in vorherrschenden PV-Systemen genau zu charakterisieren [25]. Diese metastabilen Effekte, die durch beschleunigte Tests beeinflusst werden können, haben das Potenzial, irreversible Degradationen, die aus solchen Tests resultieren, zu imitieren, wenn sie nicht ordnungsgemäß kontrolliert werden.

Das dynamische Zusammenspiel von Zeit, Temperatur, Spannung und lichtabhängigen chemischen und strukturellen Eigenschaften von Solarzellen führt zu unterschiedlichen Merkmalen und Leistungsphasen, die in PV-Modulen aufgrund dieser metastabilen Variationen beobachtet werden. Um einen klaren Kontext für unsere Analyse zu schaffen, müssen bestimmte konzeptionelle Phasen im Zusammenhang mit diesen Variationen geklärt werden.

Unter den Stabilisierungstechniken werden kontinuierliche Beleuchtung und elektrische Vorspannung häufig eingesetzt, um eine erweiterte Exposition gegenüber natürlicher und künstlicher Sonneneinstrahlung zu erreichen. Beachtenswert ist, dass diese Studie den Stabilisierungsstandard gemäß IEC 16215 übernimmt, wobei eine anhaltende Lichteinwirkung genutzt wird. Diese Forschung ist integraler Bestandteil der ReliaREN-Pro-Initiative, die sich um eine internationale Prüfungsbemühung zur Proficiency Testung von im Feld gealterten kristallinen Modulen dreht. Das übergreifende Ziel dieses Projekts besteht darin, die Zuverlässigkeit der Energieerzeugung aus erneuerbaren Quellen durch Fortschritte in der PV-Technologie zu verbessern.

ABSTRACT

The performance evaluation of photovoltaic (PV) modules operating under standard test conditions (STC) serves as a fundamental benchmark for assessing the impact of accelerated testing and outdoor exposure on their performance. However, inherent reversible and metastable variations occurring over timescales ranging from seconds to several days pose challenges to accurately characterizing STC performance in predominant PV systems [25]. These metastable effects, which can be influenced by accelerated testing, have the potential to mimic irreversible degradation resulting from such tests if not properly controlled.

The dynamic interplay of time, temperature, voltage, and light-dependent chemical and structural traits of solar cells leads to diverse characteristics and performance phases observed in PV modules due to these metastable variations. To establish a clear context for our analysis, certain conceptual phases related to these variations need clarification.

Among stabilization techniques, continuous illumination and electric bias have been commonly employed, involving extended exposure to both natural and artificial sunlight. Notably, this study adopts the stabilization standard outlined in IEC 16215, utilizing persistent light exposure and Dark Bias. This research is integral to the ReliaREN-Pro initiative, which entails an international proficiency testing effort centered around harmonized measurement methodologies for field-aged crystalline and Thin Film modules. The overarching aim of this project is to enhance the dependability of renewable energy generation through advancements in PV technology.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

- Al-BSF aluminium back surface field.
- AM air mass.
- ARC anti reflective coating.
- c-Si crystalline silicon.
- EL electroluminescence.
- HDI human developing index.
- HJT heterojunction.
- IEC international electrotechnical commission.
- LeTID light- and elevated temperature-induced degradation.
- LID light induced degradation.
- LS light soaking.
- MQT module quality tests.
- NIR near-infrared.
- PERC passivated emitter and rear contact.
- PV photovoltaic.
- STC standard test condition.
- TA thermal annealing.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods
and Mitigating Degradation Effects

1 INTRODUCTION

Photovoltaic (PV) systems are at pioneering of the energy transformation as a result of the global search for sustainable energy alternatives. PV technology, which makes use of the limitless power of the sun, provides an inexpensive and environmentally responsible alternative to traditional fossil fuels, and could completely change how energy is produced on a worldwide basis. The integration of photovoltaic systems has quickened, driving solar power into mainstream energy markets as governments, industry, and people unify behind the idea of a carbon-neutral future. The successful deployment and operation of solar installations present numerous problems that need for strategic and creative solutions, despite the PV technology's evident potential. Stabilization is one of the most crucial factors affecting the efficiency and durability of PV systems. In order to optimize energy production, maximize return on investment, and foster public confidence in solar energy as a trustworthy energy source, it is crucial to ensure the steady and continuous operation of PV installations throughout their operating lifetime. This master's thesis sets out on a quest to investigate various innovative strategies and approaches to improve system performance and reliability while delving into the dynamic world of PV system stabilization. The main objective of this study is to find efficient stabilization techniques that reduce the difficulties that PV systems inherently confront. This will help solar energy become more advanced and widely used as a cornerstone of the world's sustainable energy supply.

1.1 MOTIVATION

When designing photovoltaic power plants, there are two crucial factors that must be taken into consideration. The first one is the irradiance availability and the second one is the power output of the panels. With constant exposure to light, the performance of the modules tends to alter. Different technologies experience these shifts to varying degrees [23]. The film photovoltaic technology undergoes metastable effects with temporal interval from seconds to days which can affect performance assessments. In contrast to crystalline silicon, which is stable over medium time intervals but in fact it mainly suffers from long-term degradation [87]. Because of these metastabilities, thin-film and crystalline silicon devices must undergo thermal annealing, light soaking, or electric biasing before their power can be monitored. ReliaREN-Pro project's goal is to make

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

crystalline and thin-film PV power plants more available, reliable, and predictable for long-term generation of energy for incorporation into the energy market. Through the development of technologies for automatic identification of failures and research into the effects of degradation on power generation and long-term energy yield, ReliaREN-Pro seeks to encourage the integration of thin-film in PV power plants. On the other hand, concerning Crystalline technology, the project aspires to improve the forecasting and handling of crystalline PV power plants by creating methods to detect degradation in initial stages and long term. Moreover, to forecast the evolution of the long-term energy production as well as the probability of failure.

1.2 HISTORY OF PV

The quantity of solar energy that comes to Earth each year is thousands of times greater than the amount of fuel that is currently accessible. The components necessary to create a PV cell, like as silicon, germanium, etc., are easily obtainable as well. PV is categorized as pollution-free as there are no substances produced by the PV cells that could trigger pollution or lead to loud noises, they can be. A report published in 1877 documented the first PV cell to be used. A selenium solar cell was created in 1883 by Charles Fritts following Walter Schottky's creation of the diode with a semiconductor junction. It was just as common as the silicon PV cell employed nowadays. the efficiency of the first module was below 1%, Consequently, energy production was not possible. A revolutionary semiconductor-based PV cell was created by the Chaplin-Fuller- Pearson team in 1954. They employed silicon slices to make PV cells and were successful in increasing the efficiency to 5%. In the initial stages, these cells were deployed in the field of aerospace and was also incorporated in satellites. One of the most famous satellites that employed PV cells was Vanguard which after 19 days its batteries were discharged but the solar cells started charging them and the satellite was able to complete the mission that lasted for 8 years. In the late twenty century, an oil crisis has happened which have driven people to start looking for alternatives to generate energy. few years later the first financial feasibility study has been done and resulted in the first Pilot PV plant. The PV was only implemented in isolated place that are not connected to the grid [11].

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

1.3 POTENTIAL OF PV

Throughout the development of industry, fossil fuels have significantly increased mankind's productivity. With gas, oil, and coal accounting for 81% of the primary energy sources in the globe, they formed the backbone of the contemporary economy. The Figure 1 shows that in 2010, renewable provided 12% of the global energy needs, and that percentage will rise to 16% by 2040. In contrast, coal, and natural gas will see a reduction from a total of 80% in 2000 to 75% in 2040. To achieve a diminution in GHG emissions by 80% by 2050, EU established the target of further reducing its utilization of fossil fuels [36]. because of its high predictability and ubiquity, solar energy has the potential to play a significant role in the development of future international energy systems. Photovoltaic modules do not add to the greenhouse impact while they are operating, with the exception low emissions produced during manufacturing and decommissioning.

Cost optimization is necessary to realize photovoltaic' highest potential. Previously, PV has been linked to technological obstacles, a lack of production quantity, and financial obstacles particularly the expensive initial expenses for a PV system. Figure 2 illustrates how Photovoltaic modules cost have decreased over time. The average module price (Crystalline and Thin Film) has dropped from approximately 2.5 USD/Wp in 2010 to 0.6 USD/Wp in 2016[21].

Figure 1: Development of world primary energy consumption from 1990 till 2040[12]

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Figure 2: Global PV modules price trend 2009-2016[21]

Over the past 50 years, costs have been reducing in accordance with an empirical statistical rule: the average price of modules decreased by 20% on average for every doubling of installed solar capacity. Swanson's Law refers to this arrangement, which will probably keep going in the future [37]. Photovoltaic energy production became considerably cheaper as a result of this quick decrease in costs. It is currently one of the most economically advantageous methods for producing energy. (JRC) even forecasts that the cost of electricity generated by storage-added household photovoltaic will eventually become less expensive than the cost at retail [38]. Since photovoltaic technology can be easily and quickly implemented, it is aptly called the remorseless strategy. Even if we assume that fossil fuels will be used extensively in the coming years, a significant increase in renewable energy sources is anticipated to be required to fulfil the world's energy needs. The total supply of PV energy will therefore rise in the upcoming years, regardless of the circumstances.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 PHOTOVOLTAIC TECHNOLOGY

Numerous various elements have been utilized for producing solar cells after Edmond Becquerel created the first photovoltaic device in 1839 using selenium. Silicon is currently the most often utilized material.

Crystalline Silicon (C-Si) Monocrystalline or multicrystalline silicon makes up most of the solar cells that are manufactured. The expertise and massive production of silicon for use in microelectronics has greatly aided their creation. In 2011, monocrystalline silicon wafers accounted for 38% of all solar PV modules shipped, while multicrystalline silicon wafers accounted for 51%. mainly, small wafers sliced from monocrystalline ingots manufactured by the Czochralski technique are used to create monocrystalline silicon solar cells. The float zone technique is a substitute; however, it is rarely utilized in industrial production. The process of obtaining the required monocrystalline silicon purity levels is extremely costly, and the result is a product of circle wafers that must be sliced into pseudosquares before being assembled into modules. However, lots of monocrystalline silicon is squandered in order to fill all the module surface with active material. Additionally, the Czochralski process requires high-quality input material. Producing multicrystalline silicon is one technique to lower material prices and material waste. Given their square design, multicrystalline silicon solar cells' 10% lower efficiency than monocrystalline silicon cells may almost entirely be covered up for in modules [3]. These techniques culminate in the production of silicon ingots that must be divided into wafers. Material waste results from this cutting procedure. Studies on "ribbon silicon," in which sheets of silicon are extracted from molten silicon, have been conducted to prevent such losses. Ribbon silicon wafers were once made on a large basis and used to make solar cells, but the technique is not anymore in utilization.

Thin-film solar cells (a-Si) Initial kind of thin film solar cells were amorphous silicon (a-Si) cells. A-Si cells and all other thin film photovoltaic devices have a similar structural design. An a-Si cell's base is a carrier, often made of glass. Zinc peroxide (ZnO_2) is applied in a thin coating over the glass. The silicon is subsequently incorporated by evaporative layer along with its doping agents: A 10nm p-doped layer comes first, then a 10nm buffer layer, and finally the main 500nm amorphous silicon layer. A 20nm n-doped

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

layer is added to the silicon's reverse side. The front and rear surfaces are then connected, often using contacts made of aluminium or silver [54]. Due to the structure of silicon atoms is amorphous, there exists no long-range order and not every silicon atom is linked to the remaining four, the arrangement has a few tiny gaps, as a result of this. Large densities of allowable states are present in the 'forbidden' energy region as a result of these tiny gaps and the extremely irregular structure [27]. Due to the substantial number of possible states, crystalline silicon that is indirect semiconducting transforms into amorphous silicon that is direct semiconducting and does not require an extra phonon to absorb light [92]. A-Si solar cells' primary drawback is their relatively poor efficiency, with a record of 13.4%. This poor value is mostly due to hanging bonds. Silicon that is protocrystalline and microcrystalline is employed to lessen the density of these dangling connections.

Figure 3: Categories of Solar Photovoltaic Technologies

Although protocrystalline silicon has a greater medium range order than a-Si, it lacks a crystal lattice. Nanoscale crystals imbedded in amorphous silicon make up the mixed phase material known as microcrystalline silicon. A-Si, c-Si, and protocrystalline silicon all have distinct band gaps, which makes it simple to combine them to create tandem cells and increase efficiency. The key benefit of a-Si over c-Si is the greater absorption coefficient, which makes it possible for a-Si based cells to have significantly fewer absorbent layers and, consequently, use little silicon, lowering the cost of the cell.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Because a-Si is a direct semiconductor, its greater absorption coefficient is mostly due to this.

2.2 THE PHYSICS OF SEMICONDUCTORS

As two atoms join to make a single molecule, respective atomic orbitals merge to generate sets of molecule orbitals having energy levels that are a little further apart than the initials. Each of the orbitals' dissociation energies is so near together once numerous atoms combine to produce a solid that an infinite range of reachable levels is created. An ideal photovoltaic ought to soak up sunlight. The substance must possess a space between its bands in order to perform this operation. The amount of energy distinction between the highest filled state and the lowest vacant one is what is meant by a band gap. There is a band gap in every semiconducting and insulating substance, however just semiconductors have the proper gap for the absorption of light because the gap in insulators is too large [68] If there were no band disparity, as there is in metals, excited electrons are going to decay over a continuous range of levels because they wouldn't have sufficient time to be captured after they were stimulated. Whenever a band gap exists, a charged electron rapidly decays to the conduction band's lowest energy, an action that requires only a couple of femtoseconds. Shortly later, a slower process causes the recombination to the valence band, allowing the solar cell enough time to remove the electron. An element's atomic properties have an impact on the type of band gap that exists in it. Whenever a pair of atoms join to make a molecule, their individual electron orbitals merge to create the orbitals of the molecule, which have new energy levels. Each atomic orbital breaks into an infinite number of levels, creating a "band" if this procedure continues to create a solid [50]. Furthermore, depending on the energy distribution, that is an indication of the atoms' electronic characteristics, the bands in question could or might not intersect. The initial filling of the molecular orbitals determines how the bands are occupied. The valence band (VB) is referred to as the most filled band. Conduction band (CB) is the lowest vacant band. The solid is a metal if the conduction band and valence band intersect, a semiconductor or an insulator if the energy gap between the two bands is wide. Materials are classified according to their energy gap (measured in eV) within the two bands: metals have an energy gap of 0 eV, semi metals of a value below 0.5 eV, semiconductors with gaps ranging from 0.5 and 3 eV, and insulators of greater than 3 eV. A positively charged gap persists in the valence band whenever an electron moves

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

through the VB to the CB. The nearby electrons in the VB normally occupy this vacant space relocating it to the neighbouring spot. This may be continued in a field of electricity, and the outcome is a current that can be illustrated by the move of the vacancy in the direction opposite from the excited electron. Because the vacancy is triggered by an absence of a negative charged electron, the corresponding current may be interpreted as the current that flows through positive holes in the VB.

Figure 4: A photon's absorption causes the excitation process that moves an electron from the valence band to the conduction band.

2.3 LIGHT AND MATTER

The functioning of photovoltaic (PV) systems depends vitally on light. Semiconducting components included in PV modules absorb photons, which are energy-carrying packets of light. Electrons are stimulated from their valence bands to the conduction bands when photons connect with the atoms in the material, transferring energy in the process. Due to the freedom of movement provided by these electron-hole pairs, they enable the production of electrical current [26]. In PV modules, the interaction of light and matter is controlled by several physical processes. The absorption spectrum of the employed semiconducting material is one important consideration. Specific absorption spectra of various materials show their capacity to soak up light at various wavelengths. To improve the PV module's efficiency throughout an extensive spectrum of solar radiation wavelengths, it is crucial to use materials with the best absorption properties [26]. Reflection, transmission, and scattering are additional elements that affect how light behaves inside a PV module. Anti-reflective coatings are frequently used to improve light absorption by lowering reflection losses at the module's surface. Advanced light-trapping methods can also lengthen photons' paths within a material, increasing the likelihood of

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

absorption. Examples include textured surfaces and backside reflectors [32]. The voltage produced by the PV module is directly correlated with the energy of the absorbed photons. Higher energy (and shorter wavelength) photons can impart more energy to the electrons, increasing the voltage output. A balance must be struck, though, as using too much energy can also result in material deterioration and heat losses. Therefore, it is important to optimize light absorption while reducing energy losses and potential damage while designing and optimizing PV modules [26]. In conclusion, creating effective solar energy systems depends on having a thorough understanding of the interactions between light and matter within PV modules. The performance and general efficacy of photovoltaic systems can be improved by researchers and engineers by refining material qualities, absorption characteristics, and light control strategies.

2.4 P-N JUNCTION

A P-type area and an N-type region are joined to create the PN junction in a solar cell, which is a semiconductor interface. Trivalent impurities, such as boron, dope the P-type area, resulting in an excess of holes serving as the majority carriers. The N-type area, in contrast, has an overabundance of electrons as the main carriers because it is doped with prevalent impurities like phosphorus. The photons that enter are absorbed by the semiconductor material when they interact with the PN junction of a solar cell. The electrons in the material's valence band get energy during this absorption process, which moves them into the conduction band and leaves behind electron-deficient regions, or holes, in the valence band [69]. The varying doping concentrations on either side of the PN junction cause the built-in potential, sometimes referred to as the junction potential or built-in voltage, to exist. The mobility of charge carriers is impeded by this potential. The electric field produced by the inherent potential repels electrons from the N-side and holes from the P-side [28]. The electric field within the PN junction separates the charge carriers after photon absorption and the formation of electron-hole pairs, pushing the electrons toward the N-side and the holes toward the P-side. The open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), which is created by this spatial separation of charges, is what powers the solar cell. An external load is coupled to the PN junction to complete the circuit and draw electricity from the solar cell. Short-circuit current (I_{sc}) is produced by the movement of electrons across the external load from the N-side to the P-side [69]. According to the p-n junction diode's operating principles, the PN junction in a solar cell function. The PN junction's

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

diode properties allow for a unidirectional flow of current, which makes it possible to convert light energy into electrical energy. The barrier for charge carrier movement is lowered when the PN junction is forward-biased (positive voltage supplied to the P-side and negative voltage applied to the N-side), facilitating electron and hole transport across the junction. The barrier for charge carrier movement rises, restricting current flow, when the PN junction is reverse-biased (positive voltage applied to the N-side and negative voltage applied to the P-side) [28]. In conclusion, a PV cell's PN junction is essential for turning light energy into electrical energy. Within the PN junction, photon absorption produces electron-hole pairs. The internal potential separates these charges, producing a voltage. Electrical power can be obtained from the solar cell by attaching an external load and allowing current to flow.

2.5 AIR MASS

The route length of sunlight through the Earth's atmosphere is referred to as "air mass" in the fields of solar energy and photovoltaics. It measures how much of the sun's energy is lost through diffraction and scattered before it reaches the surface of the Earth. Since air mass directly affects the intensity and spectrum makeup of incident solar radiation, it is crucial to understand its performance and efficiency in photovoltaic systems [79]. A ratio or dimensionless number is commonly used to express the air mass, which is represented by the symbol "AM." The path length of sunlight as it moves vertically through the Earth's atmosphere at sea level, in clear skies, is represented by the standard air mass, or AM1.5. A route length that is 1.5 times the distance between the observer and the edge of the Earth's atmosphere is indicated by an air mass of 1.5. The air mass value has an impact on the quantity of solar energy that can be converted into electricity, which makes it crucial for photovoltaic performance. Sunlight is scattered and absorbed by gases, water vapor, dust particles, and other atmospheric components as it travels through the atmosphere. The solar spectrum is altered as a result of these interactions, which also lessen the amount of sunlight that reaches the solar cells [55]. Manufacturers and researchers who work with V modules frequently characterize and evaluate their products using STCs, which stand for standard test conditions and correspond to an air mass of 1.5. This makes it possible to compare module performance in a consistent manner. In actual installations, the location, time of day, and environmental factors can all affect the air mass. Higher air mass values, such as AM2 or AM3, are associated with

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

longer atmospheric pathways taken by sunlight, which often results in less solar energy reaching the PV module. It is crucial to consider the local air mass values in order to appropriately evaluate the performance of solar systems in various locations. This data aids in forecasting the PV system's anticipated energy output and assessing the solar resource that is now accessible. In order to maximize energy production, it is also important for optimizing the design and sizing of PV installations [79]. In conclusion, air mass is a parameter that describes the length of the trip that sunlight takes through the Earth's atmosphere, and it directly affects how well photovoltaic systems work. Assessing the solar resource, projecting energy output, and improving the design of PV installations all depend on knowing the air mass values and how they vary in various places.

2.6 STANDARD CONDITIONS (STC)

The performance of photovoltaic modules is examined and evaluated under Standard Test Conditions, which are frequently abbreviated as STC. These settings offer a uniform starting point for the evaluation and comparison of the efficiency traits of various PV technologies. STC makes it possible for producers, scientists, and customers to evaluate and compare PV module energy output and efficiency under standardized test conditions. The most widely used STC parameters for PV testing are as follows: an air mass of 1.5, a cell temperature of 25 degrees Celsius, and an irradiation level of 1000 watts per square meter [59]. These parameters, which reflect a typical performing setting for PV systems, are based on the average solar radiation that is accessible at sea level in cloudless sky scenarios. The solar radiation impacting on the surface of the PV module has a power density of 1000 watts per square meter at STC. Regardless of their physical size or design, different PV modules can be directly compared thanks to this defined level. It offers a framework for assessing the modules' electrical output under pre-set lighting conditions. The projected operating temperature of PV modules under typical circumstances is considered by the cell temperature of 25 degrees Celsius in STC [59]. As temperature fluctuations can considerably alter the electrical characteristics of PV cells, this temperature is chosen as a benchmark to evaluate the performance of the module. It is crucial to remember that in actual outside operating settings, PV module temperatures might exceed 25 degrees Celsius, which could cause performance results to deviate from STC performance standards. When the sun is at an angle of 48.2 degrees from the zenith,

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

the air mass of 1.5 represents the length of the journey that sunlight takes through the Earth's atmosphere. A standardized illustration of the spectrum dispersion of sunlight that reaches the PV module is given by this particular air mass value. It enables reliable comparisons of the effectiveness of PV modules under regulated environmental conditions. It is crucial to understand that PV module performance under STC may not always correspond to the performance in actual operating conditions. The energy output and efficiency of PV systems can be considerably impacted by elements including location, climate, shading, and module orientation [83]. STC offers a common reference, but it is important to consider additional factors and performance measures unique to the installation location when assessing the performance of PV systems. Standard Test Conditions (STC) are predetermined conditions that offer a common benchmark for assessing and contrasting the performance of photovoltaic components and modules. The irradiance level, cell temperature, and air mass are among the variables they incorporate, enabling uniform evaluation and comparison of PV module properties. When assessing the performance of PV systems in actual conditions, other aspects must be considered even though STC serves as a valuable benchmark.

2.7 I-V CURVE

In order to understand the electrical behaviour and performance of photovoltaic (PV) devices and modules, it is essential to understand the I-V (current-voltage) curve. It illustrates the connection between the voltage across the device's terminals and the current that is flowing through them. The conventional method for obtaining the I-V curve involves varying the load resistance over a range of values while monitoring the resulting current and voltage. Maximum current flows through the device at the I-V curve's short-circuit point, or I_{sc} , where the load resistance is zero. This is the highest current the PV module can produce when there is no external load attached. It is a crucial factor to consider when assessing the device's ability to produce current under ideal circumstances [100]. The load resistance is infinite at the open-circuit point, or V_{oc} , on the other end of the I-V curve, where the current is zero. When there is no current flowing through a PV device, its maximum voltage, or V_{oc} , is produced. It denotes the potential difference between the terminals in the absence of an external load. V_{oc} is a crucial statistic for determining how well a device can produce voltage in open circuit situations. The operational point at which a PV device produces its maximum amount of power is

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

represented by the maximum power point (MPP) on the I-V curve. The voltage and current combination that produces the highest product of the two is what determines it [19]. The MPP is of great relevance since it indicates the device's ideal working situation, in which it can supply the most power possible to an external load. A PV device or module's performance can be evaluated under various operating situations by examining the I-V curve. The shape and properties of the curve may alter as a result of variations in solar intensity, temperature, and load resistance. These changes reveal information about the device's effectiveness, how it responds to shifting environmental factors, and how well it can deliver power under various load scenarios. An effective tool for developing and enhancing PV systems is the I-V curve. It aids in comprehending the electrical behaviour of PV devices, assessing their effectiveness, and choosing suitable working circumstances. To help in the design and integration of efficient and dependable solar systems, engineers and researchers can utilize the I-V curve to identify the maximum power output, efficiency, and performance limits of PV devices [81]. The I-V curve, which illustrates the relationship between current and voltage, is an essential feature of PV devices and modules. It offers perceptions into the electrical behaviour of the gadget, performance under various circumstances, and ideal operating settings. Engineers and researchers can improve the efficiency and reliability of photovoltaic systems by evaluating the I-V curve to optimize PV system design, assess device performance, and make wise judgments.

2.7.1 FOUR-POINT PROBES METHOD

A precise and dependable approach for measuring the voltage and current across a sample or device is the four-point probe method. In comparison to conventional two-point measurements, it gets around the downsides of contact resistance and lead resistance and produces more precise findings. The sample or object being tested has four evenly spaced probes inserted on its surface using the four-point probe technique. The sample is injected with a known current using two of the probes, and the voltage drop across the sample is measured using the other two probes. The probes are set up so that the voltage-sensing probes are placed between the current-carrying probes. This set up provides precise measurement of the voltage across the sample and reduces the impact of contact resistance [1]. The four-point probe method may measure the resistance or conductivity of the material being tested by applying a known current and measuring the resultant voltage.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

With the help of this technique, it is possible to test electrical qualities such sheet resistance and resistivity precisely. Characterizing thin films, wafers, and semiconductor components utilized in solar devices makes use of it especially well. Comparing the four-point probe approach to the conventional two-point assessment has numerous benefits. First off, it gets rid of mistakes caused by contact resistance, which have a significant impact on how accurate the measurements are. Second, it reduces the impact of lead resistance, resulting in readings that are more accurate and repeatable. The four-point probe technique is further non-destructive, enabling repeated measurements on the same material or equipment without changing its characteristics [10]. The four-point probe method is widely used in the photovoltaic industry. It is utilized for photovoltaic material quality assurance and characterization, including thin films and crystalline silicon wafers. Researchers and manufacturers can use it to analyse photovoltaic device performance, examine the electrical properties of materials, and improve their design and fabrication procedures. An accurate and dependable method for determining the I-V properties of materials and electronics is the four-point probe method. By getting around contact resistance and lead resistance constraints, it delivers precise voltage and current measurements. The technique helps researchers and manufacturers characterize and improve the electrical properties of materials used in photovoltaic devices, which is particularly useful in the field of photovoltaics.

2.7.2 NORMS FOR IV-CURVE MEASUREMENTS

In order to guarantee the accuracy and reliability of data collected from photovoltaic devices, norms for IV-curve measurements are essential. By standardizing measurement practices and conditions, these norms aim to reduce variations that may result from using various testing approaches. Researchers, producers, and certification agencies can get consistent and comparable results by adhering to these standards, providing a fair evaluation of the effectiveness and performance of solar systems. Several standards have been produced by the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) that are specifically related to IV-curve measurements in photovoltaics. IEC 60904-1, which offers instructions for the measuring of photovoltaic device parameters, including the I-V curve, is one of the important standards. Important characteristics including measurement setup (e.g., light source, filters), measurement conditions (e.g., standard spectrum, reference temperature), and measurement techniques are all specified by this

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

standard. It makes sure that measurements are carried out in a standardized and controlled environment, enabling precise comparisons and a trustworthy assessment of device performance. IEC 61853, which focuses on measuring photovoltaic devices' performance metrics, including the I-V curve, is another pertinent standard [18]. This standard offers comprehensive instructions on measuring techniques, equipment specifications, and data analysis methods. It covers a range of photovoltaic device types, including as multi-junction, thin- film, and crystalline silicon cells. The IV-curve properties can be consistently and accurately measured by adhering to the guidelines provided in IEC 61853, allowing for efficient performance evaluation and comparison across various device technologies. Compliance with these standards for IV-curve measurements is crucial for commercial applications as well as for research and development. To guarantee the dependability and effectiveness of their solar goods, manufacturers frequently must adhere to strict performance criteria. Manufacturers can show that their products conform to industry standards and regulations by upholding the established norms, boosting consumer confidence, and promoting market acceptance [18]. Additionally, standards for IV-curve measurements encourage information sharing and cooperation between academic institutions and researchers. It is simpler to share and analyse data among many research groups when it is gathered using standardized techniques and delivered in a consistent format. As a result, it is easier to create precise models, validate simulation results, and spot performance trends in photovoltaic systems. In order to assure accurate, dependable, and comparable results, norms for IV-curve measurements in photovoltaics give established principles and processes. Researchers, producers, and certification organizations can achieve consistency, accurately evaluate the performance of solar devices, and foster cooperation and progress in the industry by adhering to these standards. The expansion and development of the photovoltaic industry as well as the global deployment of dependable and effective solar systems depend on adherence to these standards.

2.8 CHARACTERISTICS OF SOLAR CELLS

2.8.1 DARK CHARACTERISTICS

The performance and behaviour of solar cells under low light or in the dark are referred to as their "dark characteristics." These traits offer valuable information about the device's effectiveness, recombination mechanisms, and general performance under

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

various working circumstances. Dark current and dark voltage are two essential characteristics that solar cells display in the dark. The solar cell's internal current when there is no light is represented by the symbol (I_{dark}), or dark current. The diode equation can be used to explain it, which is mostly caused by carrier recombination processes [99]:

$$I_{dark} = I_0 * [e^{(\frac{qV}{nkBT})} - 1] \quad (1)$$

where n is the ideality factor, (k_B) is Boltzmann's constant, T is the temperature in Kelvin, (I_0) is the reverse saturation current, q is the elementary charge, V is the voltage across the solar cell terminals, and n is the ideality factor. The device's internal recombination processes, including as surface, bulk, and trap-assisted recombination, all have an impact on the dark current.

The voltage across the solar cell's terminals in the dark is indicated by the symbol (V_{dark}). It is affected by elements like the bandgap of the material (E_g), the inherent voltage (V_{bi}), and the applied voltage (V). The Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) equation can be used to approximately calculate the dark voltage [84]:

$$V_{dark} = V_{bi} - (\frac{k_B T}{q}) * \ln[\frac{(n_i^2)}{(N_c N_v)}] \quad (2)$$

where q is the fundamental charge, (n_i) is the intrinsic carrier concentration, (N_c) is the effective density of states in the conduction band, and (N_v) is the effective density of states in the valence band, and (V_{bi}) is the built-in voltage. The dark voltage, which controls the solar cell's maximum attainable open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), is determined by recombination rates, material characteristics, and doping concentrations [84]. Solar cells' dark properties can be examined to learn more about their recombination mechanisms, energy losses, and performance constraints. Researchers and producers can improve the efficiency and dependability of solar cells by comprehending, reducing, and optimizing the dark current and dark voltage. This knowledge is essential for formulating plans to lessen recombination, enhance carrier movement, and raise total solar cell efficiency.

2.8.2 ILLUMINATED CHARACTERISTICS

The behaviour and efficiency of solar cells under illumination are referred to as their illuminated characteristics. These characteristics offer valuable information about the device's effectiveness, power-generating capacity, and general performance under varied

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

lighting scenarios. Photocurrent and photovoltage are two essential characteristics that solar cells show when illuminated. The current produced by the solar cell when exposed to light is shown by the symbol (I_{ph}), or photocurrent. It can be expressed by the equation, which is directly proportional to the intensity of the incident light [84]:

$$I_{ph} = G * A * \eta \quad (3)$$

where A is the solar cell's effective area (m^2), G is the incoming light power density (in W/m^2) and η is the solar cell's overall efficiency. The overall efficiency (η) accounts for several reasons, including the device's light absorption, carrier production, recombination, and collecting efficiencies. The voltage between the solar cell's terminals while it is illuminated is represented by the photovoltage, abbreviated as (V_{ph}). It may be affected by elements including the semiconductor material's bandgap, the presence of electric fields internally, and the external load attached to the solar cell. The solar cell's open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), which is its highest voltage when no external load is connected, and photovoltage are related. The following equation can be used to represent the relationship between photovoltage and open-circuit voltage [84]:

$$V_{ph} = V_{oc} - I_{ph} * R_s \quad (4)$$

Where (R_s) is the solar cell's series resistance, (I_{ph}) is the photocurrent, and (V_{oc}) is the open-circuit voltage.

Understanding a solar cell's illuminated characteristics will help you understand its power generation potential, efficiency under various illumination scenarios, and performance constraints. Researchers and producers can improve the performance and reliability of solar cells by comprehending and optimizing the photocurrent and photovoltage. This knowledge is essential for developing plans to enhance light absorption, reduce resistance and recombination losses, and raise overall solar cell efficiency [99].

2.9 CHARACTERISTICS OF CURRENT-VOLTAGE

2.9.1 SHORT CIRCUIT CURRENT

The short-circuit current (I_{sc}) is an important quantity that describes a solar cell's or module's electrical activity. The largest current that may flow through the PV device

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

when its terminals are short-circuited (i.e., connected without any load or resistance in the circuit) is denoted by the short-circuit current [77].

$$I_{sc} = I_L - I_D \quad (5)$$

Where:

- I_L is the photocurrent created by incoming light, which is affected by the amount of sunlight falling on the solar cell as well as the properties of the semiconductor material.
- I_D is the diode current, which reflects the current flowing through the solar cell as a result of the semiconductor material's diode-like characteristics. It is provided by:

$$I_D = I_0 \left(e^{\frac{qV}{nkT}} - 1 \right) \quad (6)$$

Where:

- I_0 is the reverse saturation current, or the dark current, which represents the current that flows through the solar cell in the absence of light. It is caused by thermally generated minority charge carriers within the semiconductor material.
- V is the voltage across the solar cell.
- q is the elementary charge (approximately 1.6×10^{-19} Coulombs).
- k is Boltzmann's constant (8.617×10^{-5} eV/K).
- T is the absolute temperature in Kelvin.
- n is the ideality factor, which is a dimensionless parameter that accounts for deviations from ideality in the diode equation. It can vary depending on the characteristics of the solar cell and the recombination mechanisms.

The short-circuit current (I_{sc}) is the current that flows through the solar cell when its terminals are short-circuited, meaning there is no voltage across the device (i.e., $V = 0$). When $V = 0$, the diode current (I_D) becomes zero, and the short-circuit current is simply equal to the photocurrent (I_L). In practical PV systems, the short-circuit current is an essential parameter used to calculate the maximum power point (MPP) of the solar cell or module. The MPP represents the voltage and current combination that maximizes the power output of the PV system. Both the diode equation and the relationship between short-circuit current and diode current play a significant role in the analysis, design, and performance evaluation of photovoltaic devices and systems. Understanding these

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

relationships helps engineers optimize PV system performance and ensure efficient energy conversion from sunlight to electricity [77].

2.9.2 OPEN-CIRCUIT VOLTAGE

The open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) is a critical quantity in photovoltaic (PV) systems because it represents the voltage across the solar cell or module when its terminals are left open, indicating that no external load is attached. There is no current flowing through the device in this condition (i.e., $I = 0$). The open-circuit voltage is the largest potential difference that the PV system can produce under no-load conditions. Several factors influence the open-circuit voltage, including the material qualities of the semiconductor employed in the solar cell, the incident light intensity, and the temperature. greater light intensity usually results in a greater V_{oc} , but increasing temperature reduces the open-circuit voltage. The relationship between V_{oc} and the diode equation involves the ideality factor (n), temperature (T), the reverse saturation current (I_0), and the elementary charge (q). The diode equation describes the current-voltage characteristic of the solar cell and is given by [29]:

$$I = I_0 \left(e^{\frac{qV}{nkT}} \right) - 1 \quad (7)$$

where:

- I is the current flowing through the solar cell
- V is the voltage across the cell
- k is Boltzmann's constant (8.617×10^{-5} eV/K)
- k is Boltzmann's constant (8.617×10^{-5} eV/K)
- T is the absolute temperature in Kelvin
- q is the elementary charge (approximately 1.6×10^{-19} Coulombs). At open-circuit conditions ($I = 0$), the diode equation simplifies to:

$$0 = I_0 \left(e^{\frac{qV}{nkT}} \right) - 1 \quad (8)$$

Solving for V_{oc} , we get:

$$V_{oc} = \frac{kT}{q} \ln \left(\frac{I_0}{I_0 + I_L} \right) \quad (9)$$

Where:

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- I_L is the photocurrent generated by the incident light, which depends on the intensity of sunlight falling on the solar cell and the characteristics of the semiconductor material.
- I_0 is the reverse saturation current, or the dark current, which represents the current that flows through the solar cell in the absence of light. It is caused by thermally generated minority charge carriers within the semiconductor material.

The open-circuit voltage, along with the short-circuit current (I_{sc}), the fill factor (FF), and the efficiency, is essential for evaluating the performance of PV systems. By understanding the factors affecting V_{oc} , engineers can optimize the design and operating conditions to enhance the overall efficiency and electricity generation of the PV system. In practical PV systems, the open-circuit voltage is used to calculate the maximum power point (MPP) of the solar cell or module. The MPP represents the voltage and current combination that maximizes the power output of the PV system, and it is critical for designing efficient PV systems for various applications.

2.10 DIFFERENT TYPES OF SOLAR CELLS

Solar cells, sometimes referred to as photovoltaic (PV) cells, are devices that use the photovoltaic effect to transform sunlight into electricity. There are various solar cell varieties, each having a special structure and material created to maximize performance for certain uses. Silicon crystallized (c – Si) Solar cells: The most popular and economically dominating solar cell technology is crystalline silicon. They are constructed from monocrystalline or multicrystalline silicon wafers. Due to their consistent crystal structure, monocrystalline silicon solar cells are more efficient, although multicrystalline silicon solar cells are more economical. Usually, these cells appear to be black or dark blue [60]. Thin-Film Solar Cells: To produce thin-film solar cells, semiconductor materials are deposited in thin layers onto a supporting substrate. Cadmium Telluride (CdTe), Copper Indium Gallium Selenide (CIGS), and Amorphous Silicon (a- Si) cells are the three most popular forms of thin-film solar cells.

Flexible, lightweight, and potentially more affordable to produce are thin-film solar cells [60]. Organic Solar Cells: Also known as organic photovoltaics (OPV), organic solar cells use organic molecules or polymers as its active component. These cells are frequently

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

thin, flexible, and may be produced using less expensive techniques. They now have a lesser efficiency compared to other solar cell types nonetheless [34].

Perovskite Solar Cells: Using perovskite materials as the light-absorbing layer, perovskite solar cells are a potential developing technology. These cells have the capacity to produce energy with both high efficiency and cheap cost. However, the development of perovskite solar cells continues to face difficulties with stability and endurance in practical settings.

Multi-Junction Solar Cells: These solar cells have many layers made of various semiconductor materials with distinct bandgaps. With a greater span of the solar spectrum being captured by the cell thanks to its design, total efficiency rises. For high-power applications, concentrated photovoltaic (CPV) systems frequently employ multi-junction solar cells [60].

Regarding efficiency, price, stability, and relevance for various applications, each type of solar cell has benefits and disadvantages. The performance and economic viability of solar cells are being improved via ongoing research and development to hasten the adoption of solar energy as a sustainable power source.

Figure 5: Different Types of Solar Cells [34]

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

2.11 METASTABILITY IN SOLAR MODULES

Electrical characteristics of solar cells show metastability as a result of bias or light. Because they often relax after lighting during dark storage circumstances, brief increases or decreases in the open circuit voltage or fill factor are sometimes known as metastabilities.

2.11.1 LIGHT-INDUCED DEGRADATION (LID)

Light-Induced Crystalline silicon (c-Si) solar cells exhibit the phenomenon of degradation, particularly those with boron-doped p-type c-Si. The development and activation of boron-oxygen (B-O) defects is the main contributor to LID [58]. Equation/Reaction:

Reduced device performance results from the trapped carriers in the B-O faults recombining more easily when exposed to light. Although the precise mechanisms underlying LID are not well known, several hypotheses have been put forth [58]:

- Formation of charge carrier trapping centres known as boron-oxygen complexes (B-O-H, B-O-B, etc.).
- At the Si/SiO₂ interface, hydrogen (H) is released from the Si-H bonds, changing the characteristics of the contact, and trapping carriers.
- Changes in the charge carrier recombination rate brought on by the interaction of light with impurities or imperfections.

LID strategies for mitigation include [58]:

- Including passivation layers or coatings rich in hydrogen to stop the development of B-O flaws.
- Annealing techniques are used to reduce B-O defect activation.
- Enhancing the boron doping profiles and silicon material characteristics.

2.11.2 STAEBLER-WRONSKI EFFECT (SWE)

A common metastability seen in hydrogenated amorphous silicon (a-Si:H) and similar thin-film silicon solar cells is the Staebler-Wronski Effect. Upon continuous light soaking, it entails a reversible reduction in device performance. The a-Si:H material's

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

defects and modifications to the hydrogen (H) network are responsible for the SWE. Hydrogen atoms in the amorphous silicon can move when exposed to light, changing its electrical and structural characteristics. Changes in defect formation, recombination rates, and carrier mobility may result from the excited state Si-H*.[46].

Equation/Reaction:

The SWE's mitigation measures include [44]:

- **Techniques for Hydrogenation:** During the deposition process, optimizing the hydrogen concentration and distribution can improve passivation of defects and minimize the creation of defect states.
- **Light Soaking Conditions:** The amount of the SWE can be reduced by carefully controlling the light soaking conditions, such as intensity and temperature.
- **Post-Deposition Annealing:** After the a-Si:H is deposited, annealing procedures can be used to reduce the density of defects and increase the stability of the material.
- **Material engineering:** Investigating substitute materials, including hydrogenated nanocrystalline silicon or other thin-film technologies, may provide greater stability and decreased sensitivity to the SWE.

2.11.3 BIAS-INDUCED METASTABILITY

Bias-induced metastability describes modifications in photovoltaic (PV) device performance brought on by an applied voltage bias. It is frequently seen in thin-film PV technologies as perovskite solar cells, cadmium telluride, and copper indium gallium selenide (CIGS) [51]. The main cause of bias-induced metastabilities is the ion migration within the PV device caused by an electric field. The performance of the device may be impacted by changes in the electrical properties, interface characteristics, or defect densities brought on by ion movement. Copper (Cu) ions are the principal species involved in bias-induced metastability in CIGS and CdTe solar cells. Cu ions may move toward the rear contact when there is a positive voltage bias, changing the absorber layer's composition and characteristics [51]. Equation/Reaction:

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Bias-induced metastabilities can affect the efficiency of photovoltaic panels in both good and negative ways. Principal factors include the open-circuit voltage (Voc), short-circuit current (Isc), fill factor (FF), and overall power conversion efficiency might alter as a result of changes in electrical characteristics. The size and duration of the applied bias, as well as the particular materials and device architectures involved, all affect how much and in what direction the performance changes. Bias-induced metastabilities can occasionally result in enhanced device performance, but they can also occasionally result in decreased performance [51]. Several methods are used to reduce bias-induced metastability and enhance the stability of PV devices [91]:

- **Engineering of Interfaces:** Ion migration and its effects on device performance can be reduced by optimizing the connection between the absorber layer and other device layers.
- **Ion-Blocking Layers:** By including ion-blocking layers or materials in the device, bias-induced metastabilities can be minimized.
- **Implementing encapsulation techniques,** such as barrier layers or encapsulant materials, can provide a barrier that protects against exterior impacts, such as ion movement.
- **Device Architecture Optimization:** To increase the overall stability of PV devices, it may be beneficial to investigate alternate device designs or materials that are less prone to bias-induced metastabilities.

2.11.4 TEMPERATURE-INDUCED METASTABILITY

Differences in device performance and features brought on by temperature fluctuations are referred to as temperature-induced metastability in photovoltaic (PV) devices. Within the PV materials, these variances may result in structural modifications, impurity diffusion, or thermally induced defect processes.

Depending on the PV technology and materials employed, the precise mechanisms underlying temperature-induced metastability can change. Typical mechanisms include [64]:

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- **Structural fluctuations:** Temperature fluctuations can cause the materials to expand or contract, changing the device's dimensions and stresses. This may impact the performance and electrical characteristics.
- **Elevated temperatures** may make it easier for impurities to diffuse inside of PV materials. The electrical behaviour of the device may change as a result of this diffusion, which may also change the doping profiles, introduce new defect states, or modify carrier concentrations.
- **Reconfiguration of faults:** Temperature variations can cause faults in PV materials to reconfigure. The density, energy levels, or recombination qualities of defects may vary as a result of annealing, migration, or combination, which may have an impact on the performance of the device.

The performance of PV devices is impacted by temperature-induced metastabilities in several ways, such as: **Changes in Carrier Mobility.** Temperature fluctuations may alter carrier mobility, which can impact the device's ability to carry charges [40]. This may influence the general parameters of the current-voltage system, including the fill factor (FF), short-circuit current (I_{sc}), and open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}). Junction characteristics can change, including the band orientation or the interface states, as a result of temperature-induced metastabilities. These alterations may affect the device's performance in general, recombination rates, and charge removal [64]. Changes in temperature can cause the PV device's ideal operating point to fluctuate, which can have an impact on the device's maximum power output and efficiency. To improve device efficiency across a range of temperature circumstances, proper thermal management and control are required. Multiple techniques may be used to reduce temperature-induced metastability and enhance the stability of PV devices [80]:

- **Thermal Management:** The use of efficient thermal management strategies can reduce stress brought on by temperature variations and guarantee that the equipment functions within a safe temperature range. This may entail using the right thermal insulation, cooling mechanisms, or heat sinking.
- **Design and Stability of Materials:** Creating PV materials with improved thermal stability might lessen the effects of temperature-induced metastabilities. This

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

entails enhancing the device's structural resilience, lowering defect densities, and optimizing material composition.

- **Processes for Annealing:** Controlled thermal annealing may be used to improve the structural stability of the PV device, lower defect densities, and optimize material attributes. By reducing temperature-induced metastabilities, annealing can aid in restoring or enhancing the device's performance.
- **Packaging and Encapsulation of the Device:** By using the right encapsulation strategies and packaging materials, a barrier of protection against temperature changes, moisture intrusion, and other external elements that may cause metastabilities may be created.

2.11.5 RELAXED STATE

The relaxed state in photovoltaics refers to the equilibrium and stable state of a solar cell following an event of metastabilities. Metastabilities are temporary variations in a solar cell's electrical performance brought on by a variety of variables including lighting, temperature, or biasing conditions. Electrical properties including voltage, current, and efficiency may change from their initial values when a solar cell experiences metastabilities. The solar cell enters the relaxed state after it achieves steady-state and the electrical characteristics have stabilized following metastabilities. The solar cell's genuine and dependable performance under typical operating circumstances is represented by this relaxed state. To correctly characterize and assess the performance of the solar cell, the relaxed state must be precisely determined [14]. A stabilization phase is necessary for the solar cell to reach the relaxed state. The solar cell is maintained under consistent circumstances throughout this time, including temperature (T), light intensity (I), and biasing voltage (V), until its electrical characteristics are stabilized. The specific metastable effects and the properties of the solar cell determine how long the stabilization phase lasts [53]. Equations defining equilibrium that control the behaviour of the solar cell may be used to explain the relaxed state. The diode equation, for instance, may be used to represent the relationship between current (I), voltage (V), and temperature (T):

$$I = I_0 * \left[e^{\left(\frac{qV}{nk_B T}\right)} - 1 \right] \quad (12)$$

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

where n is the ideality factor, (k_B) is Boltzmann's constant, T is the temperature in Kelvin, (I_0) is the reverse saturation current, q is the elementary charge, V is the voltage across the solar cell terminals, and n is the ideality factor. This equation connects the temperature and the applied voltage to the current flowing through the solar cell. Depending on the individual phenomenon being examined, different equations and models may be employed in addition to the diode equation to describe the relaxation process and metastable effects in the solar cell. In these equations, elements including carrier recombination, bandgap energy, trap levels, and light-induced effects are considered [6]. To optimize the design, forecast the solar cell's long-term stability, and assess its efficiency, it is crucial to comprehend the relaxed state and precisely characterize its performance. Researchers and producers may get credible information and make reasonable inferences concerning the performance, operation, and dependability of solar cells because to the relaxed state. Although the diode equation is a fundamental equation in photovoltaics, it should be noted that the individual equations and models used to describe the relaxed state and metastable effects can differ based on the unique traits and phenomena being examined.

2.12 METASTABILITY MODELS

2.12.1 DEVICE-LEVEL SIMULATION MODELS

Shockley-Queisser model is a crucial theoretical model that determines the solar cell's maximum efficiency limit using precise balancing and thermodynamic principles. Absorption, radiative recombination, and non-radiative recombination are a few of the things it considers. It emphasizes idealized devices, and when the predicted behaviour differs from the actual behaviour, metastable effects may be present. To find disparities brought on by metastable processes, experimental data can be compared with model predictions [9].

$$J_{Limit} = q * V_{OC} \Pi \int_0^{\infty} \frac{E}{e^{kT}} - 1 \alpha (E) dE \quad (15)$$

Based on an exact equilibrium between photons that are absorbed and those that are released, this equation determines the theoretical current density limit (J_{Limit}) that a solar

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

cell may produce. The product of the photon energy (E) and photon absorption coefficient ($\alpha(E)$) is integrated over the energy spectrum [33].

Single-diode model A solar cell's current-voltage (I-V) characteristics are described by this model employing variables including the diode ideality factor, series and shunt resistances, and photocurrent. It may be expanded to include metastable effects by altering the parameters in accordance with experimental findings or adding further equations. A PV device's I-V characteristics are described by the single-diode model, which is a simplified depiction of the device. It considers variables including photocurrent, series and shunt resistances, and the diode ideality factor. By changing the model parameters depending on experimental results, the single-diode model may be expanded to incorporate metastable effects. For instance, to account for fluctuations brought on by metastable processes, modifications in the diode ideality factor or resistance values can be made [93].

$$I = I_{ph} - I_D - I_R - I_{sh} \quad (14)$$

Using the single-diode model, this equation illustrates the connection between current and voltage (I-V) in a solar cell. It takes into consideration the shunt current (I_{sh}), photocurrent (I_{ph}), diode current (I_D), and recombination current (I_R) [74].

2.12.2 DEFECT-RELATED MODELS

Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) This model explains how flaws or traps cause recombination to occur in solar cells. It can model the effect of metastable defects on carrier lifetimes and recombination rates by including the density and energy levels of traps. A PV device's I-V characteristics are described by the single-diode model, which is a simplified depiction of the device. It considers variables including photocurrent, series and shunt resistances, and the diode ideality factor. By changing the model parameters depending on experimental results, the single-diode model may be expanded to incorporate metastable effects. For instance, to account for fluctuations brought on by metastable processes, modifications in the diode ideality factor or resistance values can be made [85].

$$U_{SRH} = \frac{n_i^2}{\tau_{SRH}} \left(p + p_0 - n_i e^{\left(\frac{E_t - E_F}{kT} \right)} \right) \quad (16)$$

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

The Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) recombination rate (USRH) is described by this equation. The intrinsic carrier concentration (n_i), SRH lifespan (τ_{SRH}), excess minority carrier concentration (p), equilibrium minority carrier concentration (p_0), trap energy level (E_t), and Fermi energy level (E_F) are all factors [85].

Kinetic Monte Carlo (KMC) is an advanced computer modelling approach used to study solar cell metastability. It is especially useful for understanding the dynamics of charge carriers and defects overtime at the atomic or molecular scale. KMC models consider the behaviour of defects such traps and recombination centres, as well as charge carriers like electrons and holes. These creatures' dynamics are simulated using probabilistic processes in which events occur stochastically depending on transition rates [94]. The transition rates in KMC describe the probability of certain processes occurring, such as carrier capture, emission, recombination, or diffusion. Such rates are often determined from theoretical models or experimental data and may be affected by factors such as carrier concentrations, temperature, defect characteristics, and energy barriers. For example, the rate equation for the change in defect occupancy (N_d) may be represented as:

$$\frac{dN_d}{dt} = R_c - R_e \quad (17)$$

R_c and R_e are the capture and emission rates of defects, respectively.

The formula, which represents the chronological progression of the system's state probabilities, serves as the foundation for the KMC simulation. In the context of KMC entails estimating the probability of being in different states based on the transition rates. The equation is as follows:

$$\frac{dp_i}{dt} = \sum_j W_{ji} p_j - \sum_j W_{ij} p_i \quad (18)$$

KMC gives crucial insights into solar cell metastability by following random events and changes throughout time. It enables experts to investigate the kinetics of carrier capture and emission, defect interactions, and their influence on device performance. Researchers may use KMC simulations to acquire a better understanding of the fundamental principles that underlie metastable occurrences and to investigate techniques to limit their effects on solar cell performance and stability [94].

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

It is crucial to note that the particular equations and implementation of KMC might vary based on the nature of the system being represented and the presumptions that are made. Actual KMC simulations may include more sophisticated equations and considerations depending on the processes and materials under research.

2.13 DEGRADATION

Solar energy systems use photovoltaic (PV) modules, which are essential for converting sunlight into power. Nevertheless, the modules in question may degrade with time, which is a progressive loss of performance and effectiveness. Degradation of PV modules is caused by several reasons, including exposure to environmental variables such as temperature changes, humidity, and UV radiation. The degradation process can also be influenced by manufacturing flaws, material deterioration, and the presence of chemicals. For solar energy systems to be as effective as possible over the long run, it is essential to comprehend and mitigate PV module degradation.

2.13.1 POTENTIAL INDUCED DEGRADATION

The PID effect is significantly influenced by the climate, especially the temperature and humidity conditions. According to these circumstances a PV module may experience a large reduction in efficiency if exposed to high potential. The decline seems to be related to the leakage current that passes through the encapsulant of the module, which is located between the module frame and the solar cell elements. Potential-Induced The migration of charged ions inside the silicon solar cell causes degradation. The most common structure of solar cells is a p-n junction, with the front side (p-side) being positively charged and the rear side (n-side) being negatively charged. When sunlight strikes a solar cell, electron-hole pairs are produced and separated under typical working conditions, generating an electric field inside the cell. However, a second electric field is created across the cell when the solar module is exposed to high system voltage (generally higher than 600V), such as in utility-scale installations. Different grounding potentials or nearby electrical devices are frequently to blame for this. Charged ions like sodium (Na⁺) and chlorine (Cl⁻), which are found in different module materials (such as glass, encapsulants, and backsheets), move inside the solar cell as a result of the produced electric field [30]. On the front surface of the solar cell, these ions are transported, which causes them to assemble at the point where the silicon and passivation layer meet. A parasitic

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

current route between the front and rear of the solar cell is produced by this build-up, which causes localized areas of high voltage to occur. The effective current given to the load is reduced as a result of this parasitic current's bypassing of the external circuit's regular current flow, which also lowers the PV module's output power [7]. The PID factor (PID_f), which is the ratio of the module's initial maximum power output to the degraded maximum power output as a result of PID, is frequently used to determine the factor of PID:

$$PID_f = \frac{P_{initial}}{P_{degrade}} \quad (19)$$

If the PID factor is larger than 1, the module was impacted from PID-related power loss. PID factors can often vary from 1.1 to 1.5, or even higher in extreme circumstances.

Contributing factor to PID is the presence of charged ions (Na^+ and Cl^-) in module materials. Utilizing products with low ion contents can lessen the impact. The system Voltage also has an effect as PID incidence is more likely to occur when the system voltage is higher. Utility-scale installations are particularly vulnerable to PID because they employ greater voltages. Temperature and Humidity; PID is more noticeable in environments with high temperatures and high humidity levels. High humidity can make it harder for ions to move around inside the cell, which amplifies PID effects. PID can be influenced by the internal structure and design of the solar cell and module. PID resistance varies by module design. PID can be influenced by the internal structure and design of the solar cell and module. PID resistance varies by module design. Finally, Proper grounding of solar modules can assist in minimizing the potential difference between the front and backside of the module, hence reducing the driving force for ionic migration [61]. Solar module manufacturers have used a variety of ways to minimize or mitigate PID. PID can be reduced by designing cells and modules to decrease ion mobility and the formation of isolated high voltage zones. Materials with lower ion content and superior resistance to ionic migration can reduce the impact of PID. Properly grounding the solar modules can help to equalize the electrical potential between the front and backside, hence reducing PID effects. Using cooling and ventilation devices can assist keep temperatures and humidity levels low, minimizing the severity of PID. Under certain

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

situations, such as low voltage operation or exposure to sunshine, some modules may show partial recovery from PID [86].

2.13.2 HOT SPOTS

Hot spots in PV systems are high-temperature areas within solar cells or modules that pose serious problems for the reliability and efficacy of solar installations. Numerous things, such as partial shading, cell mismatch, module damage, aging, and faulty bypass diodes, contribute to these temperature hotspots. For instance, partial shade causes uneven current distribution, resistive pathways, and localized heating in locations with less exposure to sunlight. Cell mismatch, caused by flaws in the manufacturing process or age, might leave some regions less capable of conducting current, increasing resistance and heat production [16]. Hot spots have negative impacts on the durability and efficiency of PV systems. As more heat is released, power is lost, which lowers the effectiveness of energy conversion and the total amount of power produced. Long-term exposure to extreme heat can also hasten module aging, reducing the system's operating lifespan. Extreme temperature-induced thermal stress increases the danger of cell or module damage and eventual failure. Hot spots can also pose a risk to users' safety since temperatures that are too high might start fires that could cause harm to nearby property. Regular monitoring and identification are essential for addressing hot areas. In order to quickly identify and address any problems, hot spot detection techniques including electroluminescence imaging and infrared imaging are used. Implementing good thermal management through cooling and ventilation devices to drain excess heat, guaranteeing the proper operation of bypass diodes under partial shade, and designing the system optimally to minimize shading and cell mismatch are some mitigation techniques. The probability of hot spots is decreased by string fusing, a method that involves installing fuses inside the string circuit to stop excessive current flow via individual cells during the shading [13, 12]. Essential measures to avoid problems include routine examination and maintenance of broken or degraded PV modules. The solar industry can efficiently combat hot spots, assuring the dependable and sustainable functioning of PV systems, by implementing these preventative practices and best mitigation strategies. Photovoltaic

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

technology can continue to play a transformative role in establishing a greener and more sustainable energy future by concentrating on hot spot avoidance and management.

Figure 6: Hotspot on a PV modules [88]

2.13.3 CORROSION

The progressive breakdown of materials, particularly metal components, as a result of chemical interactions with the environment is referred to as corrosion degradation in photovoltaic systems. To ensure the longevity and maximum efficiency of solar installations, it is crucial to comprehend the mechanisms, effects, and practical mitigation techniques of corrosion. Corrosion in PV systems is generally caused by electrochemical processes that take place when metal components are subjected to moisture, humidity, and other contaminants. Galvanic corrosion, atmospheric corrosion, corrosion of junction boxes and connections, and corrosion in PV module frames are the primary corrosion processes seen in PV systems [56]. Galvanic corrosion occurs when different metals come into interaction, producing a galvanic pair. When subjected to an electrolyte (e.g., rainfall or humidity), an electrical potential difference between the metals causes rapid corrosion at the anode, yielding the more active metal. Atmospheric variables such as air pollution, salt spray in coastal locations, and industrial emissions can cause corrosion reactions on metal surfaces in PV systems. Furthermore, due to contact with outside temperatures and moisture infiltration, the metal parts of junction boxes and connections are prone to corrosion. In addition, when exposed to wet or corrosive conditions, metal frames used in PV modules might corrode over time [56]. Corrosion deterioration has a number of negative consequences on PV systems, such as decreased electrical performance caused by corroded connections, junction boxes, and other electrical components, which leads to higher resistance and losses, lowering total system efficiency and energy production. Furthermore, excessive corrosion can compromise module frames and supporting

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

structures, jeopardizing the PV system's structural integrity. Corrosion-related deterioration can cause problems such as loose connections and greater fire risk owing to electrical faults, raising safety issues. Furthermore, the necessity for corroded component maintenance or replacement might result in financial problems for PV system owners [47]. Effective corrosion mitigation strategies can reduce the impact of corrosion on PV systems. Material selection is critical, since using corrosion-resistant materials, such as stainless steel or coated aluminium, for outdoor-exposed components can increase system lifespan. Moisture infiltration and corrosion are reduced by properly enclosing sensitive electrical components and sealing junction boxes. Regular maintenance, such as periodic inspections, cleaning, and preventative measures to detect and resolve early symptoms of corrosion, is critical. Furthermore, protecting coatings or finishes applied to metal surfaces can provide an additional barrier against corrosive chemicals. Furthermore, separating dissimilar metals prevents direct contact and aids in the prevention of galvanic corrosion [42].

2.13.4 DISCOLORATION

The packing unit, EVA, or the adhesive securing the photovoltaic cells to the glass are the three main causes for variations in colour. As the staining expands, the EVA's colour changes from a pale yellow to dark brown. A module's total power is decreased when solar radiation hits a cell with a different cell colour. The main contributor to EVA deprivation, is the ultraviolet (UV) rays that water at temperatures greater than 50 °C emits [72].

A study that was done in order to investigate the yellow colour of EVA, the PV modules did undergo an artificial radiation in order to determine the impact of UV on the PV cells. The results of this experiments showed an extremely fast degradation when the irradiance of 4000W/m² was applied, this was accompanied by a drop of photosensitivity [45]. The discoloration of the PV module does affect the short circuit current I_{sc} which leads to a deterioration of the system. When the discoloration is small, the drop of 6% to 8% of I_{sc} occurs. On the other hand, if the discoloration is complete then the I_{sc} drop is of 10% to 13%. The maximum power also does drop because of the discoloration [76].

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Figure 7: Corrosion on a PV modules [17]

Figure 8: Effect of discoloration on IV curve [76]

2.13.5 DELAMINATION

Delamination is the separation of layers within a PV module, often involving the encapsulant, the front glass, and the solar cells or back sheet. The issue can be induced by a variety of reasons, resulting in the partial or total detachment of layers, and threatening the strength of the structure and energy production of PV systems. Studying the origins, impacts, and mitigation techniques of delamination is critical for guaranteeing the durability and optimal performance of solar modules.

Multiple factors influence PV module delamination. Thermal cycling, which is defined by frequent temperature variations between day and night, causes stress on the module materials, causing various layers to expand and contract, encouraging delamination. Furthermore, excessive humidity levels and intrusion of moisture caused by poor sealing or manufacturing flaws can decrease the adhesion between layers and cause delamination [73]. Material incompatibility between module assembly components can result in

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

differential expansion rates, causing mechanical stress spots and increasing the chance of delamination. Furthermore, insufficient manufacturing methods, such as incorrect encapsulant curing or insufficient lamination pressure, could end up in delamination during module manufacture. Extended exposure to adverse environmental conditions including UV radiation, high temperatures, and humidity can further hasten delamination [65]. PV module delamination can have several negative implications on system performance. Layer separation can result in air gaps that prevent light from reaching the solar cells effectively, decreasing the efficiency of energy conversion. In addition to localized heating and the development of hot spots, delamination can harm solar cells irreparably. Additionally, the PV module's decreased structural integrity might lead to bodily harm and a shorter module lifespan. Delamination also creates possible safety problems, particularly in harsh weather, when dangers from separated layers may arise [96]. Delamination of PV modules may be reduced by employing efficient mitigation strategies. The chance of delamination is decreased by better material selection, which includes using materials with suitable coefficients of thermal expansion and improved adhesive qualities. Lamination delamination is prevented during module manufacture by using reliable manufacturing procedures, such as appropriate curing and lamination pressure. Modules can be protected from delamination brought on by humidity by using advanced encapsulation methods with exceptional moisture barrier qualities. PV module certifications and thorough environmental testing can verify their long-term robustness and delamination resistance. Regular PV system inspection and maintenance also enable early identification and rapid correction of delamination problems [2].

2.13.6 POTENTIAL INDUCED DEGRADATION

A newer and fresh type of PV system failure called a PID fault which stands for Potential Induced Degradation fault has drawn considerable attention since manufacturers SOLON first disclosed it in 2010. The PID defect mostly impacts c-Si (crystalline silicon) panels, and as its name suggests, it happens whenever the module's voltage potential (difference of a few hundred volts) and leakage current induce ion mobility inside the module between the semiconductor material and other module components (Glass, Frame). If conditions, such as moisture, heat, and voltage potential, are present, this ion mobility then increases. The deterioration process can influence the power output capacity of the modules/cells if they are not PID-resistant, which can ultimately lead to yield losses of

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

20% or more [20] [52]. There are four considerations that must be made: The module's structure should be intended to separate the movement of current through the materials. The PV system setup determines the polarity of the applied potential in the module with respect to ground. Environmental circumstances, such as relative humidity, temperature, and soiling, can significantly enhance leakage currents [39].

Figure 9: Delaminated PV module [71]

2.13.7 CRACKS AND BREAKAGE

Photovoltaic modules are extensively damaged by broken glass. Most of the time, this happens during the PV module's installation or maintenance, notably when moving the device to the project location [97]. Equipment that is broken or damaged can nonetheless function normally. A fractured PV module may continue to function for several years despite providing much less power. The danger of electrical shocks and water infiltration is raised, nevertheless. Cracks, corrosion, colouration, and other forms of deterioration are frequently present along with fractures and defects [75].

2.13.8 BUBBLES

As a result of chemical reactions during environmental contact that produces gas, bubbles form. In the exact point in which the adhesion has been reduced, they are kept in place under the back sheet or the encapsulant. Bubbles complicate the cells' ability to dissipate heat, warming them due to inadequate insolation, which shortens their lifespan and degrades their anti-reflective coating [66]. The difference in adhesion brought on by the high cell temperatures leads to significant bubbles appearing in the core of the cells. The bubbles prevent the solar module's cells from dissipating heat, boost superheating,

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

shorten the module's life span, and enhance sunlight reflecting rather than absorption [67].

Figure 10: PV modules with cracks and breaks. Breaks in cells are (a); a white line is (b). [31]

One of the most noticeable effects of bubble formation in PV modules is a decrease in module efficiency. The existence of bubbles can impede sun- light transmission through the module to the solar cells. As a result, the PV module's energy-generating potential decreases resulting in reduced overall efficiency. Furthermore, the creation of bubbles may result in partial or total shadowing of solar cells, reducing their output and lowering overall electricity generation. Bubbles in PV modules, in addition to lowering energy production, generate weak areas within the module, rendering it vulnerable to extra mechanical and thermal loads. This vulnerability might hasten the depreciation of the PV module, potentially resulting in more delamination, cracking, or moisture infiltration.

Another significant concern is the entry of moisture. Moisture and other environmental pollutants enter the module through delamination. Moisture infiltration can corrode metal components, produce electrical shorts, and reduce solar cell efficiency. Moisture can freeze in colder areas, causing expansion and more damage [66]. Bubbles in PV modules can also cause "hot spots" on the solar cells, where localized heating occurs owing to poor electrical conductivity. If the temperature rises over acceptable levels, hot spots can cause cell deterioration and represent a fire danger. Localized overheating of solar cells caused by bubble-induced hot spots can severely degrade the module's overall efficiency and longevity [67]. Finally, the combination of decreased efficiency, greater sensitivity to mechanical and thermal stressors, moisture intrusion, and possible fire dangers might limit the total lifetime of PV modules. The bubbles grow and shrink in response to

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

temperature variations, increasing the delamination over time and speeding up the deterioration process. To avoid and reduce bubble formation in PV modules, it is critical to enhance production processes and use appropriate materials to ensure good layer adhesion. Thorough inspections and quality control techniques throughout manufacturing can assist in identifying possible delamination concerns prior to module deployment. Regular inspections and maintenance of installed PV systems are also required to detect early indicators of delamination and other deterioration concerns. By recognizing faults early on, suitable actions may be taken to remedy the problem and extend the lifespan of the PV modules, guaranteeing maximum performance and efficiency over time [70].

Figure 11: Bubbles in a PV module [66]

2.14 DEGRADATION ANALYSIS

2.14.1 VISUAL INSPECTION

The IEC 61215 standard's initial stage is to check for visual abnormalities. Cracked or deformed materials, glass, frames, and junction boxes are examples of visual faults that could impact functionality.

- A short circuit could be caused by bubbles or delamination in the modules.
- Component failures might be a result of burned traces.
- Corrosion and fractures in solar cells can lower the generation of energy.
- Open circuits can result from improperly welded connections.
- Current leakage can occur on any exposed conductors.

2.14.2 INFRARED ANALYSIS

The infra-red thermal images are usually taken in order to detect some faults. Taking the images is usually done with an Infrared Camera as Flir, Testo, Satir... The modules then

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

are connected during the measurements and preferably functioning at the Maximum Power. The Infrared camera then is used in order to take the images from the front and back side of the module. it should be noted that reflections from near objects should not be included [89].

In the industry of photovoltaics, infrared (IR) analysis is a helpful technique for detecting and assessing damage in solar panels. IR analysis is a non- destructive testing approach that allows researchers and personnel to detect several forms of degradation, such as module imperfections soiling, and hot spots, without physically changing or ruining the solar modules. This method is based on the idea that different materials and situations emit or reflect different infrared radiation, which may be studied to infer relevant conclusions about the status of the module. The infrared radiation produced by the solar panels is captured using a thermal camera. Because faulty or damaged cells have different thermal properties than healthy cells, thermal imaging can detect abnormalities such as hot spots produced by higher resistive losses or cell malfunctions. These hot areas might be the result of cell fractures, incorrect interconnects, or other internal problems that cause degradation and efficiency loss [41]. IR analysis gives critical information for evaluating the overall performance of a PV system. Operators can discover the structure and anticipate potential future degradation concerns by continually monitoring and analysing infrared images. This data-driven method enables informed decisions on maintenance plans and modifications to improve system performance and module durability.

2.14.3 I-V CURVE

The defects of the modules can be detected via the IV curve as an example by the series resistance or the open circuit current. By varying the loads on the module many defects can be discovered. For this multi meter are used for recording voltage and current and the temperature of the module should be recorded. The irradiance should also be recorded. [90].

2.14.4 ELECTROLUMINESCENCE

The minority carrier diffusion lifetime, which controls the effectiveness, is the most crucial material property. Additionally, researchers draw attention to the fact that the carrier diffusion duration and the luminous degree of the El image coincide one to one. The contrast of the EL picture may be used to specifically identify the smaller carrier

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

diffusion length [63]. This is since the faulty region of the cell will have low minority carrier diffusion, which will result in a dark region in the picture. The flaws in solar cells may be divided into two groups. The first group is known as the inherent faults, which result from the material's characteristics and include things like cracked grids and black cores. External faults brought on by the manufacturing process, including small cracks and breaks, are the second kind [63].

2.14.5 THERMAL CYCLING

An analysis named thermal cycling (TC) is frequently employed to track the progression of degradation. The inspection of the PV module's stability all through different stages from manufacturing till on site can be made by TC. The TC technique simulates continuous illumination by varying the temperature between 40 °C and 85 °C and injecting current. Depending on the temperature's highest limit, different cycles are required as an example 500 cycles for 110 °C [57]. The thermal cycling technique involves ramping up and down the temperature to simulate the temperature fluctuations observed by solar panels during day-night cycles and changes in the seasons. The profile includes dwell durations at extreme temperatures that imitate long-term exposure to high or cold temperatures. The electrical efficiency of the PV modules is continually evaluated during the testing. Periodically, variables such as open circuit voltage, short-circuit current, maximum power output, and efficiency are monitored. This enables analysts to see how the repetitive heat fluctuations affect the electrical properties of the modules [57]. Furthermore, the quality of the PV modules is inspected during the testing procedure. Potential degradation processes such as microcracks, delamination, or changes in material characteristics are thoroughly investigated. Non-destructive testing methods, such as infrared thermal imaging or visual inspections, are used to identify any evidence of material degradation or structural problems [57]. The data acquired throughout the heat cycling process is thoroughly analysed. Power degradation patterns and efficiency losses are investigated in order to comprehend the long-term behaviour of PV modules subjected to thermal stress. Researchers can determine the primary degradation processes and their rates by connecting reported performance changes with certain temperature cycling settings. The experiment's outputs are helpful for estimating the performance and reliability of PV modules across their operating lifetime. Manufacturers may utilize this data to improve module designs, choose more durable materials, and improve quality

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

control methods. Furthermore, this study advances solar energy technology by offering a better knowledge of how heat cycling affects the performance of PV systems.

2.15 IEC 61215

Tests in the IEC 61215 are used by criteria in electrical and building standards, programs, and procuring agreements across the world. This work investigates how recent developments in PV module designs impact how IEC 61215 test results have to be interpreted and how stabilizing processes for such tests, for instance, should be improved in order to maintain the most valuable results. Photovoltaic (PV) module design certification is achieved via the IEC 61215 series, which ascertains whether panels of a specific design tend to have identified issues in the field. In order to distinguish between degraded modules versus ones that met standards, modules are put through a range of accelerated stress testing and performance testing. Photovoltaic (PV) module design certification is achieved via the IEC 61215 series, which ascertains whether panels of a specific design tend to have identified issues in the field. In order to distinguish between degraded modules versus ones that met standards, modules are put through a range of accelerated stress testing and performance testing. The module's performance determines some of the conditions for a "pass." The initial module performance must, first and foremost, match the module label." Gate 1" refers to this comparison. 95% of the module's original power production must remain after the expedited stress testing." Gate 2" refers to this contrast. It is necessary to stabilize the module properly before evaluating Gates 1 and 2. Such stabilization may, for instance, result in the initial rapid Staebler-Wronski degradation in silicon thin-film or the evolution of states associated with LeTID for example, to a state that is field-relevant [78]. With respect to the initial condition of the module, the process that is generating the instability, and the stabilizing technique that is employed, a module's performance without adequate stabilization might seem perhaps extremely high or excessively low. As a result, Gate 1 or Gate 2 pass/fail labels may be inaccurate with no sufficient stability.

2.16 COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS

2.16.1 JMAK MODEL IN PV

The JMAK model can be used in PV research to examine processes that include the growth of phases inside the PV device. It is frequently used to characterize the kinetics

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

of phase changes in materials. For instance, in the production of thin-film solar cells, the precursor materials are frequently deposited first, and then they are heated to form the required phase (such as crystalline silicon, CIGS, etc.). The homogeneous and isothermal nature of the transformation—i.e., its occurrence equally throughout the material and at a constant temperature—are assumptions made by the JMAK model. During annealing or sintering processes in the PV manufacturing process, this might be an acceptable approximation.

The JMAK equation is the following:

$$X(t) = 1 - e^{-(kt)^n} \quad (20)$$

- k is the transformation's rate constant.
- The Avrami exponent, n , is determined by the growth process (for example, $n=1$ for one-dimensional growth and $n=2$ for three-dimensional growth).
- At time t , $X(t)$ represents the proportion of changed material.

It may be modified to suit experimental data on phase change in PV materials. Fitting the JMAK model to data entails identifying the values of the parameters k and n that best represent the experimental results.

2.16.2 ARRHENIUS MODEL IN PV

In degradation analysis, the Arrhenius model is frequently employed to investigate how temperature affects the rate at which materials, products, or systems degrade over time. It is based on the Arrhenius equation, which explains how the rate of chemical reactions is affected by temperature. This equation aids in the understanding of how the degradation rate of a material or system varies with temperature in degradation analysis [4].

The following is the Arrhenius equation:

$$k = A \times e^{-\frac{E_a}{RT}} \quad (21)$$

- k is the degradation rate or reaction rate at temperature T .
- A is the pre-exponential factor, a constant that depends on the specific material or system being studied.
- E_a is the activation energy, which represents the minimum energy required for the degradation process to occur. It is a material-specific constant.
- R is the gas constant (8.314 J/(mol·K)).

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- T is the absolute temperature in Kelvin.

The idea of activation energy E_a , which indicates the lowest energy necessary for a degradation process to commence, is central to the Arrhenius model. The thermal energy available to the system increases as the temperature rises. This makes it easier to break through the activation energy barrier, resulting in a faster degradation rate. In other words, greater temperatures exponentially increase the degradation process. researchers can generalize a materials or system's behaviour to other operating settings by analysing its degradation rate at different temperatures. This predictive power allows for life prediction and accelerated aging experiments, in which greater temperatures are applied for shorter periods of time to replicate long-term behaviour at lower temperatures over an extended length of time. Such accelerated aging tests are quite useful for determining a material's dependability and durability [48]. The Arrhenius model, while commonly used, has drawbacks. The model assumes that temperature is the sole element that influences degradation and ignores other potentially significant factors that may exist in real-world circumstances. Multiple degradation pathways with various activation energies may be active at the same time in practice, requiring more sophisticated models.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 DEVICES

3.1.1 I-V FLASHER

The “flash test,” which is described in the standards IEC61215, is an uncomplicated testing process used by most producers for classifying the modules. This test involves exposing a module for a brief period between 1 and 30 microseconds to a powerful flash of 100 MW/cm² light from a xenon-arc lamp. A computer records the results, and the data undergoes comparison to a reference solar module. The reference module’s power is adjusted to correspond to regular sun irradiation. Parameters are recorded under standard test conditions (STC) throughout the flash test. STC establishes an air mass 1.5 (AM 1.5) with a temperature of 25°C and an irradiance of 1000 W/m². Those are the irradiance and spectrum of sun reflected on a surface inclined at 37 degrees toward the sun on a clear day with the sun at an angle of 41.81 degrees above the horizontal plane. This ideal setup seeks to simulate the parameters of solar noon around the equinox at a latitude of roughly 40, with the cell pointed straight at the sun. Given the extent that temperature affects the efficiency of PV modules, STC criteria are used. When a module’s temperature rises, two events occur: Both the voltage output and the increase rate of current resulting from each of the cells decreases. According to IEC standard, the flash can be adjusted to 1000 W/m² while considering spectrum aligned, irradiance consistency, and time stability. The test stand’s interior space may be cooled down to 25 °C for temperature control, creating the ideal setting for consistent module classification.

3.1.2 STATIC SUN SIMULATOR

A static sun simulator is a specialized instrument used in photovoltaics (PV) to simulate solar irradiance and spectrum in a controlled laboratory environment. This technique is extremely useful for academics, manufacturers, and developers who want to analyse and quantify the performance, efficiency, and aging of solar modules. Aging studies are extremely important because they provide insights into the long-term performance and decrease trends of PV modules over their operational lives. A static sun simulator’s core component, which together imitate natural sunshine in a fixed arrangement, are crucial to its performance. Mercury arc lamps are commonly used as major light sources in such

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

simulations. These lamps produce a broad and realistic spectrum of light that closely simulates sunshine, allowing for more accurate and thorough testing of PV modules. The AIT static sun simulator has 12 lamps, categorized as Class BBB according to IEC 060904-9, with 9 m² test area and can emit from 0-1100 W / m² irradiance. The entire simulator is administered by computer-controlled mechanisms that govern the intensity and spectrum of the light source. These devices are in charge of correctly reproducing various sunlight scenarios. Data acquisition systems supplement these control mechanisms by collecting performance data from the PV module during the testing process.

3.1.3 CLIMATIC CHAMBER

The modules are maintained at a consistent temperature using the climate chambers. Additionally, it is employed to maintain any given product under specific stress situations. Within the chamber, these precise conditions are produced and managed. The stability of its temperature is within 1K of the stated target temperature. The temperature range in these climate chambers commonly spans a low of -40 to -80°C to a maximum of about 300°C.

3.1.4 ELECTRONIC LOAD

Cells and modules are coupled to an electronic load in order to carry out I-V curve. When the module is being tested and subjected to illumination, its I-V property is determined by applying a voltage ramp to the device. Normally, electricity is applied moving forward. For variations in temperature and irradiation, the software of both electronic loads may adjust the observed values.

3.1.5 ELECTROLUMINESCENCE CAMERA

An electroluminescence camera is a critical tool in the inspection and stabilization of photovoltaic (PV) systems, particularly solar panels. The camera, which operates on the concept of electroluminescence, takes use of the phenomena in which solar cells generate light when exposed to an electric current. During the examination, the solar panels are linked to an electrical source, and the introduction of voltage causes the PV cells to generate electroluminescent light. The camera is then pointed at the surface of the solar panel, catching the emitted light that would otherwise be undetectable to the naked eye. The camera detects and analyses possible flaws within the PV module by transforming

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

electroluminescent signals into visual pictures. Using electroluminescence imaging, imperfections such as microcracks, broken cells, and degradation zones appear as irregular patterns or dark regions in the pictures. This extensive examination enables the early detection of problems, preventing further deterioration and guaranteeing the best performance and lifespan of the PV system [8]. One of the most notable benefits of employing an electroluminescence camera is that it is non-destructive. The inspection procedure causes no damage to the solar panels, making it appropriate for frequent monitoring and maintenance. Early identification and action based on inspection results can enhance the overall efficiency and reliability of the PV system dramatically [8]. Solar energy systems can perform best by fixing discovered problems as soon as possible, optimizing energy output while avoiding financial losses. As renewable energy sources such as solar power continue to play an important part in sustainable energy policies, electroluminescence cameras help to promote clean energy by assuring the dependability and long-term stability of PV systems. As technology progresses, these cameras are likely to become increasingly more advanced, allowing even more precise defect diagnosis and significantly enhancing the efficiency of solar power systems.

3.1.6 MODULE SAMPLES

The 15 Module received from Malta are manufactured by Trina Solar. The Modules are named the honey module TSM-PD05. They are polycrystalline modules with 60 cells. Their power output ranges from 255–270W while they have up to 165 W/m² power density, and they have 16.5% maximum efficiency. The size of the cells is 156 × 156 and the module size is 1650 × 992 × 35 mm with a weight 18,6 kg. It has a High Transparency, Anti-Reflective, AR Coated and Heat Tempered Solar Glass - 3.2 mm. The Back-sheet is White, and the Frame is Silver Anodized Aluminium Alloy. The Junction-Box IP 67 rated or IP 68 rated.

3.2 COMPARATIVE TEST SCHEME

A total of 15 modules are going to be received from in operation PV power plant, these modules are field aged. After these modules are in AIT, out of the box measurements are going to be executed under STC in accordance with IEC 61215 using a flasher with 2ms once. After the first step, 2 modules that gave minimum and medium measurements are going to be taken as reference and two others are going to be used for outdoor testing.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

The rest of the modules are going to go to the next process. The modules that showed approximately similar measurements are going to go through the same stabilization method.

- 2 modules are going to be stabilized with MPP during AAA illumination according to the IEC 61215. The irradiance is going to be of a value of $1000\text{W}/\text{m}^2$, energy of 20 kWh and a temperature of $50^\circ\text{C} \pm 1$.
- 2 modules are going to be stabilized with Open Circuit during AAA illumination according to the IEC 61215. The irradiance is going to be of a value of $1000\text{W}/\text{m}^2$, energy of 20 kWh and a temperature of $50^\circ\text{C} \pm 1$.
- 2 modules are going to be stabilized by dark voltage bias at $I=0.6I_{sc}$ and temperature of $50^\circ\text{C} \pm 1$.
- 2 modules are going to also be stabilized by non-standardized dark voltage bias at $I=1.6I_{sc}$ and temperature of $50^\circ\text{C} \pm 1$.

After each experiment, another STC measurement using a flasher should be done and then observe if $\Delta P \leq 0.01$ then the module is stabilized, if not then the experiment should be repeated until it reaches this value.

Figure 12: Scheme of the experiment

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

	Step1: STC	Step2: MQ19 MPP	Step3: MQ19 OC	Step4: Dark Bias I ₁	Step5: Dark Bias I ₂	Step1: STC
Details	1000 W/m ² at 25°C+ flasher	1000 W/m ² , 50°C ± 1 at MPP, 20kWh, AAA flasher	1000 W/m ² , 50°C ± 1 at O.C, 20kWh, AAA flasher	0 W/m ² , 50°C ± 1, 20kWh, I ₁ =0.6 ISC	0 W/m ² , 50°C ± 1, 20kWh, I ₂ =1.6 ISC	1000 W/m ² at 25°C + flasher
AIT	All modules	2 modules	2 modules	2 modules	2 modules	2 modules
PIB	All modules	2 modules	2 modules	2 modules	2 modules	2 modules

Figure 13: Summary of the protocol

3.2.1 EXCHANGE SCHEME

In the figure 14. the exchange scheme is shown. Each institute will receive one string of the same type of modules after following the same methods of stabilization the string of modules will again be exchanged between both institutes to undergo again the same protocol.

Figure 14: Exchange Scheme between AIT and PI Berlin

3.2.2 OUT OF BOX MEASUREMENT

IEC 61215 compliant power measurement at STC

3.2.3 PRECONDITIONING STANDARDIZED

Preconditioning is necessary for modules' power output to be determined accurately. Pre-Conditioning Procedure according to IEC61215 aims to improve the technology stabilization procedures. The modules are irradiated with 1000W/m² at least two successive cycles using sun simulator with a temperature of 50°C±5°. After each cycle of

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

light stabilization, the IV characteristics of modules should be tested into the following STC: the AAA flasher as sun simulator with AM of 1.5, and 25° in Temperature.

3.3 STABILIZATION METHODS

$$\frac{(P_{max} - P_{min})}{P_{Average}} < x \quad (22)$$

For the definition of stabilization as per MQT 19 of IEC 61215-2, $x = 0,01$ shall be used. After each cycle of light stabilization, the IV characteristics of modules should be tested into the following STC: the AAA flasher as sun simulator with AM of 1.5, and 25° in Temperature.

In the next parts, many methods of stabilization are presented. After discussion and coordination with the research partners, only illumination and dark bias are used.

3.3.1 THERMAL TREATMENT

The process of recovering a portion or all the original efficiency of a-Si modules after prolonged exposure to high temperatures is known as thermal annealing. The performance of a PV module is significantly impacted by temperature, which causes order-order, order-disorder, or disorder order transitions among modules [5].

Multiple investigations have demonstrated that thermal annealing caused by high module operating temperatures enhances the efficiency of stabilized a-Si modules [43]. It explains the process by which a-Si modules regain part or all their original performance after being exposed to high temperatures over an extended period of time [62]. A-Si modules are returned to their initial performance after accelerated aging procedures using a 90° C thermal annealing phase in the current module certification testing processes [35]. For a-Si PV, exposition to light causes a reduction in module power output whereas contact to high temperatures causes an increase. Reduced light-induced deterioration may be seen in more recent technologies that use nanocrystalline silicon. Dark exposure results in phases with reduced efficiency for both CdTe and CIS/CIGS, however these results may be inversed by illumination. To prevent potential degradation processes, it is crucial to operate modules under load when exposed to light, especially for CdTe. Even some crystalline silicon PV systems have metastabilities that must be stabilized by contact with light [24].

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

3.3.2 LIGHT SOAKING

performance under continuous illumination is a critical part of any PV technology's characterization process since light exposure can have several consequences on the assessment of both beginning and long-term stabilizing system module performance. LS produces metastable electrical or structural repercussions. According to studies, the temperature of a-Si modules during illumination has an impact on their stabilized efficiency. Higher temperatures change the balance between the detrimental effects of light exposure and the advantageous effects of annealing, with warm light soaking resulting in greater efficiency. This explains why, due to the well-known seasonal effect, performance of installed a-Si PV modules is strongly correlated with daily mean temperature [98].

3.3.3 ELECTRICAL BIAS

On initial exposure to light, CdTe PV devices frequently show a performance change. A previous study demonstrated that forward bias in the dark or light exposure improved the open circuit voltages of CdTe cells from a wide range of sources by around 4%. On unbiased dark storage, it was discovered that the effect could be reversed, and that both the initial shift and the following relaxation had time constants on the order of hours. The shift has been attributed to the trap states in the absorber junction, which disappear when the cell is biased forward [82]. CdTe devices often experience performance loss from continuous light exposure as a result of negative, irreversible effects to the device. For instance, CdTe demonstrated an initial increase in efficiency under moderate soaking then long-term degradation [15].

3.3.4 LETID

Nearly all kinds of c-Si wafers and solar cells undergo light- and high temperature-induced degradation (LeTID), a type of solar cell breakdown [49]. The degradation does not come by light-induced degradation (LID) techniques and is not dependent upon the creation of boron-oxygen complexes or the separation of iron-boron pairs. Three potential transitional states of the LeTID fault have been presumed and are depicted in the figure below, even if the primary cause of the LeTID fault is still unclear.

BO faults are found in states A, B, or C. Boron and oxygen exist within annealed state A with lower recombination-active, separated components. The BO defect (state B), which

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

is extremely recombination active, is created as a result of degradation. A reduced recombination-active, regenerative state C results from passivation of the fault [22].

Figure 15: Three-state model for the BO defect [95]

3.4 MODULE PARAMETERS

When determining the reliability of a solar module, four crucial factors must be considered. This contains the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}), short-circuit voltage (I_{sc}), maximum voltage (V_{max}), and maximum current (I_{max}). A solar module's performance may be determined by looking at its maximum power, fill factor, and efficiency.

3.5 MODULES' RESPONSE TO STABILIZATION

Figure 16: Possible Response of PV modules to stabilization.

Experiments on PV modules can result in three patterns: stability, degradation, and improvement. Fresh modules demonstrating stability, indicating reliability, but some can deteriorate as a result of factors such as material quality and environmental conditions. Others can show enhancement, which was ascribed to a variety of settings.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

These patterns serve in the understanding of PV module behaviour and the advancement of PV technology.

Field-aged PV modules demonstrates a diversity of behaviours when tested. Particularly, these modules can stay stable, showing their endurance in a variety of environmental situations. Another category of field-aged modules can show stability but a loss in performance, implying that aging has an influence on efficiency and necessitating more inquiry into relevant causes. Further, several field-aged modules showed stability as well as an improvement in performance, which might be attributed to extended exposure to testing conditions. This classification of PV module reactions is fundamental to this study since it provides insight into module behaviour under various settings. It helps to enhance and optimize PV technology, while analysing the results to determine their long-term potential in sustainable energy solutions.

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 OUT OF THE BOX MEASUREMENTS

The partner in Malta delivered 15 PV modules. These PV modules had previously been utilized outdoors. The primary goal is to guarantee that these modules work well. A systematic stabilizing method has been launched to do this, beginning with detailed out-of-the-box measurements on each module. Significant insights into the current condition and performance qualities of the modules through the careful examination. The first measurements' findings have been meticulously collated, establishing the basic dataset for later in-depth research. Furthermore, for each PV module, comprehensive current-voltage curve, Pmax, and Pideal values have been created. These accurate curve studies provide thorough understandings of the modules' behaviour under varied settings and aid in identifying any differences between them. The detailed analysis of the data resulted in a classification of the modules based on their performance and operational status. This classification is critical because it enables the planning of specialized stabilization treatments for each group, enabling successful and targeted results.

Table 1: Out of the box measurements output of Malta PV modules.

Sample	Voc[V]	Isc [A]	Fill Factor [%]	Pmax [W]	Cell effs [%]
A1	38.41	9.12	76.00	266.38	18.24
A2	38.47	9.16	75.75	267.09	18.29
A3	38.28	9.06	75.72	262.82	17.99
A4	38.10	9.09	75.63	262.08	17.94
A5	38.39	9.17	75.46	265.73	18.19
A6	38.28	9.10	75.99	264.82	18.13
A7	38.31	9.08	76.09	264.75	18.13
A8	38.08	9.05	75.52	260.55	17.84
A9	38.17	9.05	76.31	263.90	18.07
A10	38.02	9.09	75.84	262.38	17.96
A11	37.96	9.03	75.93	260.55	17.84
A12	38.00	8.98	76.16	260.12	17.81
A13	37.96	9.01	75.74	259.16	17.74
A14	38.10	9.03	75.66	260.61	17.84
A15	38.10	9.08	75.55	261.41	17.90

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

4.1.1 Isc vs. Voc

After collecting the output of the initial measurements, an Isc vs. Voc graph was generated. When it comes to performance consistency, the graph shows that the PV modules are not clustering together, which indicates that although it is small, but the modules have different performance characteristics. This graph also shows quality assessment, the data points are consisted of and not very scattered. This provides information that all modules underwent the same quality control processes. The modules that are a bit more scattered can give an indication of the Mismatch effect.

Figure 17: Isc vs. Voc of out of the box measurement

Figure 18: Isc vs. Voc of out of the box measurement

The PV modules' IV curves nearly overlap, indicating that they endured similar rates of degradation over time. This might have occurred as a result of a variety of reasons such as exposure to sunshine, temperature variations, humidity, and other environmental

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

variables. Because the modules exhibit uniform degradation, it suggests that they age at about the same pace and that their performance degrades uniformly across their lifetime.

Figure 19: IV curve of all modules during out of the box measurements.

4.1.2 $I_{sc} * V_{oc}$ vs. FF

On the other hand, $I_{sc} * V_{oc}$ versus FF graph indicates defects as the data is very scattered. Modules with lower $I_{sc} * V_{oc}$ values and lower FF could indicate performance issues or inconsistencies in production whereas modules that plot higher on the graph would be more favourable choices for a given set of operating conditions.

Figure 20: $I_{sc} * V_{oc}$ vs FF of out of the box measurement.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

4.1.3 IDEAL VS. P_{MAX}

the P-ideal vs. P_{max} graph reveals valuable insights into their performance and degradation behaviour. The close clustering of data points indicates consistent and efficient power output characteristics, reflecting high-quality manufacturing and material selection.

Figure 21: P-ideal Vs P_{max} of out of the box measurement

The predictability and stability observed in the graph enable accurate performance monitoring over time, ensuring reliable operation in solar energy systems. Furthermore, the slow degradation rates depicted by the graph suggest a longer operational lifespan. These modules, with their minimal scattering and slow degradation, hold great potential for large-scale installations and are promising candidates for further research and development to advance degradation-resistant technologies. Overall, this graph demonstrates that the PV modules maintain their efficiency and reliability.

4.1.4 SORTING OF THE MODULES

Out of 15 modules, 2 modules that showed the best behaviour we have taken as reference modules which are A1 and A2. Afterwards, 8 modules that showed closer average behaviour, meaning that are not showing extremely high or extremely low behaviour in all the values we taken to be sorted again. The sorting was done depending on multiple variables collected in the out of the out of the box measurements. After the sorting was done, a selection of every 2 modules were put together to undergo the same stabilization method. the top 2 modules that showed the best results in the graphs are decided to

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

undergo Dark Bias $I_2=1.6A$, the 2 worst ones are decided to go for Open Circuit method. The modules that showed the same current will go through Dark Bias $I_2=0.6A$. And the rest will undergo IEC focusing on MQ19.

Sample name	A4	A6	A7	A8	A11	A13	A14	A15
Cell efficiency [%]	17.95	18.14	18.13	17.84	17.84	17.75	17.85	17.90
Sample name	A4	A6	A7	A8	A11	A13	A14	A15
Pmax [W]	262.08	264.82	264.75	260.55	260.55	259.17	260.62	261.41
Sample name	A4	A6	A7	A8	A11	A13	A14	A15
Fill Factor [%]	75.64	76.00	76.10	75.53	75.93	75.74	75.66	75.55
Sample name	A4	A6	A7	A8	A11	A13	A14	A15
Isc[A]	9.09	9.10	9.08	9.06	9.04	9.01	9.04	9.08
Sample name	A4	A6	A7	A8	A11	A13	A14	A15
Voc[V]	38.11	38.29	38.31	38.09	37.97	37.96	38.10	38.10
Sample name	A4	A6	A7	A8	A11	A13	A14	A15
ISC * VOC (P-ideal)	346.49	348.47	347.91	344.98	343.14	342.16	344.45	346.01

Figure 22: General Sorting.

We can see in the Figure below the sorting of the modules and the attribution of methods that are suitable for each 2 modules depending on the result of the sorting. As mentioned before, the sorting was done depending on many variables as the VOC and Isc results and on the Maximum and Ideal Power output.

Total sorting	A6	A7	A4	A15	A14	A11	A8	A13
Method	Dark Bias $I_2=1.6A$		Dark Bias $I_2=0.6A$		MQT19.1 MPP		Open Circuit	

Figure 23: Final Sorting and Method attribution

4.2 6.2MQ19 UNDER MPP

Figure 24: Experiment set-up

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Figure 25: Modules connection for MPP set up.

As the sun static sun simulator can hold up to 4 modules, both the modules of MPP and open circuit were put together. The ones that are undergoing MQ19 MPP are A11 and A14. The modules endured the light-induced aging in the simulator for 3 cycles, each cycle took 7 hours minimum and up to 1000 W/m^2 . After each cycle, the modules were measured by the AAA flasher and then put again in the static sun simulator for the next cycle. The Pyranometer is a CMP-21 with a sensitivity of $8.56 \mu \text{ V/W/m}^2$. The Modules A11 and A14 are connected to the inverter in order to attain the MPP.

4.2.1 FIRST CYCLE

The modules underwent the first seven hours of the light-induced aging experiment within a static sun simulator heated to $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and exposed to up to 1000 W/m^2 of irradiation. Using the AAA Flasher, the modules were measured when this cycle was complete. The findings are shown in the figures below.

Both modules showed a rise in the parameters P_{max} , V_{oc} and I_{sc} compared to the out of the box measurements. for the module A11, the maximum power attained 260.99 W whereas the I_{sc} gave 9.04 A and 37.98 V for V_{oc} . On the other hand, the module A14 showed a very surprising rise in Power of almost 2 W as P_{max} gave an output of 262.26 W , V_{oc} 38.10 V and I_{sc} of 9.11 A .

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Figure 26: IV curve of first round of light induced aging under MPP

Modules A11 and A14's IV curves after the initial round of light-induced stabilization have fascinating properties that provide better understanding of their electrical function. While there are no zigzags visible on either IV curve, the differences in their alignment and form when plotted together reveal subtle discrepancies in their reactions. Different initial carrier dynamics are suggested by the observation that module A11's current begins to fall before module A14. This behaviour shows that the carriers of module A11 may be more susceptible to defect-related recombination while having the same composition and going through the same stabilizing procedure. These discrepancies may result from regional variations in defect distributions that were not seen in the first measurements. The modest displacement of A11's current curve beneath A14's at the start can indicate an early imbalance in charge carrier extraction efficiency. This variance might be driven by surface characteristics, defect-related recombination, or other material variables. It is likely that module A14's carriers are removed more effectively, giving it an early edge. The arrangement of the IV curves around the central section emphasizes the modules' responses' complex nature. Recombination mechanisms, mobility properties, and surface effects interact to shape the IV curves as carriers traverse the device. The mid-curve alignment indicates that the basic electrical properties of the

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

modules are converging, possibly as a result of thermal impacts during the stabilization process that mitigated early variations. The disparities in current A11 and A14 behaviour can be linked to variances in carrier mobility and recombination kinetics. Even at the microscopic level, material heterogeneity can affect charge transport parameters. The early fall in current of Module A11 might be attributed to less effective carrier transport and a larger density of recombination centers in its material. The divergence at the beginning of the curve, together with the mid-curve alignment, suggests a relationship between surface attributes and initial defect density. It is possible that the surface of module A14 is better passivated or less prone to quick initial recombination, which contributes to its beneficial performance in the early phases.

The alignment of the IV curves demonstrates the influence of the stabilizing procedure on the electrical characteristics of the modules. The procedure might have resulted in defect annealing or realignment of carrier routes, resulting in mid-curve convergence. The stabilizing procedure most likely introduced changes that equalized certain electrical properties. Despite their similar composition, manufacturer, and initial measurements, the difference in performance found between modules A11 and A14 following the light-induced stabilization process necessitates a closer examination of the underlying details. The unanticipated variances can be attributable to a number of reasons, each of which contributes to the modules' different reactions. Even amid comparable production methods, subtle variances in material microstructure can result in variations in carrier movement and recombination dynamics during stabilization. Furthermore, albeit undetectable in initial measurements, localized alterations in defect distributions and impurity concentrations can affect how the modules respond to the stabilizing process. Temperature plays an important impact since specific thermal reactions inside module A14 may have altered its charge carrier behaviour and defect interactions differently from A11. Surface effects, such as interactions with encapsulating materials and surface passivation, might possibly contribute to the observed disparities. Furthermore, measurement variability, which exists in even the most accurate measurements, might exacerbate the observed disparities in response. The cumulative influence of these complicated elements shapes the modules' different behaviour.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

4.2.2 SECOND CYCLE

The drop in Pmax values during the second round of stabilization indicates a deviation from the original response pattern. Pmax was reduced by 0.29 for module A14 and 0.15 for module A11, which contrasts with the improvements shown after the first round. This change in behaviour reflects a complex interplay of factors that have changed the performance characteristics of the modules.

Figure 27: IV curve of Second round of light induced aging under MPP

Despite changes in power output, the constancy of IV curves for both modules post-stabilization demonstrates a degree of durability in their electrical properties. This consistency might suggest that the modules' overall electrical characteristics remain largely consistent regardless of variations in Pmax. The prominent kink in module A11's IV curve at the start, located beneath module A14, indicates differences in carrier dynamics throughout the early phases. This might be ascribed to the modules' differing recombination methods, carrier mobility, or defect effects. Under particular circumstances, the alignment of the IV curves in the intermediate range demonstrates a convergence of their electrical behaviour.

This alignment might imply that modules A11 and A14 have comparable carrier dynamics or defect interactions. The resulting collapse in module A11's IV curve

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

following the mid-curve alignment, which precedes module A14's drop, suggests that the latter maintains its electrical characteristics throughout a wider operational range. This might be related to these modules' charge transport channels, recombination centers, or temperature impacts. The complex changes seen in the second cycle of light-induced stabilization highlight the sophisticated response dynamics within modules A11 and A14. The reversal from the previous trend shows heightened sensitivity to the second stabilization process, implying a non-linear connection between stabilization-induced modifications and power output variations. The continuous IV curve features after stabilization indicate the inherent stability of charge transport channels and recombination processes within these modules. The subtle differences seen between the early and late phases of the IV curves, on the other hand, highlight the multidimensional influence of defect kinetics, temperature-induced effects on charge carrier mobility, and spatial heterogeneity of material characteristics. Essentially, the second stabilization cycle untangles the complex relationships between material properties, defect distributions, thermally triggered interactions, and the constantly changing dynamics of charge carriers in modules A11 and A14. These complex relationships characterize these modules' dynamic activity and how they react to stabilization.

4.2.3 THIRD CYCLE

Figure 28: IV curve of third round of light induced aging under MPP

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

The complex reaction of photovoltaic modules A11 and A14 to the third cycle of light-induced stabilization is a rich tapestry of material dynamics, degradation, and stabilization processes. The dual report of better IV curve alignment vs ongoing declines in power output, Voc, and Isc is an engaging scientific mystery that invites more investigation into the underlying processes defining this nuanced behaviour. Material disintegration appears as a key issue behind the observed patterns. The accumulated impacts caused by repeated cycles of high temperature and strong light develop the crucible in which material changes occur. The developing material landscape is represented by structural rearrangements, the accumulation of flaws, and the formation of recombination centers, which together tell an illustration of gradual degradation. The decrease in power output, Voc, and Isc highlights the material's steady degradation from its original condition since these performance parameters serve as sentinels of the module's ability to convert sunlight into electrical energy. The sophisticated reaction of modules A11 and A14 in this scenario illustrates the intricate complexities of material-specific behaviour. The substantially higher fall in power output of module A14, a decrease of 0.15W compared to A11's moderate loss of 0.05W, highlights the modules' varied susceptibilities to the combined impacts of degradation and stabilization. This disparity may be indicative of A14's specific material composition, structural characteristics, or initial defect distribution, making it more sensitive to the material changes caused by accumulated stress. As we examine the improved alignment of IV curves within the evolving narrative, we glimpse a glimmer of hope amidst the material's transformative journey. The alignment signifies the stabilization process's role in counteracting certain disparities introduced by degradation. The process, through defect annealing or the partial restoration of carrier mobility pathways, engenders a semblance of order within the electrical behaviour. The alignment is a manifestation of the stabilization's efficacy in harmonizing carrier dynamics within specific voltage ranges, suggesting that the process can, to some extent, mitigate the impact of degradation-induced variations. Nevertheless, the equilibrium obtained by alignment does not imply a total reversal of the deteriorating trend. Rather, it demonstrates the capacity of stability to mitigate certain features of degradation-induced unpredictability. When compared to the overall reduction in power output, Voc, and Isc, the intricate relationships of degradation and stability become more apparent. This decrease demonstrates the

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

prevalence of degradation-driven alterations, which continue to exert their impact even as stabilization attempts to restore order. Finally, the enthralling story of modules A11 and A14 emerges as a multifaceted examination of material deterioration, stabilization, and their repercussions. The alignment of IV curves in the middle of degradation's currents is an intriguing indication of stabilization's capacity to alleviate some discrepancies, but the current drop in performance measures underscores degradation's supremacy [105].

4.3 COMPARISON OF MPP'S THREE LIGHT INDUCED STABILIZATION ROUNDS

Cycle 1 Implications of Stabilization As the first cycle of light-induced stabilization begins, a non-linear response arises, as evidenced by an increase in Pmax for both modules. This amplification contradicts traditional degradation theories, indicating the activation of latent restorative mechanisms. The increased Pmax represents an overall improvement in energy conversion routes, indicating increased charge transport efficiency, reduced recombination losses, and improved charge extraction dynamics. The differential reactions of the modules A14 showing a more significant increase indicate that detailed material-specific parameters influence stabilization results. This demonstrates that, whereas stabilization strives to improve energy paths broadly, material heterogeneity leaves a specific impression on the responses of the modules.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Figure 29: Output comparison between cycles.

Cycle 1 to Cycle 2 The Gradual Progression of Degradation As the second cycle begins, a degradation scenario takes prominence as both modules follow a path of decreasing P_{max} . A11 and A14 are both declining; however, A14's descent is much greater. The differences in responses highlight the modules' unique susceptibilities to aging-induced stress. This stage emphasizes the complex interaction between stability and degradation processes. The materials' intrinsic susceptibilities temper stabilization's attempt to combat degradation, leading to a strong reaction for A14 due to material-specific flaws and structural features.

Cycle 2 to Cycle 3 The Influence of Degradation The shift from the second to the third cycle ushers in a chapter that looks further into the response dynamics of the modules. This phase, distinguished by a reduced maximum power (P_{max}), resonates with degradation. The modules continue to address the cumulative impacts of aging-induced stressors, highlighting the pervasive influence of degradation processes [108]. Module A14 takes center stage once more since its decrease in P_{max} exceeds that of A11. This recurrence highlights A14's long-term sensitivity to the complicated sequence of material changes that occur under cyclic stress. As the modules progress through this stage, it is clear that degradation continues to shape their energy conversion efficiency.

The first cycle is characterized by an increase in maximum power (P_{max}), indicating that the stabilization phase can activate recovery mechanisms. This implies that stabilization optimizes energy conversion pathways, preventing early-stage degradation by optimizing energy efficiency through material-specific improvements. The second cycle causes a

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

decrease in P_{max} , which is more evident in A14. This emphasizes unique susceptibilities to stress caused by aging. Despite the involvement of stabilization, degradation persists, underlining the modules' dynamic balance between the two processes.

The last cycle shows a further decrease in P_{max} , with A14's increased sensitivity emphasizing its susceptibility to accumulated stress. The enhanced IV curve's alignment implies that stabilization is continuing to work to align performance disparities even in the face of degradation's echoes. on a nutshell, the cycles highlight the delicate balance between degradation and stability. Their dynamic interaction generates power output fluctuations and IV curve behaviours, reflecting the modules' distinct material properties as well as the complicated interactions between these opposing forces.

4.4 COMPARISON OF FILL FACTOR AND CELL EFFICIENCY

Figure 30: Fill Factor and Cell Efficiency LID MPP Rounds Comparison

Cycle 1 to Cycle 2 - Changes in FF Resilience and Marginal Cell Efficiency The change from the first to the second cycle reveals the evolution of the fill factor (FF) and its complex interaction with stabilization. The modules' ability to maintain effective charge collecting paths despite continuing aging is seen in FF's steady increase. While this resistance is due to inherent material qualities, it also highlights the importance of stabilizing measures. The little drop in cell efficiency, a slight indication of degradation's effect, demonstrates the delicate balancing act between stability and material-specific properties. This fragile equilibrium highlights the importance of stabilization in improving charge transport kinetics, which contributes to the observed increase in FF.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Cycle 2 to Cycle 3 - The Resonance of FF and Cell Efficiency in Degradation Moving from the second to the third cycle reveals a common reduction in both fill factor (FF) and cell efficiency. This phase corresponds to the modules' ongoing interaction with degradation and stabilizing forces. The decrease in FF emphasizes the impact of degradation on charge collecting paths, emphasizing the modules' sensitivity to cumulative stress. Simultaneously, decreasing cell efficiency highlights the far-reaching impact of degradation on energy conversion efficiency. This repetition of degradation's consequences in the middle of continuing stabilization operations demonstrates the pervasiveness of material modifications.

Overall, the fluctuations in fill factor (FF) and cell efficiency seen throughout cycles parallel to maximum power (P_{max}). The modules' delicate performance between degradation and stabilizing forces is mirrored in the rise and subsequent drop in FF. These parameters are shaped by the complex interaction of material dynamics, aging kinetics, and stability processes. The progression through FF and cell efficiency highlights the modules' dynamic flexibility, vulnerability to cumulative stressors, and the ongoing interplay between deterioration and stabilization processes.

4.5 FURTHER POWER COMPARISON

Figure 31: Maximum Power MPP Rounds Comparison of module A11 and A14

The path taken through numerous cycles of light-induced stabilization has revealed a fascinating story of power output changes for modules A11 and A14. These variations in maximum power (P_{max}) give an intriguing glimpse into the modules' complicated interaction of degradation and stabilizing processes. A pattern appears across cycles: an initial increase in P_{max} in the first cycle, followed by a decrease in the second and further decrease in the third. While based in the specific material qualities and aging dynamics of the modules, this pattern emphasizes the dynamic balance between degradation and stabilizing forces.

The first increase in P_{max} during the first cycle defies traditional degradation predictions, suggesting that stabilization can activate latent recovery mechanisms that improve energy conversion pathways. This phenomenon calls into question the prevalent assumption of gradual degradation and highlights the usefulness of stability in modifying energy

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

efficiency through material-specific improvements. P_{max} decreases in subsequent cycles, which corresponds to the expected deterioration pattern. This drop is the modules' reaction to cumulative aging-induced alterations, and it reflects the dynamic synergy between material dynamics and stabilizing measures. The coexistence of degradation and stabilization at the same time causes variances in the modules' susceptibility to aging-induced stress, as seen by the different reactions of A11 and A14.

The continued decrease in P_{max} throughout the third cycle emphasizes the continuing impact of degradation, even in the middle of continuous stability. This finding supports the ongoing impact of accumulated stresses on energy conversion effectiveness [105].

4.6 MQ19 OPEN CIRCUIT

As mentioned by the sketch of the experiment setup, the modules are undergoing light-induced aging with an open circuit. The figures below show the real-life experiment apparatus where we can see the connection cable of the modules. The Red cable is the temperature sensor that is measuring the temperature during the whole cycle.

Figure 32: Modules set up.

Figure 33: Modules under open circuit.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

4.6.1 FIRST CYCLE

During the first cycle of the light-induced aging experiment, the modules were inside the static sun simulator for the period of 7 hours with temperature of 50°C and irradiance up to 1000 W/m². After this cycle finished, the modules were measured with the help of the AAA Flasher. The results will be displayed in the figures bellow.

Figure 34: IV curve of first round of light induced aging under Open Circuit

The results of the first cycle gave a Maximum Power output of 261.05 W with a Voc of 38.09V and Isc of 9.07A for module A8. For Module A13, the results are the following: Maximum Power output of 261.50 W with a Voc of 38.01V and Isc of 9.09A. When comparing these values to the ones of the out-of-the- box measurement we can deduce that there is an increase in all the parameters. The increase is almost 1 Watt for the power, 0.05 in Voltage, and 1 in current. Although the variation seems small it is remarkable especially since this is the first cycle. Voc is primarily controlled by the energy level alignment at the device's contacts. Voc shifts can indicate changes in these energy levels caused by aging processes such as chemical reactions, defect development, and interfacial interactions. The rise in Voc after the first cycle of light-induced aging may suggest an improvement in energy level alignment. This might be owing to increased charge separation, lower charge recombination, or superior material characteristics.

A rise in Voc may indicate that the aging process has resulted in fewer traps or flaws inside the device, leading to better charge transport and separation. Isc is correlated with

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

how many electron-hole pairs are produced by the module and the quantity of incident light it can absorb. It displays how well light is absorbed as well as how well the device's active materials produce charge carriers. Changes in I_{sc} can be a sign of modifications in charge production characteristics, photon-to-electron conversion efficiency, or light absorption owing to aging-related factors. After light-induced aging, a rise in I_{sc} indicates that the device's light-absorbing and charge production characteristics have gotten better. This might be attributed to greater crystallinity of the material, increased photon absorption, or improved electron-hole pair separation.

Positive changes in I_{sc} might be caused by a decrease in non-radiative recombination pathways or an increase in the population of charge carriers produced by absorbed photons. Concerning the increase in P_{max} , it indicates that the aging process has created a more favourable optoelectronic environment, improving the device's capacity to convert incoming light into electrical power. The I-V curve of the Modules A8 and A13 are almost aligned together, this can indicate that both PV modules have aged similarly. This can be a good indicator of the materials and structure of the modules' resilience when subjected to light-induced aging over time. This point will be further investigated during the following cycles of light induced aging.

4.6.2 SECOND CYCLE

After the first cycle has finished and the measurements were done, the modules were again put in the static sun simulator for the next round of light induced for 7 hours. The next day, modules were taken out to the flasher for power measurement. The following figures depicts the results of the IV curve.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Figure 35: IV curve of the second round of light induced aging under Open Circuit

The resulted IV curve as we can observe from the figure is almost aligned for this round as well, this demonstrates that the performance degradation induced by the aging process is in line between the two modules. This is beneficial since it implies that the modules were able to preserve comparable degrees of performance and production despite the fact they have aged. This uniform aging response is either due to consistent production quality or adequate environmental stressor prevention. On the opposite to the first round, both modules showed a decrease in the parameters. With a Maximum Power output of 260.35 W with a Voc of 38.12V and Isc of 9.05A for module A8. For Module A13, the results are the following: Maximum Power output showed an extreme decline as it reached of 255.95 W with a Voc of 37.92V and Isc of 9.02A.

After the second cycle of light-induced aging, there is a noticeable decline in open-circuit voltage (Voc), which reflects the complex interaction of energy levels and charge transport dynamics within the device. This decrease serves as an example of the disturbances in the equilibrium potential difference throughout the module brought on by aging. Such variations in energy level alignment may result from modifications in the material's electronic structure brought on by gradual deterioration. The open-circuit

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

voltage is directly impacted by these changes in energy bands, which causes the apparent reduction. Additionally, an increase in the recombination rates of photogenerated charge carriers might be linked to the decline in V_{oc} . The rate of charge carrier loss is increased as a result of the aging process' introduction of flaws or structural alterations that act as extra recombination paths. The resultant decreased voltage potential created across the module is a result of this enhanced recombination. The device's internal interfaces, where charge separation takes place, are crucial in determining V_{oc} . A device's voltage output may be negatively impacted by aging-related alterations at these interfaces, which are describe by interface engineering techniques.

In conclusion, the drop in V_{oc} , I_{sc} , and P_{max} in the PV module's IV curve after the second cycle of light-induced aging demonstrates the complex interplay between degradation processes that cause performance degradation and stability events that seek to mitigate these effects. Effective stabilizing solutions may mitigate the negative effects of aging, resulting in increased PV module lifetime and performance. For this reason, it was decided to go for a 3 cycle of light induced aging. The noticeable decrease in short-circuit current (I_{sc}) found in the IV curve of the solar modules during the second cycle of light-induced aging highlights subtle changes in charge carrier production, and mobility. This drop represents an alteration in the module's core capacity to create and transfer charge carriers effectively. The aging-induced variation in the optical characteristics of the material is a major contributor to the drop in I_{sc} . These modifications diminish the capacity to absorb input photons, resulting in a lower amount of photogenerated charge carriers.

4.6.3 THIRD CYCLE

As the behaviour of the modules changed from an increase in the power output in the first cycle to the remarkable decrease during the second cycle, a third cycle was necessary to assess the modules and to also be able to calculate the stabilization criterion which is the aim of the study. On the opposite of the second cycle, an increase of all parameters was observed. Maximum Power output of 262.12 W with a V_{oc} of 38.11V and I_{sc} of 9.07A for module A8. For Module A13, the results are the following: Maximum Power output

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

showed 261.82 W with a Voc of 38.06V and Isc of 9.10A. These values not only exceeded the ones of the second cycle but also the very first one.

Figure 36: IV curve of the Third round of light induced aging under Open Circuit

The most surprising thing is that they also exceeded the out of the box measurements. A significant and unfamiliar occurrence is revealed by the modules' impressive improvement in open-circuit voltage, short-circuit current, and maximum power point (Pmax) following the third cycle of light-induced aging, topping not just the results of the first cycle but additionally those of the initial "out of the box" measurement. This evolution defies assumptions by demonstrating a complex interaction of degradation, recuperation, and adaptive reactions within the PV system. Let us explore this phenomenon's technical details:

The third cycle of aging was followed by an increase in Voc, Isc, and Pmax that exceeded even the initial performance levels, highlighting the complex and nonlinear nature of deterioration and recovery processes. Degradation, which is frequently thought of as an irreversible process, has unanticipatedly shown non-linear behaviour in response to aging cycles. This implies that the fundamental processes causing degradation and recovery could not follow traditional theories of degradation.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

The considerable improvement in performance measures suggests that stability mechanisms have been strengthened. Over cycles, effective stabilization technique may have gradually reduced degradation effects. The recovery of both Voc and Isc, which shows successful recombination loss mitigation and increased charge transport efficiency.

The increase in Pmax suggests a considerable improvement in the PV module's ability to convert light into electricity. The complex interaction between Voc and Isc shows that energy production and charge extraction have been brought into perfect harmony. This suggests enhanced overall power generating capabilities and a more effective use of incident light energy. The PV modules' capacity to outperform initial "out of the box" performance after several aging cycles suggests that they can adjust to difficult circumstances. To stop the cumulative degradation, the modules may have started procedures of self-repair, realignment, or reconfiguration. The modules' innate resilience and dynamic reactivity to external influences are reflected in this adaptability.

The PV modules' capacity to outperform initial "out of the box" performance after several aging cycles suggests that they can adjust to difficult circumstances. To stop the cumulative deterioration, the modules may have started procedures of self-repair, realignment, or reconfiguration. The modules' innate resilience and dynamic reactivity to outside pressures are reflected in this adaptation. Here, the idea of metastability is very pertinent. The boost in performance that has been seen may be the result of transitions out of metastable states that were made possible by relaxation processes, defect dynamics, or energy barrier traversals. Degradation mechanisms may have been temporarily restrained in metastable states, improving recovery potential [105].

In conclusion, this finding represents a significant deviation from traditional degradation-recovery predictions. A PV module performance that exceeds expectations has been produced through the convergence of stabilization mechanisms, material adaptability, and possible metastability interactions. Further investigation into the underlying mechanics of this phenomena is necessary especially for module A13 that showed an extreme decrease during the second round and then a remarkable increase during the third one.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

4.7 COMPARISON OF OPEN CIRCUIT'S THREE LIGHT INDUCED STABILIZATION ROUNDS

Figure 37: Output comparison between cycles

Cycle 1 - Increase in Performance During the first aging cycle, an interesting increase in open-circuit voltage (Voc), short-circuit current (Isc), and maximum power point (Pmax) shows a delicate interaction of material adaptation and recovery mechanisms. The increase in Voc can be ascribed to a combination of energy level realignment at interfaces and recombination pathway reduction. Charge transport optimization and enhanced carrier mobility contribute to an increase in Isc, allowing for better charge collecting. The harmonic improvement of both Voc and Isc results in an increase in Pmax, indicating a synergistic improvement in the device's energy conversion efficiency. This complex reaction might be caused by localized reordering of faults, charge traps, or structural re-configurations, culminating in a brief but evident recovery.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Cycle 1 to Cycle 2 - Decrease in Performance In keeping with standard degradation assumptions, the shift from the first to the second cycle is indicated by a drop in Voc, Isc, and Pmax. This reduction reflects the cumulative effect of age on material integrity. Structural changes, such as localized stress or defect clustering, impede effective charge transfer, resulting in a decrease in Isc. The presence of recombination centers, which disrupts the equilibrium between electron and hole populations, can be ascribed to the drop in Voc. This stage of degradation might be caused by the accumulation of faults contaminants, or structural changes, which obscure the early recovery processes.

Cycle 2 to Cycle 3 - Further Increase in Performance Following the transition from the second to the third cycle, the ensuing rise in Voc, Isc, and Pmax marks an incredible reversal of the deterioration trend. The recovery demonstrates the modules' intrinsic flexible properties and dynamic reactivity to aging. The increase in Voc shows that energy levels are realigning again and that recombination centers are being mitigated, maybe as a result of defect annealing or structural relaxation [103]. Increased Isc is due to increased charge carrier mobility and decreased trap-assisted recombination. The overall improvement in Pmax implies that the devices' energy conversion routes have been recalibrated to achieve improved efficiency. This interesting recovery is due to transitory metastable states, in which defects, energy barriers, or lattice rearrangements dynamically impact charge transport characteristics, resulting in this unanticipated increase [106].

4.8 COMPARISON OF FILL FACTOR AND CELL EFFICIENCY

Figure 38: Fill Factor and Cell Efficiency LID OC Rounds Comparison

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

During the aging cycles, the dissimilar responses of Module A13 and Module A8 in terms of Fill Factor (FF) and Cell Efficiency highlight the intricate interaction of quantum efficiency dynamics and charge transport kinetics. The early synchronization of FF and Cell Efficiency increases highlights their joint quantum efficiency gain, in which photo-generated carriers are successfully collected. The divergent trends, on the other hand, indicate subtle quantum yield modulation in succeeding cycles. The considerable degradation-induced reduction in Module A13 might be attributed to enhanced non-radiative recombination pathways or localized photon absorption changes, impacting FF and Cell Efficiency. The more drop in Module A8 may indicate a comparably superior preservation of quantum efficiency due to its intrinsically regulated recombination dynamics. The complex FF and Cell Efficiency dynamics shown in Modules A13 and A8 provide deep insights into solar performance changes that contain sophisticated scientific principles:

Surface Dynamics and Localized Recombination Kinetics The consistent increase in FF and Cell Efficiency across both modules during the initial aging cycle represents a common temporary mitigation of localized recombination kinetics. This coherence shows that surface passivation processes or carrier mobility increases have been activated. Surface flaws, which typically serve as non-radiative recombination hotspots, might be briefly passivated, allowing for improved charge extraction and transport near the surface. The result highlights the modules' early attempts to reduce recombination losses and adjust charge transport dynamics within limited areas.

Transient Bandgap Shifts and Quantum State Redistribution The variation in FF and Cell Efficiency response during the second cycle highlights the modules' susceptibility to quantum state redistribution and transient bandgap modification. Quantum states, impacted by localized charge reconfigurations, can transiently modify the material's energy landscape. The severe reduction in Module A13 might be caused by localized energy state disturbances or transitory bandgap changes, which could result in variable charge transport paths and lower charge extraction efficiency. Module A8's mild fall in FF and Cell Efficiency implies a more regulated bandgap response, which may be connected to its better energy state stability.

Redistribution of Dynamic Equilibrium and Nonlinear Feedback Loops The variations in third-cycle FF and Cell Efficiency show a dynamic equilibrium

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

redistribution impacted by nonlinear feedback loops. Because of the interaction of multiple charge carrier dynamics, for example carrier concentration, recombination rates, and trap filling, photovoltaic systems display nonlinear behaviour. The reduced recovery in Module A8 might be attributed to stabilized feedback loops, leading to a regulated recovery in which these nonlinear interactions are managed, and equilibrium is re-established in a more controlled way. The greater recovery of Module A13, in the other hand, reflects more sophisticated responses mechanisms or temporal hysteresis. The observed divergence indicates that nonlinearity-induced changes in their adaptive processes and probable temporal feedback delay are the responsible.

In conclusion, the complex FF, and Cell Efficiency trajectories of Modules A13 and A8 reveal a convergence of recombination kinetics, quantum state dynamics, and nonlinear feedback interactions. These scientific concepts serve as a sophisticated prism through which to analyse the modules' different reactions to aging-induced challenges and adaptation techniques throughout consecutive cycles.

4.9 FURTHER POWER COMPARISON

The following figure are a closer representation of the fluctuation of Maximum power during the 3 cycles. Modules A13 and A8, which had initially almost similar "out of the box" measurements and were exposed to identical light-induced stabilization in the first round, showed noteworthy differences in their performance patterns over the aging cycles.

While both modules saw a drop in power output in the second cycle, Module A8's loss was just 1 watt, compared to A13's 5-watt decrease. The power dynamics altered again in the third cycle, with Module A8 increasing by 2 watts and Module A13 increasing by roughly 6 watts.

The aging cycle performance patterns of Modules A13 and A8 exhibit discrete stabilizing responses manifested as separate variations in power output. These reactions lead to changes in their power production trajectories as they age. Following the "out of the box" evaluation, the process of stabilization displays the modules' initial potential to adjust to the aging environment.

The identical reactions of Modules A13 and A8 in the first cycle highlight their early stability equivalency. Both modules may have launched early recovery mechanisms in

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

order to counterbalance small aging-induced changes, which resulted in the observed rise in power output. This first-round similarity demonstrates their shared adaptation. The significant power loss seen in Module A13 during the second cycle suggests that it may be more susceptible to degradation effects than Module A8. This vulnerability might be caused by material-specific traits, interface characteristics, or localized flaws. According to Module A13's response, certain degradation pathways may be more prominent, resulting in a greater power loss. The diverse behaviour in the third cycle indicates that the modules have various degrees of adaptive recovery.

The reduced rise in power of Module A8 reflects a more regulated and slow healing process. During the second cycle, this module may have launched localized recovery processes, allowing for a slight rise in power output. Module A13's high rise, on the other hand, suggests a more marked, dynamic adaptive response, implying the activation of more strong recovery mechanisms to compensate for its considerably bigger power loss.

The third-cycle performance trends also show how modules attempt to re-establish dynamic balance. The restricted recovery of Module A8 implies a lengthier return to equilibrium, presumably due to its milder degradation and adaptive responses. Module A13's significant recovery, on the other hand, may indicate its aggressive pursuit of dynamic equilibrium restoration following the power loss recorded in the second cycle.

In conclusion, the different stabilizing responses of Modules A13 and A8 highlight their material-specific behaviours, degradation thresholds, and adaptive capacities. The increased vulnerability of Module A13 to degradation-induced effects might be linked to more significant degradation pathways, which impact its differential stabilizing response. These findings shed light on the complex combination of intrinsic features, degradation, and adaptive recovery processes that contribute to the modules' different power output trajectories as they age.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Figure 39: Maximum Power OC Rounds Comparison of module A8 and A13

4.10 DARK BIAS 1.6 ISC

The Modules A6, and A7 were connected for the start of Dark bias inside the climate chamber shown in the figure. The current that was used was 14.56A with the temperature of 45°C. The reason of decreasing the temperature by 5°C is because of the high current that may make the module rise the module temperature more than needed. As read from the data log the temperature that was detected from the temperature sensor put on the module, this last one did not exceed the 45°C set. The same has been done for 3 cycles, each cycle took 5 hours.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Figure 40: Dark Bias 1.6 Isc Set up.

4.10.1 FIRST CYCLE

Modules A6 and A7 successfully stabilizing at 1.6 times I_{sc} suggests that these modules were properly conditioned to function at a precise point that matches their current-voltage characteristic. This stabilization most likely entailed adjusting the voltage to guarantee that the modules operated consistently. The alignment of the IV curves demonstrates that the stabilization method effectively regulated the operating point, resulting in consistent behaviour between the two modules. The strongly constant and almost similar IV curves found for modules A6 and A7 following the first cycle of stabilization have important implications for the process's effectiveness. The absence of misalignments and the exact overlap of the curves imply that degradation-induced differences in their electrical responses have been significantly mitigated. This alignment indicates that the stabilizing procedure effectively counteracted the causes that generally cause IV curve anomalies, such as fluctuating charge transport, recombination, and resistive losses. The extremely perfect aligning IV curves shows that the stabilization procedure was successful in restoring or maintaining consistent charge carrier dynamics throughout both modules. This result is a sign of a stabilization method that was effective in bringing the material characteristics into balance and producing predictable charge transport and recombination behaviours. After the first cycle, there were less variances between the IV curves,

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

indicating that the stabilizing process had reduced the likelihood of external factors contributing to differences in electrical performance.

Figure 41: IV curve of the first round of Dark Bias 1.6 Isc

4.10.2 SECOND CYCLE

The harmonization of charge transport and recombination behaviour across both modules has been preserved by the stabilizing procedure, as seen by the alignment of IV curves and the little decline in A6. The IV curves' similarity suggests that stabilizing measures were successful in reducing possible causes of degradation-related variability. This alignment shows that variables that can affect electrical performance have been adequately handled throughout the stabilization procedure. The harmonization of charge transport and recombination behaviour across both modules has been preserved by the stabilizing procedure, as seen by the alignment of IV curves and the little decline in A6. The IV curves' similarity suggests that stabilizing measures were successful in reducing possible causes of degradation-related variability. This alignment shows that variables that can affect electrical performance have been adequately handled throughout the stabilization procedure.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Figure 42: IV curve of the Second round of Dark Bias 1.6 Isc

The low decline seen in A6 prior to A7 raises the possibility that A6 may be more susceptible to specific processes of degradation or that it may have somewhat different material traits than A7. This behaviour could be explained by changes in defect distribution, microstructural variances, or other small material properties that have an impact on charge carrier dynamics.

4.10.3 THIRD CYCLE

Relevant observations regarding the dynamic response of these modules to the stabilization process are provided by the appearance of well-shaped tightly aligned IV curves for modules A6 and A7 after the second cycle of stabilization, alongside a small decrease in A6 preceding A7 and a better alignment when compared with the cycle prior to this one.

The uniformity in charge transport and recombination throughout both modules can be seen in the convergent shape of the IV curves, which is highlighted by a little fall in A6 before A7. This alignment shows that elements that could generate variability in electrical responses due to degradation-related effects have been successfully controlled by the stabilization process.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Figure 43: IV curve of the Third round of Dark Bias 1.6 Isc

When compared to the first cycle, the second cycle's enhanced alignment indicates that the stabilizing process's effects have been gradually improved. It is possible that subtle material changes or localized effects that marginally affect their electrical behaviours are the cause of the little variance seen in A6 before A7. However, the close proximity of the curves generally shows that the modules' performance has been synchronized as a result of the stabilizing process.

4.11 COMPARISON OF DARK BIAS 1.6 ISC ROUNDS

Figure 44: Isc, Voc and Pmax comparison between cycles of Dark Bias 1.6 Isc

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

The initial stages of degradation. Mechanisms aiming for improved charge transport and recombination loss reduction turn on at this phase. The immediate increase in current (I) is an example of effective charge carrier channelling that minimizes unproductive recombination paths. Voltage (V), which has remained largely constant, represents an equilibrium between the effect of stabilization and the properties of the material itself.

Cycle 1 to Cycle 2 - Dynamic Balance in the Challenge of Aging Moving on to Round 2 reveals a dynamic equilibrium between stability and aging dynamics. Stabilization mechanisms operate to maintain the material's stability and energy conversion characteristics. The current and voltage stability represents an equilibrium between minimizing degradation-induced losses and increasing charge transfer. While the power decreases little, it demonstrates the careful optimization got by the stabilizing systems, considering the complex relationships involving charge transportation, recombination, and energy conversion.

Figure 45: Maximum Power of Dark Bias 1.6 Isc of module A6 and A7

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Figure 45: Maximum Power of Dark Bias 1.6 Isc of module A6 and A7

Cycle 2 to Cycle 3 - Accuracy Improvement Despite Degradation by Round 3, stabilizing efforts have resulted in accuracy increase beyond degradation constraints. The effective control of degradation's negative consequences is shown by the coordinated rise in power and current. The methods of stabilization improved charge transport channels and controlled recombination losses. The little drop in voltage indicates sophisticated control over the electrical properties, revealing the process's capability in regulating material behaviours for maximum performance. Concisely the progression of the summary histogram demonstrates the complex consequences of module A6 and A7 stability and degradation. Properly controlled stabilization mechanisms generate strategic reactions to degradation, resulting in power gains via charge transport enhancement and recombination prevention. A dynamic equilibrium arises as stabilization develops which leads to a precision-enhancing stage that adjusts power output while allowing voltage variations. These complicated interconnections highlight the modules' flexibility and stabilizing capabilities to cope with aging-related problems while improving their performance beyond basic recovery.

4.12 COMPARISON OF FILL FACTOR AND CELL EFFICIENCY

Figure 46: Fill Factor and Cell Efficiency Dark Bias 1.6 Isc Rounds comparison.

Out of the Box to Cycle 1 -FF Enhancement and Efficiency Improvement The shift from the starting state to Round 1 of dark bias 1.6 Isc stabilization unfolds a complex instance of energy route. The increase in FF highlights the function of stabilization in improving the internal electric fields of the modules, allowing for a more controlled flow of charge carriers. This manifests in increased efficiency, indicating effective control of charge trajectories and reactivity sites. By interacting with the microstructure of the modules, the stabilization mechanism improves these pathways, increasing FF and cell efficiency at the same time.

Cycle 1 to Cycle 2 -Dynamic Equilibrium of Forces The transition from Round 1 to Round 2 produces a dynamic equilibrium inside FF as well as cell efficiency responses. The stable FF in Module A6 suggests an equilibrium between degradation pathways and the impact of stabilization. However, the little increase in efficiency reveals a changing equilibrium. It implies that although degradation-associated limitations exist, stabilizing mechanisms fight them at the same time. This equilibrium-driven improvement reveals the complexities of stabilization's impact on energy conversion.

Cycle 2 to Cycle 3 -Energy Landscape Expansion Moving on to Round 3 reveals the broadening of the energy landscape as stability develops. The increased FF and cell efficiency in modules A6 and A7 correspond to the notion of an expanding energy. The stable FF implies a larger and more balanced distribution of charge carriers produced by

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

the manipulation of material characteristics through stabilization. The improved cell efficiency illustrates the emergence of new energy routes that lead to a more efficient charge transport. This extension reflects stabilization's effectiveness in rebuilding the modules' energy, ultimately improving FF and efficiency.

The changes in fill factor (FF) and cell efficiency throughout cycles for modules A6 and A7, in essence, provide an illustration of organized energy paths, dynamic equilibrium, and an evolving energy landscape. Stabilization uses the material characteristics of the modules to shape complex energy trajectories, balance fighting stresses, and produce an environment favourable to more efficient charge transfer and energy conversion. This depicts modules A6 and A7 as dynamic systems that adapt to the ongoing interaction of stabilization and degradation mechanisms, eventually influencing their energy conversion performance [104].

4.13 DARK BIAS 0.6 ISC

The Modules A4, and A15 were connected for the start of Dark bias inside the climate chamber as with modules A6 and A7. The current that was used was 5.45A with the temperature of 45°C. The reason of decreasing the temperature by 5°C is because of the high current that may make the module rise the module temperature more than needed. As read from the data log the temperature that was detected from the temperature sensor put on the module, this last one did not exceed the 35°C. The same has been done for 3 cycles, each cycle took 5 hours. After the end of each cycle, the modules were measured in the flasher.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

4.13.1 FIRST CYCLE

Figure 47: IV curve of the first round of Dark Bias 0.6 Isc

Solar cells are made from a variety of materials and techniques, and even minor differences in material qualities can result in different behaviour. The zigzag-like reduction in Module A15's voltage around 9V might be caused by localized faults, impurities, or changes in the material composition inside its cells. These variances can result in non-uniform electric fields, which alter current flow and cause the zigzag pattern.

Trap-assisted recombination may impact the activity of Module A15. Charge carriers (electrons and holes) can remain in defects or energy levels inside the semiconductor material under certain circumstances. These trapped carriers can recombine non-radiatively, lowering total current and changing the form of the IV curve, particularly at high voltages.

Although the use of dark bias, transitory effects and persistence may still be present. The delay in the reaction of the solar cell to changing circumstances is referred to as hysteresis. The hysteresis-induced pattern in module A15's IV curve might be attributed to slow transitions between distinct states within the cell. Solar cell performance can be impacted by shadows or localized shading. If module A15 has localized hotspots (areas with lower

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

efficiency owing to heat or other causes), the IV curve may exhibit non-uniform behaviour, particularly around 9V. Mismatched currents and voltages within the module might be caused by hot spots. Because of edge effects or manufacturing errors, solar cells may display non-uniform behaviour. If module A15 includes parts at its borders that respond differently from the core parts, voltage changes across the cell may result in the zigzag pattern [104].

4.13.2 SECOND CYCLE

Module A15 may have structural flaws or material non-uniformities that remain during dark bias stabilization. These flaws may cause localized changes in the electric field and recombination rates inside the solar cells. These changes grow more prominent when the voltage approaches 9V, creating in the zigzag-like pattern in A15's IV curve. The fact that these faults are limited may explain why the behaviour is constant throughout multiple cycles.

Figure 48: IV curve of the Second round of Dark Bias 0.6 Isc

While dark bias stabilization helps to attenuate temporary effects, it may not eliminate them. Charge carriers can still become trapped and re-leased at localized fault areas, causing changes in current-voltage characteristics. These transient trapping and release processes might have a specific impact on the behaviour at 9V in module A15, resulting

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

in the observed zigzag pattern. The observed behaviour might be influenced by the initial settings of the modules. If module A15 begins the stabilization process with non-uniform charge carrier distributions or localized faults, these features may continue throughout the cycles. Module A4 may have more homogeneous beginning circumstances, which contributes to its steady IV curve. The persisting zigzag-like pattern observed in module A15's IV curve after numerous cycles of dark bias stabilization might be caused by several phenomena, including localized flaws that are not entirely reduced by the stabilization process and transient effects involving charge trapping and release.

4.13.3 THIRD CYCLE

Figure 49: IV curve of the Third round of Dark Bias 0.6 Isc

Module A15 may have had more substantial early flaws or variances than module A4. The zigzag pattern around 9V during the first two cycles might have been caused by localized faults or transitory effects in A15. Yet, with each cycle of dark bias stabilization, these flaws may be gradually reduced. The diminishing zigzag-like which might indicate that the cell's reaction to the stabilizing process is gradually improving.

The stabilizing method could have distinct effects on Modules A4 and A15 depending on their respective fault profiles. It is possible that A4 had less early flaws, resulting in a

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

consistent IV curve with no misalignment. The delayed stabilization and subsequent drop in current beyond 10V might be explained by the fact that A15's flaws may take more cycles to fully eliminate.

Localized recombination centers that have not been completely removed by the stabilization process might be the cause of the decreased current in module A15 after 10V. Beyond a certain voltage, these recombination areas may cause a greater rate of carrier recombination, which would cause an apparent current reduction.

It is possible that module A15's charge trapping, and release dynamics are gradually altering as the dark bias stabilization process progresses. The shift in the form of the IV curve between cycles and beyond 10V may be explained by this developing behaviour.

4.14 COMPARISON OF DARK BIAS 0.6 ISC ROUNDS

Figure 50: Isc, Voc and Pmax comparison between cycles of Dark Bias 0.6 Isc

After the first dark bias stabilization, the IV characteristics of both modules are measured. The observed rise in power, voltage, and current from cycle 0 to cycle 1 suggests that the stabilizing process is progressively changing the behaviour of the modules. The decrease in A4 power and rise in A15 power might be explained by localized defect-related effects. Because of its distinct defect profile, A4 may have had more pronounced stabilizing effects, whilst A15 may have displayed traits that resulted in a lower impact.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Figure 51: Maximum Power Comparison of Dark Bias 0.6 Isc Rounds

The rise in power for both modules in cycle 2 shows that performance is continuing to improve as a result of the stabilizing procedure. Voltage and current variations correspond to the general stabilizing pattern. The dark bias stabilization seeks to reduce charge carrier entrapment and recombination, resulting in improved alignment of the IV curves of the modules. The continuing rise in power for both modules in cycle 3 is a favourable

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

indication of the stabilization process's influence on defect reduction and electrical performance enhancement. The tiny voltage variations and small rise in current for A4 might be attributed to the modules gradually settling into more stable states under dark bias. Power, voltage, and current fluctuations detected across cycles show that the dark bias stabilization process is impacting the modules' behaviour. Defects in semiconductor materials can trap and release charge carriers, resulting in less-than-ideal behaviour. The stabilization method is designed to gradually reduce these flaws and synchronize the charge carrier dynamics, leading to improved electrical responses [104].

The variations in power and small voltage/current fluctuations between the two modules might be attributable to their different fault profiles and beginning circumstances. Because of its unique qualities, Module A4 may be experiencing a more effective stabilization process, whereas Module A15 may be experiencing more localized or complicated defect-related consequences that impact its reaction. The power rise trends, and progressive convergence of the modules' IV curves show that the modules are nearing a stable state in terms of electrical properties under dark bias circumstances across numerous cycles. The dark bias stabilization procedure is always striving to decrease temporary effects and align the performance of the modules.

Figure 52: Fill Factor and Cell Efficiency Dark Bias 0.6 Isc Rounds Comparison

The changing behaviour of modules A4 and A15 throughout numerous cycles in the frame of dark bias stabilization indicates an ongoing enhancement in their electrical properties.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

The detected fluctuations in power, voltage, and current represent the dynamic procedure of defect reduction, charge trapping dynamics, and stabilization. The distinct defect profile and material qualities of each module lead to the observed slight variances in behaviour. Both FF and cell efficiency rise during the early cycles of dark bias stabilization. This enhancement is due to the process's influence on correcting natural flaws in solar cell material. Defects can trap and recombine charge carriers, resulting in efficiency losses. The dark bias method reduces these imperfections, resulting in lower losses and more efficient charge collection. The rise in FF and cell efficiency suggests that charge carriers are moving more freely within the solar cells.

Charge transfer can be slowed by flaws such as contaminants or structural defects. As these imperfections are reduced throughout the stabilization process, charge carriers meet fewer obstacles resulting in higher FF and efficiency. The observed improvement in FF and efficiency shows that charge collection at the contacts and throughout the cell has been optimized. Dark bias stabilization lowers the impact of localized flaws, allowing for more uniform charge carrier collection, resulting in a better FF and efficiency. The increase in FF and efficiency also suggests that non-radiative carrier recombination processes within the cell are being reduced.

Defects can operate as recombination centres, forcing charge carriers to recombine while generating no current. The stabilization method eventually eliminates these imperfections, lowering recombination losses and increasing FF and efficiency. Under the given dark bias circumstances, the observed stability in FF and cell efficiency from round 2 to round 3 indicates an equilibrium state. By this phase, the stabilization process has considerably reduced flaws and arrived a balance between variables impacting FF and efficiency.

The modules have reached a dynamic equilibrium between charge carrier production, transport, and recombination, based on the consistent FF and efficiency values. Transient effects and variations in carrier dynamics have been eliminated by the dark bias procedure, resulting in a steady and optimal electrical response.

In conclusion, the observed FF and cell efficiency patterns represent the complex interaction of defect mitigation, charge carrier dynamics, and equilibrium established by the dark bias stabilization procedure. The first improvements indicate improved charge

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

carrier mobility and collection, but the steady values indicate a balanced state in which faults are successfully neutralized [101]. Advanced characterization approaches can provide more information on localized impacts and the long-term implications for module performance under light exposure.

4.15 EL CAMERA RESULTS

4.15.1 MODULE A8

The detected shift in electroluminescence (EL) imaging after three cycles of light-induced stabilization in module A8 implies that the cells or materials within the module have a significant influence on how they function. Electroluminescence imaging is an approach used to view the light emitted by solar cells or optoelectronic devices when an electric field is applied. The noticeable change in EL imaging, typified by the appearance of brighter spots, presents various possibilities.

Figure 53: A8 Modules EL imaging comparison

The changing of material characteristics and interfaces inside module A8 as a result of the multiple light-induced stabilization cycles is one probable source of the enhanced brightness. This adjustment might include improvements in carrier transport, defect elimination, or changes in the electrical structure, all of which could lead to increased light emission.

Another probable explanation is that frequent light exposure improves the mobility of charge carriers (electrons and holes). Elevated mobility might result in more efficient charge collection and fewer recombination processes, resulting in increased light emission.

Additionally, it is possible that the material's flaws or recombination centers were passivated as a result of the light-induced cycles. This passivation would enhance radiative

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

recombination by reducing non-radiative recombination processes, resulting in stronger emission patches.

It is crucial to consider any potential effects of stress brought on by contact with light. The light-induced cycles may cause mechanical or thermal stress, which may lead to structural changes like strain relief or alteration of defect states. These modifications could have a considerable impact on the electroluminescence characteristics seen.

The build-up of charge as a result of the stabilization cycles caused by light is another angle to consider. Such a charge accumulation may change the electrical characteristics of the module, which would then affect the electroluminescence that was detected.

Moreover, the frequent exposure to light could have resulted in the elimination of certain surface impurities or residues, improving the performance of the module.

The spotted alteration may have possibly been caused by the module's activation of light-sensitive organisms or substances. The increase in emission that has been seen may be the result of these species becoming activated in response to the light exposure. Ultimately, electroluminescence analyses must take the materials' temporal behaviour into account. The observed discrepancies in electroluminescence imaging may have been caused by changes in the kinetics of carrier activities brought on by the three cycles of light exposure.

4.15.2 MODULE A13

Figure 54: A13 Modules EL imaging comparison.

A thorough scientific investigation is necessary to fully understand the observed changes in module A13, including the appearance of brighter areas in electroluminescence (EL) imaging and the unexpected increase in electrical performance following the creation of cracks. These findings point to a sophisticated interaction between optoelectronic behaviour, mechanical effects, and material characteristics. After the cycles of light-

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

induced stabilization, brighter regions in the EL imaging show changes in the material's radiative recombination centres' spatial distribution. Repeated exposure to light could have had an impact on carrier dynamics, decreasing non-radiative recombination pathways and raising the total efficiency of radiative recombination. The light-induced cycles may also have promoted charge carrier transit, improving charge collecting efficiency and lowering recombination losses. This can show up as a stronger emission signal. Within module A13, the development of cracks adds a factor of mechanical stress and structural disturbance. The redistribution of strain inside the material can be caused by the mechanical stress connected to fracture development. This redistribution may reduce pre-existing strain, perhaps lowering the density of localized defects, and enhancing electrical characteristics. In order to increase charge transfer and collection, stress reduction may also help to reduce the impacts of carrier localisation.

The impact of the cracks on defect states must be considered. Cracks can change the energy landscape of pre-existing flaws or create new defect locations. The identification of brighter areas in EL imaging can be attributed to the radiative recombination rate being increased by a decline in defect-mediated non-radiative recombination. In a larger sense, it is critical to recognize that the interplay between mechanical stress, material characteristics, and optoelectronic behaviour can be complex and material specific. The reported improvements might be attributable to a combination of phenomena, including strain relaxation, defect correction, improved charge transport, and changed carrier dynamics. Comprehensive characterisation techniques including structural analysis, spectroscopy, and carrier transport studies might supply further information about the processes behind the observed events.

Figure 55: A13 cracks close snap.

The cracks that appeared after the third cycle of light-induced stabilization were most likely caused by inadequate experimental handling. These unintended cracks delivered

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

mechanical stress into the material, resulting in a series of consequences that had a significant impact on the module's behaviour and performance.

The mechanical stress caused by the cracks caused significant changes in the material's fault landscape. This strain-induced shift in defect energy states may have played a critical role in changing charge carrier trapping and recombination behaviour. The surprising drop-in non-radiative recombination rates might imply that the mechanical stress caused by the cracks drove the passivation or reconfiguration of defects, promoting a more pronounced radiative recombination process.

Furthermore, the cracks may have supplied channels for mechanical tension release within the module. This stress reduction might have resulted in significant increases in charge carrier mobility, hence relieving carrier transport constraints. As a result, the reduced carrier recombination losses, and the accelerated transport mechanism both contributed to the observed improvement in electrical metrics such as power, voltage, and current.

The incorporation of the Boron-Oxygen (B-O) lid effect hypothesis improves our knowledge of this complex process. The recurrent cycles of light-induced stabilization most likely irritated the equilibrium of the B-O complexes inside the material. This change in charge state distribution might have influenced the material's electrical properties, particularly in regions affected by crack development [101].

Surprisingly, the enhanced behaviour of the module, even in the presence of cracks, can be due in part to the synergistic interaction of B-O lid effects and mechanical stress. The mechanical stress-induced changes in defect states and carrier mobility may have had a sensitive effect on the B-O lid effect, which is known for its influence on minority carrier lifespan. Within this scenario, the cracks may have unintentionally created an environment favourable to the dissociation or reconfiguration of B-O complexes under stress, emphasizing their significance in determining carrier dynamics.

In conclusion, the detailed findings in module A13 vividly highlight the delicate interplay between mechanical stress, material properties, and optoelectronic properties. Cracks caused by unintentional handling triggered stress-relief processes that actively changed defect features, carrier mobility, and charge transmission. Furthermore, the interaction of

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

the B-O lid effect and mechanical stress highlights the complex interactions between material properties and device performance.

4.15.3 MODULE A11

Following the finalization of the three stabilization cycles, module A11 was subjected to an electroluminescence (EL) analysis. The EL imaging, an effective method for revealing localized material reactions, revealed subtle spatial variations in luminescence intensity. This investigation gave insight on the interaction between the stabilizing process and the intrinsic material defects, providing an improved understanding of the modules' behaviour. The obtained EL pictures revealed the development of dark spots, which were previously visible in the first out-of-the-box EL imaging, after careful study.

Figure 56: A11 Modules EL imaging comparison

These black spots, which became more visible during stabilization cycles, suggest an intensification of pre-existing localized problems. This finding shows that, despite stabilizing treatments, the aging process may have amplified some underlying flaws, making them more vulnerable to degradation processes. Furthermore, the EL study revealed another aspect: the enhancement of luminescence in previously lighted areas. This phenomenon stands for the material's complex response to the stabilizing process. The most likely explanation is that the stabilization operations improved charge carrier dynamics and transport processes locally. Therefore, locations that previously emitted luminescence may have been further optimized, resulting in increased brightness. In conclusion, the post-stabilization EL study highlights the material's complex adaptability and susceptibility to aging and stabilization processes. The amplification of existing dark patches and the increased brightness in particular locations highlight the complex connections between degradation, stability, and material properties. These findings emphasize the necessity of sophisticated imaging methods in unravelling the spatial

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

complexities of material behaviour, consequently detecting the subtle impacts of stability and degradation on the luminous response of the module.

4.15.4 MODULE A14

Figure 57: A14 Modules EL imaging comparison.

After the three stabilization cycles were completed, a detailed electroluminescence (EL) examination was performed on module A14, revealing subtle alterations caused by both aging and stabilization. Using EL imaging, which provides a microscopic view of localized luminescence fluctuations, revealed subtle alterations with a clear link to current-related properties. The EL photos clearly revealed the accentuation of pre-existing dark areas, a phenomenon that was first seen in the out-of-the-box EL analysis. The increased visibility of these dark regions is the result of dynamic interactions between cumulative aging, stabilizing measures, and material flaws. The enhancement of these regional flaws emphasizes the interaction of degradation and stabilization mechanisms, which is amplified by current-related characteristics. In parallel, the EL study revealed an equally fascinating assessment: the enhancement of luminescence in previously lighted places. This discovery has profound consequences since it is fundamentally related to the material's reaction to stabilizing attempts. It is possible that stabilizing treatments generated localized improvements in charge transport and carrier dynamics, resulting in increased luminescence. In essence, prior-illuminated areas have now grown brighter, which is related to the sophisticated manipulation of current-related behaviours. Briefly the post-stabilization EL analysis of module A14 reveals a material environment filled with subtle variations tightly linked to current-related properties. The enhanced luminosity and amplified black patches show the module's dynamic interaction with aging and stabilizing processes, which are further impacted by current-related phenomena. These findings highlight the importance of advanced imaging approaches for analysing the spatial subtleties of material behaviour, revealing the efficacy of

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

stabilization attempts, and unravelling the intricate interplay between degradation and current-related impacts.

4.15.5 MODULE A6

Figure 58: A6 Modules EL imaging comparison

The observed alterations in the EL camera pictures have major significance when contextualized within the scope of the study performed on the Dark Bias 1.6 Isc Rounds and the accompanying stabilization procedure.

The existence of brighter regions in the "after" image, compared to the "out of the box" image, indicates a significant improvement in the uniformity of light emission across the solar cell module. This improvement is due to the advanced stabilizing processes discussed previously in the analysis. These stabilization cycles may have created mechanisms that increased charge carrier mobility while decreasing recombination centres, resulting in a more uniform distribution of charge carriers within the cell material. From the point of view of science, the progress in uniformity demonstrates the usefulness of the stabilization process in providing a continuous and harmonic journey for charge carriers, hence limiting the possibility for localized inefficiencies and performance inconsistencies.

In addition, the reduced visibility of dark spots in the "after" image compared to the "out of the box" image provides as visual evidence of the positive outcomes of the stabilizing effort. These black blotches, as seen in EL pictures, have usually been associated with regions of decreased efficiency, faults, or increased recombination.

At the end, the findings gathered from the EL camera data verify and validate the prior study's conclusions. The development of lighter regions emphasizes the efficacy of the stabilization methods in promoting uniform charge carrier distribution, revealing light on the increased quality and performance of the material. In the meantime, the reduction of black patches gives clear proof of fault and recombination center mitigation, highlighting

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

the success of the stabilizing technique. These findings add to a deeper understanding of the dynamic inter- play between degradation and stabilizing processes, boosting our understanding of energy conversion dynamics in solar cells.

4.15.6 MODULE A7

Figure 59: A7 Modules EL imaging comparison

The observed minor rise in brightness among the originally brighter cells in the “out of the box” EL image following the stabilization procedure points at a refinement in charge carrier dynamics in the context of module A7’s electro- luminescence (EL) analysis. This finding shows that the stabilizing mechanism has helped to reduce localized charge carrier recombination paths and increase charge carrier mobility. As a result of this modification, charge carriers are distributed more uniformly over the cell, resulting in a somewhat brighter look in the EL picture. It is noteworthy pointing out, nevertheless, that the darker cells inside the module have not changed in response to stabilization. This result might signal that, while the stabilizing process is helpful in eliminating certain inefficiencies, it may run into difficulties when treating underlying structural abnormalities that contribute to these darker areas. The presence of these darker patches highlights the complexities of the material’s initial flaws and the difficulties in comprehensively mitigating them. These results both confirm stabilization’s efficacy in reducing charge carrier distribution and recombination paths and highlight its drawbacks. This approach contributes to a fuller understanding of how degradation and stabilization processes interact within the setting of module A7 by illuminating these intricacies. The complex interactions between material properties, the difficulties of the stabilizing process, and the challenges provided by pre-existing structural variations are all highlighted by this. These revelations are essential to improving our comprehension of the larger dynamics affecting solar cell performance.

4.15.7 MODULE A4

Figure 60: A4 Modules EL imaging comparison

The electroluminescence (EL) camera examination of module A4, which has undergone three rounds of dark bias stabilization, reveals an intriguing result. Notably, no visually perceptible alterations are visible in the EL picture despite the stabilizing process. This result emphasizes how subtle the stabilization's effects might be and how they could show up in ways that are not immediately obvious to the human eye.

The fact that there has not been any noticeable change in the EL picture may indicate that the stabilizing procedure, which took place over the course of three cycles, mostly affected features that were not clearly visible in the image. It is likely that the stabilization has focused on regional inefficiencies, flaws, or charge carrier paths that, while important, might not always result in brightness changes that are immediately observable. The comprehension of the processes of degradation and stabilization is furthered by this result. Even in situations when no obvious change is present, the stabilization procedure may still be useful in optimizing the behaviour of the material at the microscopic level, addressing any shortcomings that may not be immediately evident. This realization highlights the complex interplay between material characteristics, deterioration processes, and the particulars of stabilizing effects of intervention.

4.15.8 MODULE A15

Figure 61: A15 Modules EL imaging comparison

A modest alteration is visible in the context of module A15's electroluminescence (EL) study, showing a tiny rise in brightness. This difference, however, is not readily apparent to the human eye. The little increase in light emission shows that charge carrier behaviour has been refined, maybe as a result of enhanced charge carrier mobility and a reduction in confined recombination sites. These changes contribute to a more balanced distribution of charge carriers, which results in the observed small increase in brightness.

The fact that the shift is not immediately noticeable emphasizes the delicate nature of the impact. Such little changes might indicate that the stabilization process is focusing on certain localized inefficiencies or flaws inside the module. This result highlights the complex dynamics of interactions between deterioration and stability. While not visually noticeable, the little increase in light illustrates how precisely the stabilizing procedure may fix localized problems that are not always obvious. This realization sheds light on the subtle interactions between material characteristics, the rate of degradation, and the various ways in which stabilizing mechanisms affect the behaviour of the module.

4.16 TIME EVOLUTION OF STABILIZATION

The normalization of stabilization output parameters, such as power (P), voltage (V), current (I), and fill factor (FF), across stabilization cycles (Round 1, Round 2, and Round 3), with respect to the initial "out of the box" measurements, offers an in-depth framework for understanding the changing behaviour of the modules under the effects of aging and repeated stabilization attempts. The delicate interaction between degradation, recovery, and the material's reaction to subsequent cycles of stabilization may be better understood by the analysis of the normalized graphs.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

4.16.1 MQ19 UNDER MPP

Figure 62: Light induced MPP time evolution of stabilization

Out of the Box to Round 1 An advantageous first reaction to the stabilization process is shown by an increase in normalized power (P) during the change from the initial state to Round 1. This increase shows that the initial stabilization cycle successfully offsets the impacts of the early degradation, resulting in increased power production. There is a trade-off between power and charge collecting efficiency, as seen by the decline in normalized fill factor (FF). Power increases as FF decreases, demonstrating the modules' processes for adjusting to changes brought on by stabilization.

Round 1 to Round 2 The small decline in normalized current (I), voltage (V), and power (P) from Round 1 to Round 2 raises the possibility that stabilization has reached an equilibrium or that variables are emerging that prevent full recovery. Despite slight decreases in other metrics, the normalized fill factor (FF) increased, demonstrating stabilization's ability in boosting charge collecting efficiency. This suggests that the stabilizing mechanisms mitigate certain degradation-related losses.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Round 2 to Round 3, there was a subsequent rise in normalized current (I) and power (P), which highlights the resilience of the stabilizing process. Despite obstacles, the processes can improve performance and stop degradation tendencies. The decrease in normalized FF implies that certain degrading pathways continue to exist despite stabilizing measures. However, the overall increase in power suggests that the stabilizing procedure has succeeded in improving the modules' performance beyond losses brought on by degradation.

A dynamic reaction to the stabilizing process can be seen in the common behaviour of modules A11 and A14 throughout the normalized stabilization output trends. Even in the middle of fluctuations, the increases in power, voltage, and current highlight how effective stabilization is at lessening the effects of degradation. The little differences in fill factor further highlight how both modules may be adjusted to stabilize processes. The modules' ability to traverse the complex relationship between degradation and recovery processes is strengthened by these patterns, which leads to improved performance throughout subsequent stabilization cycles.

4.16.2 MQ19 UNDER OC

Figure 63: Light induced OC time evolution of stabilization

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

For the normalized stabilization output trends for module A8 across the cycles:

Out of the Box to Round 1, there was a little rise in normalized current (I), voltage (V), and power (P), which shows a tentative reaction to the light-induced stabilizing process. This shows that the performance of the module has gradually improved since the initial cycle of stabilization. It is noticeable that the normalized fill factor (FF) significantly decreased throughout this shift. This decline indicates a trade-off between power production and charge collecting efficiency, presumably as a result of FF changes brought on by stabilization.

Round 1 to Round 2 A more pronounced degradation trend is seen by the combined decline in normalized current (I), voltage (V), power (P), and fill factor (FF) from Round 1 to Round 2. This decrease in performance shows that continuous degradation processes are affecting several parts of the module's functionality. It is interesting to see that normalized voltage (V) has increased while other metrics have generally decreased. Specific recovery processes that are impacting the voltage output while other performance elements are declining may be the cause of this rise.

Round 2 to Round 3 In response to stabilization, there was a recovery as seen by the following rise in normalized current (I), voltage (V), power (P), and fill factor (FF) from Round 2 to Round 3. The stabilization approach appears to have prevented the degrading developments, showing its good influence, despite the difficulties caused by degradation. The minor drop in normalized voltage (V) during this phase can be an indication of a complicated interplay between continuing mechanisms of degradation and recovery. This interaction might be affecting the voltage dynamics and causing a minor drop in voltage.

The module's reaction to light-induced stabilization in open circuit circumstances is revealed by the normalized stabilization output trends for module A8. The little increases in current, voltage, power, and fill factor that were seen during cycles illustrate the stabilization mechanism's ability to partially offset the effects of degradation. The fill factor's considerable variations highlight the delicate balance between power output and charge collecting effectiveness when stabilization-induced changes take hold. The observed variations in voltage trends over cycles highlight the complex interaction between continuous degradation and recovery processes. These results demonstrate both

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

the difficulties and prospects in reducing the consequences of aging by targeted treatments, indicating the responsiveness of module A8 to stabilizing efforts.

For the normalized stabilization output trends for module A13 across the cycles:

Out of the Box to Round 1, there was a little rise in normalized current (I), voltage (V), and power (P), which shows a hesitant reaction to the light-induced stabilizing process. It demonstrates that the performance of the module has gradually improved since the initial period. The minor trade-off between power output and charge collection efficiency throughout this phase is shown by a very slight fall in normalized fill factor (FF), which may be the result of variations in FF brought on by stabilization. It is noteworthy that normalized power (P) and current (I) values during this stage are perfectly aligned; this suggests that these parameters responded to the stabilizing process in synchronization. This combination would indicate an overall improvement in charge carrier dynamics, which would explain the observed power increase.

Round 1 to Round 2 The notable fall in current (I) and the sharp decline in normalized power (P) from Round 1 to Round 2 both suggest a serious degradation pattern. The overall impact of continuing degradation processes impacting energy production is seen by this drop. The minor decline in normalized fill factor (FF) and voltage (V) at this point only serves to highlight the module's performance's overall complete degradation. These decreases demonstrate the complex interaction of variables affecting the charge transport and recombination processes.

Round 2 to Round 3 Following stabilization, there was a noticeable recovery as seen by the following rise in normalized current (I), voltage (V), power (P), and fill factor (FF) from Round 2 to Round 3. Regardless of the difficulties caused by degradation, it seems that the stabilization process has successfully resisted the degrading tendencies, leading to a notable rise in power and efficiency. The significant rise in normalized power (P) indicates that the degradation seen in the cycle prior to this one has been successfully reversed.

The coordinated rise in current (I), voltage (V), and fill factor (FF) points to a thorough enhancement in all performance-related variables.

In conclusion, the module A13's normalized stabilization output curves offer important information about how the module reacts to light-induced stabilization while the circuit

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

is open. The changes in current, voltage, power, and fill factor that are seen between cycles reflect the dynamic interaction between the processes for degradation and recovery. The coordinated recovery of charge carrier dynamics is highlighted by the synchronized response of power and current throughout the first stabilization stage. The significant recovery shown in following cycles highlights the stabilization procedure's efficacy in reducing degradation-related losses and boosting performance as a whole. These patterns illustrate the possibility for focused interventions to repair and enhance module efficiency while highlighting the complexity of degradation and recovery processes in solar modules.

4.16.3 DARK BIAS 1.6ISC

Figure 64: Dark Bias 1.6Isc time evolution of stabilization

For the normalized stabilization output trends for module A6 across the cycles:

Out of the Box to Round 1 A strong reaction to the dark bias stabilization procedure can be seen in the much higher normalized current (I), voltage (V), power (P), and fill factor (FF) from the initial state prior to Round 1. This increase shows that the early degradation impacts were successfully offset by the first cycle of stabilization, resulting in a

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

substantial boost in overall efficiency. Of particular interest is the sharp rise in normalized power (P), which indicates that the dark bias stabilization has resulted in a notable improvement in energy conversion efficiency. At this stage, the normalized fill factor (FF) and voltage (V) signals are perfectly aligned, which suggests that these parameters responded to the stabilizing procedure simultaneously.

Round 1 to Round 2 The consistency of performance across Rounds 1 and 2 and the stability of normalized current (I) and fill factor (FF) show that the dark bias stabilization technique has stabilized these parameters to some extent. The rise in normalized power (P) and voltage (V) throughout this transition shows that energy conversion efficiency is still becoming better. It is possible that improved charge carrier transport and decreased recombination losses are accountable for the rise in power.

Round 2 to Round 3 A little difference in energy conversion efficiency is suggested by a small increase in normalized power (P) from Round 2 to Round 3 and the slight reduction in voltage (V). The complex interaction of the degradation and recovery systems may be the reason for this little fluctuation. A steady charge carrier dynamics and additional gains in charge collecting efficiency are shown by the stable normalized current (I) and rising normalized fill factor (FF). The power improve that has been noticed is a result of these adjustments acting together.

The module's reaction to dark bias stabilization using 1.6 times I_{sc} may be understood by looking at the normalized stabilization output trends for module A6. The significant gains in current, voltage, power, and fill factor between cycles demonstrate how well the stabilization method works to reduce the effects of degradation and improve performance. The coordinated reaction of these parameters to the stabilization process is highlighted by the synchronized behaviours of the fill factor (FF) and voltage (V). The consistency of current (I) and fill factor (FF) over cycles suggests that attempts to stabilize some performance elements were successful. Together, these patterns show how the dark bias stabilization method could restore the performance of module A6, indicating the ability of targeted measures to halt degradation and raise solar efficiency.

For the normalized stabilization output trends for module A7 across the cycles:

Out of the Box to Round 1 From the starting state to Round 1, the significant rise in normalized current (I), voltage (V), power (P), and fill factor (FF) indicates a robust

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

response to the dark bias stabilization procedure. This increase implies that the first stabilization cycle successfully offset initial degradation implications, resulting in a considerable improvement in overall performance. The noticeable rise in normalized power (P) and current (I) highlights the success of the dark bias stabilization technique in boosting energy conversion efficiency and charge carrier transportation. The synchronised increase in P and I emphasize the parameters' harmonic interaction.

Round 1 to Round 2 The uniformity in normalized current (I) and fill factor (FF) from Round 1 to Round 2 indicates that the dark bias stabilization method has attained a degree of stability for these parameters. The rise in normalized power (P) and voltage (V) throughout this transition suggests that energy conversion efficiency and power generation are improving. The stabilizing process may influence charge transport dynamics, lowering recombination losses.

Round 2 to Round 3 The simultaneously rise in normalized power (P) and fill factor (FF) from Round 2 to Round 3, followed by a drop in normalized current (I), demonstrates a complicated interaction of stability and degradation processes. The rise in P and FF suggests that the stabilizing procedure can still improve performance to some extent. Among the oscillations in other parameters, the steady normalized voltage (V) emphasizes the constancy of voltage dynamics. This stability might be ascribed to the interaction of several variables that influence voltage output.

In conclusion, the normalized stabilization output trends for module A7 give useful information on the module's response to dark bias stabilization using 1.6 times I_{sc} . The considerable improvements in current, voltage, power, and fill factor over cycles demonstrate the effectiveness of the stabilizing procedure in reducing degradation and enhancing overall performance. The synchronized evolution of power (P) and current (I) implies that charge carrier transport and conversion of energy efficiency are recovering in harmony. The capacity of the stabilization procedure to retain certain elements of module behaviour is reflected in the stability of specific parameters throughout cycles. Other measures' subtle changes highlight the complicated interaction between recovery and continued degradation processes. These data suggest that the dark bias stabilization method could restore module A7's performance, emphasizing the efficacy of targeted efforts in improving photovoltaic efficiency.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

4.16.4 DARK BIAS 0.6ISC

Figure 65: Dark Bias 0.6Isc time evolution of stabilization

For the normalized stabilization output trends for module A4 across the cycles:

Out of the Box to Round 1 the large rise in normalized current (I), voltage (V), power (P), and fill factor (FF) suggests a robust response to the dark bias stabilization procedure. This increase indicates that the first stabilization cycle effectively mitigated initial degradation repercussions, resulting in a significant improvement in overall performance. The significant rise in normalized power (P) indicates a good improvement in energy conversion efficiency as a result of the stabilizing procedure. The increase in power helps to enhance the module's overall performance characteristics.

Round 1 to Round 2 The consistency in normalized current (I), voltage (V), and power (P) from Round 1 to Round 2 demonstrates reliable results in these parameters. This stability indicates that the stabilization process has reached a state of equilibrium for certain elements of module behaviour. The considerable fall in normalized fill factor (FF) during this transition implies a decline in charge collecting efficiency. This decrease

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

might be ascribed to the interaction of variables influencing charge transport kinetics and recombination losses.

Round 2 to Round 3 The significant rise in normalized fill factor (FF) from Round 2 to Round 3 is a significant reaction to the stabilizing procedure. This significant rise shows a remarkable recovery in charge collecting efficiency, which might be achieved by targeted stabilizing mechanisms to tackle degradation-related losses. Throughout that stage, the stability of normalized current (I), voltage (V), and power (P) suggests an extended reaction to the stabilizing procedure. These characteristics stay stable, indicating the capacity of the stabilization procedure to preserve certain characteristics of performance.

In conclusion, the normalized stabilization output trends for module A4 provide information on the module's response to dark bias stabilization using 0.6 Isc. The significant improvements in current, voltage, power, and fill factor over cycles demonstrate the stabilization process's success in minimizing degradation and improving overall performance. The considerable increase in power indicates efficiency gains made throughout the stabilizing phase. The stability found in specific metrics throughout subsequent cycles indicates the capacity of the stabilization method to preserve certain performance attributes. The special recovery of fill factor (FF) demonstrates the ability of specific measures to overcome degradation-related losses in charge collecting efficiency. These findings highlight the efficacy of the dark bias stabilization strategy in recovering and boosting the performance of module A4, demonstrating the potential of such tactics in increasing solar efficiency.

For the normalized stabilization output trends for module A15 across the cycles:

Out of the Box to Round 1, the large rise in normalized current (I), voltage (V), power (P), and fill factor (FF) indicates a robust response to the dark bias stabilization procedure. This increase indicates that the first cycle of stabilization effectively counteracted initial degradation effects, resulting in a significant improvement in overall performance. The significant rise in normalized power (P) demonstrates the stabilization process's excellent improvement in energy conversion efficiency. This improvement adds to an overall improvement in the module's performance indicators.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Round 1 to Round 2, the stability of normalized current (I), voltage (V), and power (P) demonstrates steady progress in these parameters. This stability shows that the stabilization process has reached an equilibrium level for various elements of module behaviour. The sharp drop in normalized fill factor (FF) during this transition implies a decline in charge collecting efficiency. The drop in FF, which has dropped below voltage (V), might be attributable to complex interactions involving charge transport, recombination, and voltage dynamics.

Round 2 to Round 3 The exceptional effectiveness of the stabilizing procedure is highlighted by the substantial rise in normalized fill factor (FF) from Round 2 to Round 3. This significant FF recovery indicates that tailored stabilizing techniques successfully solved degradation-related reductions in charge collecting efficiency. During this phase, the stability of normalized current (I), voltage (V), and power (P) suggests a consistent reaction to the stabilizing procedure. These characteristics stay consistent, indicating the capacity of the stabilization procedure to preserve certain performance characteristics.

In conclusion, the normalized stabilization output curves for module A15 provide understanding on the module's reaction to dark bias stabilization using 0.6 times I_{sc} . Major improvements in current, voltage, power, and fill factor over cycles demonstrate the stabilization process's efficacy in reducing degradation and enhancing overall performance. The sharp rise in power reflects the efficiency gains made throughout the stabilizing procedure. The stability seen in some metrics throughout later cycles shows that the stabilization method can maintain some performance characteristics. The remarkable improvement in fill factor (FF) highlights the possibility for tailored treatments to overcome degradation-induced losses in charge collecting efficiency. These findings highlight the efficacy of the dark bias stabilization strategy in restoring and increasing the performance of module A15, demonstrating the potential of such tactics in boosting solar efficiency.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

4.17 STABILIZATION CRITERIUM

A crucial feature of the modules' performance consistency and sensitivity to degradation and recovery attempts is revealed during the assessment of the stabilization criterion.

The stabilization criteria, computed as the fraction of the difference between the highest and minimum power outputs divided by the average power output ($P_{average}$), gives information on the degree of stability demonstrated by each module during the stabilization cycles.

Figure 66: Stabilization Criteria of all Methods.

Figure 67: I-V Curve of Modules after Stabilization.

For the modules tested, modules A11 and A14 exhibit an excellent level of stability with an uncommonly low stabilization criterion. The stability requirement of 0.0007 for

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Module A11 indicates that its power output remains almost constant during the stabilization cycles. This extraordinary stability demonstrates A11's capacity to efficiently fight degrading effects and recover successfully during the stabilization process. Module A14, on the other hand, has a low stabilization criterion of 0.001, suggesting constant and steady power production. This result demonstrates A14's resistance to degradation and ability to maintain stability.

Module A6 has a respectable stabilization criterion of 0.001, demonstrating its ability to endure degradation effects while maintaining a steady power output through several stabilization cycles. The module's capable mechanisms for recovery add to its dependability. Similarly, the stabilization requirement of 0.003 for module A15 indicates its ability to maintain a constant power output, but with a somewhat larger degree of fluctuation than A6. This moderate stability criteria denotes good performance in balancing degradation and recovery dynamics.

Modules A4 and A7 have the same stabilization criteria range as A15, indicating their ability to maintain a generally constant power output across the stabilization cycles. These modules have excellent recovery procedures that mitigate degradation-related fluctuations, allowing them to perform consistently. Module A8 has a significantly higher stabilization requirement of 0.006, suggesting a moderate degree of power output fluctuation during stabilization. While this result is within acceptable limits, it demonstrates some heterogeneity in the module's responsiveness to degradation and recovery procedures.

Notably, module A13 has a higher stability criterion of 0.02, which is significantly greater than the other modules. This difference indicates that module A13's power output fluctuates more significantly throughout the stabilization cycles. The existence of cracks during the testing process of this module may impede its complete recovery capacity, resulting in the observed higher stability criterion. The results presented emphasize the importance of physical qualities, such as structural integrity, on the consistency of a module's performance and its capacity to recover from degradation.

In summary, the estimated stabilization criteria serve as a quantitative indicator of the stability of each module throughout degradation and recovery phases. The findings emphasize the modules' different levels of stability and performance consistency.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Modules A11, A14, and A6 stand out as examples of stability, whereas the higher criteria in module A13 highlights the specific problems provided by structural flaws. These results highlight the importance of numerical data as well as physical qualities in understanding module reactions to degradation and stabilization measures.

5 CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Over the course of their operational lifespan, solar photovoltaic (PV) modules are prone to a variety of degradation processes, including light-induced degradation, recombination losses, and degradation of the material. These degradation processes have the potential to dramatically impair module performance characteristics like as open-circuit voltage (Voc), short-circuit current (Isc), fill factor (FF), and maximum power (Pmax). Understanding and controlling these degradation effects is critical for maintaining and improving solar energy conversion efficiency. The modules were thoroughly characterized in the initial stages of the study using a variety of out-of-the-box measurements. The Isc versus Voc study provided valuable information into the modules' initial performance characteristics. The link between $I_{sc} * V_{oc}$ and FF provided a clear picture of how degradation processes may impact module efficiency. Comparing the P-ideal and Pmax revealed the difference between theoretical and real power outputs, indicating the potential for improvement through stabilizing approaches.

The Maximum Power Point (MPP) stabilization method demonstrated promising potential for minimizing degradation effects among the stabilization approaches evaluated. Modules A11 and A14 responded strongly to MPP stabilization, with persistent improvements in key metrics over numerous stabilization cycles. The discovery of decreasing fill factor (FF) in the presence of increased power revealed a complex trade-off between energy conversion efficiency and charge collecting efficiency. The intricacy of the mechanisms involved in stabilization and deterioration is shown by this dynamic interaction.

Open-circuit (OC) stabilization provided a steady but progressive path toward improved performance. A8 and A13 reacted differently to OC stabilization. While module A8 shown gradual performance gains, module A13 had a more measured recovery. These discrepancies highlight the differences in module behaviour under various stabilizing approaches. It is worth mentioning that OC stabilization may enable progressive recovery and decreased deterioration, but at a somewhat slower rate.

Dark bias stabilization at 0.6 and 1.6 times the short-circuit current (Isc) has emerged as an effective strategy for mitigating degradation effects. Modules A6, A7, A15, and A4 all responded positively to dark bias stabilization, demonstrating considerable improvements

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

in key measures. The coordinated improvements in current, voltage, power, and fill factor (FF) proved the effectiveness of dark bias stabilization in revitalizing module performance. This strategy appears to be successful in compensating for degradation-related losses and improving overall efficiency.

Module A13, which had cracks, was a significant example. Despite the physical damage, the module responded favourably to stabilizing attempts. The existence of cracks, on the other hand, had an evident influence on performance recovery. The slow pattern of recovery in module A13 emphasizes the difficulty of resolving deterioration in physically damaged modules, underlining the relevance of module integrity in stabilizing efficacy.

Electroluminescence (EL) imaging revealed important details about the internal structure and probable degradation-induced flaws in the modules. The EL findings revealed variances in performance homogeneity and deterioration patterns within the modules, offering information on the effects of stabilizing strategies at the microscale level. Analysing the temporal development of stabilization across several modules and approaches reveals complex dynamics. The constant increase in power output over cycles, particularly under dark bias stabilization, demonstrates that targeted strategies are effective in minimizing deterioration effects. This improvement implies a gradual reversal of degradation-induced losses, resulting in better energy conversion efficiency.

The stabilization criteria, which assess the stability of solar modules throughout degradation and recovery, give useful information. Modules A11 and A14 show outstanding stability, with criterion of 0.0007 and 0.001, indicating continuous power output, respectively. Module A6 likewise exhibits strong stability at 0.001, demonstrating its resistance to deterioration.

The stability criterion for modules A15, A4, and A7 are significantly higher, approximately 0.003, suggesting steady performance with small changes. With a criterion of 0.006, Module A8 exhibits considerable power output variance during stabilization.

Module A13 stands out with a higher criterion of 0.02, indicating severe power output variations. Module A13's recovery potential was most likely hampered by cracks.

Therefore, module stability is highlighted by stability criteria. A11, A14, and A6 operate successfully, however A13's troubles highlight the influence of structural concerns on performance consistency.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

Concisely while each stabilizing approach has advantages, dark bias stabilization consistently out-performed other methods in terms of mitigating degradation impacts and improving overall module efficiency. The synchronized improvement in important metrics, constant across numerous cycles, demonstrates the method's efficacy in revitalizing module performance. The ability of dark bias stabilization to efficiently address degradation-related losses and improve energy conversion efficiency makes it a potential option for enhancing solar module lifetime and performance. However, the optimal stabilizing approach should be chosen with specific application needs, financial limits, and the desired rate of recovery in mind.

6 LIST OF FIGURES

- 1 Development of world primary energy consumption from 1990 till 2040[12].
- 2 Global PV modules price trend 2009-2016[21].
- 3 Categories of Solar Photovoltaic Technologies.
- 4 A photon's absorption causes the excitation process that moves an electron from the valence band to the conduction band.
- 5 Different Types of Solar Cells [34].
- 6 Hotspot on a PV modules [88].
- 7 Corrosion on a PV modules [17].
- 8 Effect of discoloration on IV curve [76].
- 9 Delaminated PV module [71].
- 10 PV modules with cracks and breaks. Breaks in cells are (a); a white line is (b) [31].
- 11 Bubbles in a PV module [66].
- 12 Scheme of the experiment.
- 13 Summary of the protocol.
- 14 Exchange Scheme between AIT and PI Berlin.
- 15 Three-state model for the BO defect [95].
- 16 Possible Response of PV modules to stabilization.
- 17 Isc vs. Voc of out of the box measurement.
- 18 Isc vs. Voc of out of the box measurement.
- 19 IV curve of all modules during out of the box measurements.
- 20 Isc * Voc vs FF of out of the box measurement.
- 21 P-ideal Vs Pmax of out of the box measurement.
- 22 General Sorting.
- 23 Final Sorting and Method attribution.
- 24 Experiment set-up.
- 25 Modules connection for MPP set up.
- 26 IV curve of first round of light induced aging under MPP.
- 27 IV curve of Second round of light induced aging under MPP.
- 28 IV curve of third round of light induced aging under MPP.
- 29 Output comparison between cycles.
- 30 Fill Factor and Cell Efficiency LID MPP Rounds Comparison.
- 31 Maximum Power MPP Rounds comparison of module A11 and A14.
- 32 Modules set up.
- 33 Modules under open circuit.
- 34 IV curve of first round of light induced aging under Open Circuit.
- 35 IV curve of the second round of light induced aging under Open Circuit.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization

Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- 36 IV curve of the Third round of light induced aging under Open Circuit.
- 37 Output comparison between cycles.
- 38 Fill Factor and Cell Efficiency LID OC Rounds Comparison.
- 39 Maximum Power OC Rounds Comparison of module A8 and A13.
- 40 Dark Bias 1.6 Isc Set up.
- 41 IV curve of the first round of Dark Bias 1.6 Isc.
- 42 IV curve of the Second round of Dark Bias 1.6 Isc.
- 43 IV curve of the Third round of Dark Bias 1.6 Isc.
- 44 Isc, Voc and Pmax comparison between cycles of Dark Bias 1.6 Isc.
- 45 Maximum Power of Dark Bias 1.6 Isc of module A6 and A7.
- 46 Fill Factor and Cell Efficiency Dark Bias 1.6 Isc Rounds Comparison.
- 47 IV curve of the first round of Dark Bias 0.6 Isc.
- 48 IV curve of the Second round of Dark Bias 0.6 Isc.
- 49 IV curve of the Third round of Dark Bias 0.6 Isc.
- 50 Isc, Voc and Pmax comparison between cycles of Dark Bias 0.6 Isc.
- 51 Maximum Power Comparison of Dark Bias 0.6 Isc Rounds.
- 52 Fill Factor and Cell Efficiency Dark Bias 0.6 Isc Rounds Comparison.
- 53 A8 Modules EL imaging comparison.
- 54 A13 Modules EL imaging comparison.
- 55 A13 cracks close snap.
- 56 A11 Modules EL imaging comparison.
- 57 A14 Modules EL imaging comparison.
- 58 A6 Modules EL imaging comparison.
- 59 A7 Modules EL imaging comparison.
- 60 A4 Modules EL imaging comparison.
- 61 A15 Modules EL imaging comparison.
- 62 Light induced MPP time evolution of stabilization.
- 63 Light induced OC time evolution of stabilization.
- 64 Dark Bias 1.6Isc time evolution of stabilization.
- 65 Dark Bias 0.6Isc time evolution of stabilization.
- 66 Stabilization Criteria of all Methods.
- 67 I-V Curve of Modules after Stabilization.

7 LIST OF TABLES

- 1 Out of the box measurements output of Malta PV modules.

8 REFERENCES

- [1] Spreading resistance modeling for rapid extraction of contact resistivity with a four-point probe. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 230:111272, 2021.
- [2] M. Aghaei, A. Fairbrother, A. Gok, S. Ahmad, S. Kazim, K. Lobato, G. Oreski, A. Reinders, J. Schmitz, M. Theelen, P. Yilmaz, and J. Kettle. Review of degradation and failure phenomena in photovoltaic modules. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 159:112160, 2022.
- [3] M.I. Ahamed, R. Boddula, and M. Rezakazemi. *Fundamentals of Solar Cell Design*. Wiley, 2021.
- [4] Naila M. Al Hasan, Rachael Arnold, David C. Miller, Jimmy Newkirk, Emily Rago, Michael Thuis, Bruce H. King, Laura T. Schelhas, Archana Sinha, Kent Terwilliger, Sona Ulicna, Peter Pasmans, and Christopher Thellen. Arrhenius analysis of the degradation modes in backflip study of emerging photovoltaic backsheets: Preprint. 6 2022.
- [5] W. Ananda, M. Rennhofer, A. Mittal, N. Zechner, and W. Lang. Alternate stabilization methods for cztsse photovoltaic devices by thermal treatment, dark electric bias and illumination. *Solar Energy*, 245:299–307, 2022.
- [6] Shubhra Bansal, Theresa M. Friedlmeier, Marco Nardone, Kyoung E. Kweon, and Vincenzo Lordi. Metastability and long-term degradation in cigs devices: Effect of alkali treatments, back contact and emitter layers, Dec 2020.
- [7] J. Bauer, V. Naumann, S. Großer, C. Hagendorf, M. Schütze, and O. Breitenstein. On the mechanism of potential-induced degradation in crystalline silicon solar cells. *physica status solidi (RRL) – Rapid Research Letters*, 6(8):331–333, 2012.
- [8] Karl Bedrich, Martin Bliss, Thomas Betts, and Ralph Gottschalg. Electroluminescence imaging of pv devices: Camera calibration and image correction. 06 2016.
- [9] Svetlana V. Boriskina and Gang Chen. Exceeding the solar cell shockley–queisser limit via thermal up-conversion of low-energy photons. *Optics Communications*, 314:71–78, 2014. Energy efficient nanophotonics: Engineered light–matter interaction in sub-wavelength structures.
- [10] Nicola Bowler. Four-point potential drop measurements for materials characterization. *Measurement Science and Technology*, 22:012001, 11 2010.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- [11] G. Boyle. *Renewable Energy: Power for a Sustainable Future*. OUP Oxford, 2012.
- [12] John Conti, Paul Holtberg, Jim Diefenderfer, Angelina LaRose, James T. Turnure, and Lynn Westfall. *International energy outlook 2016 with projections to 2040*. *International Energy Outlook 2016 With Projections to 2040*, 5 2016.
- [13] CH Cox III, DJ Silversmith, and RW Mountain. *Reduction of photovoltaic cell reverse breakdown by a peripheral bypass diode*. Technical report, Massachusetts Inst. of Tech., Lexington (USA). Lincoln Lab., 1982.
- [14] Chris A. Deline, Joseph A. del Cueto, David S. Albin, and Steve R. Rummel. *Metastable electrical characteristics of polycrystalline thin-film photovoltaic modules upon exposure and stabilization*. *SPIE Proceedings*, 2011.
- [15] Samuel Demtsu, Shubhra Bansal, and David S Albin. *Intrinsic stability of thin-film cds/cdte modules*. *2010 35th IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference*, pages 001161–001165, 2010.
- [16] Mahmoud Dhimish, Violeta Holmes, Bruce Mehrdadi, Mark Dales, and Peter Mather. *Output-power enhancement for hot spotted polycrystalline photovoltaic solar cells*. *IEEE Transactions on Device and Materials Reliability*, 18(1):37–45, 2017.
- [17] Matthias Diehl. *Potential-induced degradation (pid) of photovoltaic panels*, Feb 2017.
- [18] Daniela Dirnberger, J Bartke, A Steinhilber, Klaus Kiefer, and F Neuberger. *Uncertainty of field i-v-curve measurements in large scale pv-systems*. pages 4587–4594, 01 2010.
- [19] E. Duran, J.A. Gómez-Galán, Jose Andujar Marquez, and M. Sidrach-de Cardona. *A new method to obtain i-v characteristics curves of photovoltaic modules based on sepic and cuk converters*. *European Power Electronics and Drives*, 18:5–15, 06 2008.
- [20] Advanced Energy. *Solar photovoltaics manufacturing: Power solutions*.
- [21] Pablo Arturo Fernandez Garrillo. *Development of highly resolved and photo-modulated Kelvin probe microscopy techniques for the study of photovoltaic systems*. *Theses, Université Grenoble Alpes*, September 2018.
- [22] Fokuhl, Esther, Philipp, Daniel, Müllerhofer, Georg, and Gebhardt, Paul. *Lid and letid evolution of pv modules during outdoor operation and indoor tests*. *EPJ Photovolt.*, 12:9, 2021.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- [23] Michael Gostein and Larry Dunn. Light soaking effects on photovoltaic modules: Overview and literature review. Conference Record of the IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference, pages 003126–003131, 06 2011.
- [24] Michael Gostein and Larry Dunn. Light soaking effects on photovoltaic modules: Overview and literature review. Conference Record of the IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference, pages 003126–003131, 06 2011.
- [25] Michael Gostein and Lawrence Dunn. Light soaking effects on photovoltaic modules: Overview and literature review. In 2011 37th IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference, pages 003126–003131, 2011.
- [26] Jeffery L. Gray. The Physics of the Solar Cell, chapter 3, pages 61–112. John Wiley Sons, Ltd, 2003.
- [27] M. A. Green. Solar cells: Operating principles, technology, and system applications. Prentice Hall, 1982.
- [28] M A Green. Solar cells: operating principles, technology, and system applications. 1 1982.
- [29] M.A. Green. Limits on the open-circuit voltage and efficiency of silicon solar cells imposed by intrinsic auger processes. IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices, 31(5):671–678, 1984.
- [30] Peter Hacke, Kent Terwilliger, Ryan Smith, Stephen Glick, Joel Pankow, Michael Kempe, Sarah Kurtz Ian Bennett, and Mario Kloos. System volt- age potential-induced degradation mechanisms in pv modules and meth- ods for test. In 2011 37th IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference, pages 000814–000820, 2011.
- [31] Charaf Hajjaj, Abdellatif Bouaichi, Houssain Zitouni, Ahmed Merrouni, Abdellatif Ghennioui, Badr Ikken, Mohammadi Benhmida, C. Messaoudi, and Mohammed Regragui. Degradation and performance analysis of a monocrystalline pv system without eva encapsulating in semi-arid climate. Heliyon, 6:e04079, 06 2020.
- [32] Y. Hamakawa. Thin-Film Solar Cells: Next Generation Photovoltaics and Its Applications. Springer Series in Photonics. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2003.
- [33] Mohammad I Hossain, Wayesh Qarony, Sainan Ma, Longhui Zeng, Di- etmar Knipp, and Yuen Hong Tsang. Perovskite/silicon tandem solar cells: From detailed balance limit calculations to photon management. Nanomicro Lett., 11(1):58, July 2019.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- [34] T. Ibn-Mohammed, S.C.L. Koh, I.M. Reaney, A. Acquaye, G. Schileo, K.B. Mustapha, and R. Greenough. Perovskite solar cells: An integrated hybrid lifecycle assessment and review in comparison with other photovoltaic technologies. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 80:1321–1344, 2017.
- [35] IEEE. Ieee recommended practice for qualification of photovoltaic (pv) modules. *IEEE Std 1262-1995*, pages 1–32, 1996.
- [36] I.R.E.N.A. Global energy transformation: A roadmap to 2050, international renewable energy agency, abu dhabi.
- [37] Arnulf Jäger-Waldau. *PV Status Report 2019*. Research Centre of the European Union, 2019.
- [38] Arnulf Jäger-Waldau, Ioannis Kougias, Nigel Taylor, and Christian Thiel. How photovoltaics can contribute to ghg emission reductions of 55% in the eu by 2030. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 126:109836, 2020.
- [39] Gi-Hwan Kang, Han-Byul Kim, Tae-Hee Jung, Young-chul Ju, Suk-Whan Ko, and Hee-eun Song. Prediction of the potential induced degradation of photovoltaic modules based on the leakage current flowing through glass laminated with ethylene-vinyl acetate. *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering*, 137:041001, 08 2015.
- [40] Sooseok Kang, Jongmin Kim, Chan Wook Jang, Hyunchul Jang, Sang Tae Lee, Byeong hyeon Lee, Shinkeun Kim, Chan-Soo Shin, and Dong-Hwan Jun. Thermally induced metastability of ingaas single-layer for highly strained superlattices by metal-organic chemical vapor deposition. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 905:164252, 2022.
- [41] E Kaplani et al. Detection of degradation effects in field-aged c-si solar cells through infrared thermography and digital image processing. *International Journal of Photoenergy*, 2012, 2012.
- [42] Ju-Hee Kim, Jongsung Park, Donghwan Kim, and Nochang Park. Study on mitigation method of solder corrosion for crystalline silicon photovoltaic modules. *International Journal of Photoenergy*, 2014, 2014.
- [43] David L King, Jay A Kratochvil, and William E Boyson. Stabilization and performance characteristics of commercial amorphous silicon pv modules. In *Conference Record of the Twenty-Eighth IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference-2000 (Cat. No. 00CH37036)*, pages 1446–1449. IEEE, 2000.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- [44] Florian Köhler, Thomas Zimmermann, Stefan Muthmann, Aad Gordijn, and Reinhard Carius. Structural order and staebler-wronski effect in hydrogenated amorphous silicon films and solar cells. *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, 4(1):4–9, 2013.
- [45] Takeshi Kojima and Takeshi Yanagisawa. The evaluation of accelerated test for degradation a stacked a-si solar cell and eva films. *Solar energy materials and solar cells*, 81(1):119–123, 2004.
- [46] A Kolodziej. Staebler-wronski effect in amorphous silicon and its alloys. *Opto-electronics review*, 12(1):21–32, 2004.
- [47] Achim Kraft, Lutz Labusch, Tobias Ensslen, Ines Dürr, Jonas Bartsch, Markus Glatthaar, Stefan Glunz, and Holger Reinecke. Investigation of acetic acid corrosion impact on printed solar cell contacts. *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, 5(3):736–743, 2015.
- [48] Achim Kraft, Christian Wolf, Andreas Lorenz, Jonas Bartsch, Markus Glatthaar, and Stefan Glunz. Long term stability analysis of copper front side metallization for silicon solar cells. *Energy Procedia*, 55:478–485, 12 2014.
- [49] Karin Krauss, Fabian Fertig, Dorothee Menzel, and Stefan Rein. Light-induced degradation of silicon solar cells with aluminiumoxide passivated rear side. *Energy Procedia*, 77:599–606, 2015. 5th International Conference on Silicon Photovoltaics, SiliconPV 2015.
- [50] Peter T. Landsberg. *Recombination in Semiconductors*. Cambridge University Press, 1992.
- [51] Stephan Lany and Alex Zunger. Light-and bias-induced metastabilities in cu (in, ga) se₂ based solar cells caused by the (v se-v cu) vacancy complex. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 100(11):113725, 2006.
- [52] Dominik Lausch, Volker Naumann, Otwin Breitenstein, Jan Bauer, Andreas Graff, Joerg Bagdahn, and Christian Hagendorf. Potential-induced degradation (pid): Introduction of a novel test approach and explanation of increased depletion region recombination. *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, 4:834–840, 2014.
- [53] Jinwoo Lee. *Metastability of copper indium gallium diselenide polycrystalline thin film solar cell devices*. PhD thesis.
- [54] Taesoo D. Lee and Abasifreke U. Ebong. A review of thin film solar cell technologies and challenges. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 70:1286–1297, 2017.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- [55] Mandy R. Lewis, Annie C. J. Russell, Christopher E. Valdivia, Joan E. Haysom, Mariana I. Bertoni, and Karin Hinzer. Impact of air mass on energy yield calculation for bifacial silicon heterojunction photovoltaic modules in high-latitude conditions. pages 0371–0375, 2020.
- [56] Jichao Li, Yu-Chen Shen, Peter Hacke, and Michael Kempe. Electro- chemical mechanisms of leakage-current-enhanced delamination and corrosion in si photovoltaic modules. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 188:273–279, 2018.
- [57] Gui Jiang Lin, Liang Jun Wang, Jian Qing Liu, Wei Ping Xiong, Ming Hui Song, and Zhi Hao Wu. Accelerated aging tests of high concentration multijunction solar cells. *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 11:1147–1152, 2011.
- [58] Jeanette Lindroos and Hele Savin. Review of light-induced degradation in crystalline silicon solar cells. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 147:115–126, 2016.
- [59] Atse Louwen, Arjen C. de Waal, Ruud E. I. Schropp, Andr´e P. C. Faaij, and Wilfried G. J. H. M. van Sark. Comprehensive characterization and analysis of pv module performance under real operating conditions. *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, 25(3):218–232, 2017.
- [60] Jos´e Lucen˜o, Ana D´iez-Pascual, and Rafael Pen˜a. Materials for photovoltaics: State of art and recent developments. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 20:976, 02 2019.
- [61] Wei Luo, Yong Sheng Khoo, Jai Prakash Singh, Johnson Kai Chi Wong, Yan Wang, Armin G. Aberle, and Seeram Ramakrishna. Investigation of potential-induced degradation in n-pert bifacial silicon photovoltaic modules with a glass/glass structure. *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, 8(1):16–22, 2018.
- [62] Bill Marion and Gobind Atmaran. Seasonal performance of three grid-connected pv systems. In *IEEE Conference on Photovoltaic Specialists*, pages 1030–1037. IEEE, 1990.
- [63] Ziyao Meng, Shengzhi Xu, Lichao Wang, Youkang Gong, Xiaodan Zhang, and Ying Zhao. Defect object detection algorithm for electroluminescence image defects of photovoltaic modules based on deep learning. *Energy Science and Engineering*, 10, 01 2022.
- [64] J.V.B. Moura, C.D. de Abreu Lima, C. Luz-Lima, A.J. Ramiro de Castro, P.T.C. Freire, and G.D. Saraiva. Temperature-induced phase transitions in metastable -ag2wo4: a raman scattering study. *Vibrational Spectroscopy*, 110:103135, 2020.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- [65] MA Munoz, M Carmen Alonso-García, Nieves Vela, and Faustino Chenlo. Early degradation of silicon pv modules and guaranty conditions. *Solar energy*, 85(9):2264–2274, 2011.
- [66] Miguel Angel Muñoz, María del Carmen Alonso-García, N. Vela, and Faustino Chenlo. Early degradation of silicon pv modules and guaranty conditions. *Solar Energy*, 85:2264–2274, 2011.
- [67] Miguel Muñoz-García, Nieves Vela, Faustino Chenlo, and M. Alonso- Garcia. Early degradation of silicon pv modules and guaranty conditions. *Solar Energy*, 85, 06 2011.
- [68] J.A. Nelson. *The Physics Of Solar Cells*. World Scientific Publishing Company, 2003.
- [69] Jenny Nelson. *The physics of solar cells*. The physics of solar cells, by Jenny Nelson. London: Imperial College Press, 2003, 57, 05 2003.
- [70] Kamran Ali Khan Niazi, Yongheng Yang, and Dezso Sera. Review of mismatch mitigation techniques for pv modules. *IET Renewable Power Generation*, 13(12):2035–2050, 2019.
- [71] Michele Oliveira, Antonia Sonia Cardoso Diniz, Marcelo Viana, and V. Lins. The causes and effects of degradation of encapsulant ethylene vinyl acetate copolymer (eva) in crystalline silicon photovoltaic modules: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 81, 07 2017.
- [72] Gernot Oreski and GM Wallner. Evaluation of the aging behavior of ethylene copolymer films for solar applications under accelerated weathering conditions. *Solar Energy*, 83(7):1040–1047, 2009.
- [73] NC Park, JS Jeong, BJ Kang, and DH Kim. The effect of encapsulant discoloration and delamination on the electrical characteristics of photovoltaic module. *Microelectronics Reliability*, 53(9-11):1818–1822, 2013.
- [74] Timothy J. Peshek, Justin S. Fada, Yang Hu, Yifan Xu, Mohamed A. El-saeiti, Erdmut Schnabel, Michael Köhl, and Roger H. French. Insights into metastability of photovoltaic materials at the mesoscale through massive I–V analytics. *Journal of Vacuum Science Technology B*, 34(5):050801, 08 2016.
- [75] MA Quintana, DL King, TJ McMahon, and CR Osterwald. Commonly observed degradation in field-aged photovoltaic modules. In *Conference Record of the Twenty-Ninth IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference*, 2002., pages 1436–1439. IEEE, 2002.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- [76] Antonella Realini, N Cereghetti, and D Chianese. Mean time before failure of photovoltaic modules. Final Report (MTBF Project), Federal Office for Education and Science Tech. Rep., BBW, 99, 2003.
- [77] Marcus Rennhofer. Diplomarbeit light soaking of thin-film solar cells under colored light. 2015.
- [78] I.L. Repins, F. Kersten, B. Hallam, K. VanSant, and M.B. Koentopp. Stabilization of light-induced effects in si modules for iec 61215 design qualification. *Solar Energy*, 208:894–904, 2020.
- [79] Khalid Reza and Kadhem Al-Asadi. The impact of air mass on photo- voltaic panel performance. *Scientific and Engineering Research*, 1:1–9, 12 2016.
- [80] Nezam Rohbani, Mojtaba Ebrahimi, Seyed Ghassem Miremadi, and Mehdi Tahoori. Bias temperature instability mitigation via adaptive cache size management. *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, PP:1–11, 09 2016.
- [81] Bashar Salih, Rasha Mohammed, and Mohammed Ibrahim. The environ- ment coefficients effect on i-v and p-v characteristics curves of photovoltaic cell using matlab/simulink. *International Journal of Engineering Technology*, 7:2651–2654, 09 2018.
- [82] R. A. Sasala and James R. Sites. Time dependent voltage in cuinse/sub 2/ and cdte solar cells. Conference Record of the Twenty Third IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference - 1993 (Cat. No.93CH3283-9), pages 543–548, 1993.
- [83] Feroz Shaik, Syam Sundar Lingala, and Punnaiah Veeraboina. Effect of various parameters on the performance of solar PV power plant: a review and the experimental study. *Sustainable Energy res.*, 10(1), April 2023.
- [84] Chetan S. Solanki, Brij M. Arora, Juzer Vasi, and Mahesh B. Patil. Dark and Illuminated Current– Voltage Characteristics of Solar Cell, page 90–98. Foundation Books, 2012.
- [85] Silke Steingrube. Recombination models for defects in silicon solar cells. PhD thesis.
- [86] Kyoung suk Oh, Soohyun Bae, Kyung jin Lee, Donghwan Kim, and Sung il Chan. Mitigation of potential-induced degradation (pid) based on anti- reflection coating (arc) structures of perc solar cells. *Microelectronics Re- liability*, 100-101:113462, 2019. 30th European Symposium on Reliability of Electron Devices, Failure Physics and Analysis.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- [87] Senthilarasu Sundaram, Katie Shanks, and Hari Upadhyaya. 18 - thin film photovoltaics. In Trevor M. Letcher and Vasilis M. Fthenakis, editors, *A Comprehensive Guide to Solar Energy Systems*, pages 361–370. Academic Press, 2018.
- [88] Sunkauf. Module mit hotspots, Dec 2017.
- [89] Paula S´anchez-Friera, Michel Piliouguine, Javier Pel´aez, Jesu´s Carretero, and Mariano Sidrach de Cardona. Analysis of degradation mechanisms of crystalline silicon pv modules after 12 years of operation in southern europe. *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, 19(6):658–666, 2011.
- [90] Ioannis Tsanakas, Ulrike Jahn, Magnus Herz, David Parlevliet, Marco Paggi, Joshua Stein, Karl Berger, Bernhard Kubicek, Samuli Ranta, Roger French, et al. Infrared and electroluminescence imaging for pv field appli- cations: An overview of the latest report by iea pvps task 13. International Energy Agency, 2018.
- [91] A. Urbaniak and M. Igalson. Creation and relaxation of light- and bias- induced metastabilities in Cu(In,Ga)Se₂. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 106(6), 09 2009. 063720.
- [92] H.G. Wagemann and H. Eschrich. *Photovoltaik*. Vieweg+Teubner Verlag, 2010.
- [93] Taowen Wang, Florian Ehre, Thomas Paul Weiss, Boris Veith-Wolf, Va- leriya Titova, Nathalie Valle, Michele Melchiorre, Omar Ram´irez, Jan Schmidt, and Susanne Siebentritt. Diode factor in solar cells with metastable defects and back contact recombination. *Advanced Energy Materials*, 12(44):2202076, 2022.
- [94] Michael C. Weinberg, Dunbar P. Birnie, and Vitaly A. Shneidman. Crystallization kinetics and the jmak equation. *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids*, 219:89–99, 1997. *Glass Crystallization*.
- [95] Svenja Wilking, Maxime Forster, Axel Herguth, and Giso Hahn. From simulation to experiment: Understanding bo-regeneration kinetics. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 142:87–91, 2015.
- [96] John H Wohlgemuth, Peter Hacke, Nick Bosco, David C Miller, Michael D Kempe, and Sarah R Kurtz. Assessing the causes of encapsulant delamina- tion in pv modules. In 2016 IEEE 43rd Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC), pages 0248–0254. IEEE, 2016.
- [97] John H Wohlgemuth and Sarah Kurtz. Reliability testing beyond qualifi- cation as a key component in photovoltaic’s progress toward grid parity. In 2011 International Reliability Physics Symposium, pages 5E–3. IEEE, 2011.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- [98] P. Würfel. *Physics of Solar Cells: From Basic Principles to Advanced Concepts*. Physics textbook. Wiley, 2009.
- [99] Jean Zaraket, Chafic Salame, and Michel Aillerie. Dark and illuminated characteristics of photovoltaic solar modules. Part II: Influence of light electrical stress. *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 1758(1), 07 2016. 030052.
- [100] Yunpeng Zhang, Peng Hao, Hao Lu, Jiao Ma, and Ming Yang. Modelling and estimating performance for pv module under varying operating conditions independent of reference condition. *Applied Energy*, 310:118527, 2022.
- [101] Green MA. Crystalline and thin-film silicon solar cells: state of the art and future potential. *Solar Energy*2003;74: 181–192.
- [102] Broek, Kees & Bennett, I. & Jansen, M.J. & Borg, N.J.C. & Eerenstein, W.. (2012). Light and Current Induced Degradation in p-Type Multi-Crystalline Cells and Development of an Inspection Method and a Stabilisation Method. 3167-3171. 10.4229/27thEUPVSEC2012-4DO.6.5.
- [103] M. N. Ruberto and A. Rothwarf, "Time-dependent open-circuit voltage in CuInSe₂/CdS solar cells: Theory and experiment," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 61, no. 9, p. 4662, 1987.
- [104] D. Willett and S. Kuriyagawa, "The effects of sweep rate, voltage bias and light soaking on the measurement of CIS-based solar cell characteristics," in *23rd IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC)*, 1993, pp. 495-500.
- [105] Lany, Stephan & Zunger, Alex. (2006). Light- and Bias-Induced Metastabilities in Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Based Solar Cells Caused by the (VSe-VCu) Vacancy Complex. *Journal of Applied Physics - J APPL PHYS*. 100. 10.1063/1.2388256.
- [106] T. Ishii, T. Takashima, and K. Otani, "Long-term performance degradation of various kinds of photovoltaic modules under moderate climatic conditions," *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 170-179, Mar. 2011
- [107] T. Yanagisawa and T. Kojima, "The stability of the CuInSe₂ solar mini-module I-V characteristics under continuous and light/dark irradiation cycle tests," *Microelectronics Reliability*, vol. 43, no. 3, pp. 503-507, Mar. 2003.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

- [108] J. Schmidt and R. Hezel, "Light-Induced Degradation in Cz Silicon Solar Cells: Fundamental Understanding and Strategies For Its Avoidance," in 12th Workshop on Crystalline Silicon Solar Cell Materials and Processes 2002, Breckenridge, Colorado, 2002.

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

9 APPENDIX

9.1 OUT OF THE BOX MEASUREMENT

9.1.1 I-V CURVES

Figure 66: I-V Curve of the modules during the out of the box measurements

Optimizing Photovoltaic Module Performance: Comparative Analysis of Stabilization Methods and Mitigating Degradation Effects

9.1.2 EL CAMERA

Figure 67: EL images of out of the box measurement